

Interview – 01

Play Pattern

1. PCVR

2. PC

Interviewer: Okay, so as I already said, it's more about how you felt about the game—the real raw feeling. We played both versions, and my main focuses are the immersion between the VR and the PC version, the control schemes (like both the controllers—which feels better in your hand, which feels more intuitive, which is easy to understand), and finally the comfort level on both versions.

Interviewer: In general, let's get some background about you. What type of games do you generally play and how often do you play them?

Participant: I usually play different games. Among my favorite genres are strategies—both real-time and turn-based. I also played Dota 2 a lot. I played a lot of World of Warcraft, MMORPGs. I think if the game is popular, there's a chance I played it, but not everything. I'm not like—I didn't play Death Stranding, right? I'm a PC gamer, that means I usually didn't play games that are exclusive to PlayStation unless they port it on PC like a year or two later. The last games that I finished were God of War Ragnarok and Spider-Man: Miles Morales, both on PS5 here in the lab. During the last two or three weeks, I played a lot of Civilization 6 and Anno 1800.

Interviewer: What about VR? Have you played any VR games before?

Participant: Yeah, I did. I played Vader Immortal—I finished it fully. I played some simple games. I tried VR Chat. I played some game where you play as a gorilla and communicate with other players. It's full of school children, by the way, but some of them are very nice and they taught me some mechanics there. I also used some applications. I played on Apple Vision Pro—there's some game they did with Disney about Thanos and the Infinity Stones. I didn't play too much on VR. I played a lot of Beat Saber just for fun. I tried to play Quake 3 as I said, but I got really nauseous because it's a really high-paced FPS shooter—it was too fast-paced for me. But mostly on VR I was doing and developing either virtual tours, virtual exhibitions, or 360 videos.

Interviewer: Great, so you played both versions. Which version did you enjoy the most?

Participant: I think I enjoyed more with the controller—PC on the PC.

Interviewer: Why do you feel that?

Participant: Maybe it was—I did it much faster. I completed the game much faster, the prototype. I just got stuck a couple of times in VR with these ladders and this climbing things that for me were difficult. I didn't find the control with the ladder intuitive for me personally, even though it's subject to controversy, of course. **I thought I would climb ladder like this, and without your input I wouldn't have guessed it. I think I would just be stuck probably.** But yeah, overall—even in this game with the gorilla, they have a lot of similar things where you need to grab stuff, and I also had a hard time there. **Even though for school children of 13-15 years old that play, they just naturally do it really easily and I can't wrap my head around it. So I don't know, maybe it's just me.**

Interviewer: So it's in general a struggle with traversal games?

Participant: Maybe yeah. Okay, and one thing about the controllers—the controls on VR. **I immediately wanted to strafe left and right like I do here, but I couldn't for some reason on VR. I can only move front and back and that really disturbed me. I'm like, "Okay, I really need to move sides" because this is what in most VR games you do.** On gamepads too—I think these controllers are just like gamepads, they're really similar, they have the same buttons even. Just naturally I wanted to move, and on PC version I could do it but in VR I couldn't. I think that maybe the reason was the cable, as of course I could just rotate around, but all the time rotating around and moving forward was really uncomfortable. I would rather prefer the strafing.

Interviewer: I think the intuition behind the design was I was quite concerned about people being motion sick. For example, me myself, I cannot handle sideways movement in VR because I get really sick very easily. That was my motivation—maybe I thought maybe there are more people like me. But I've got this complaint from two people already. My other friend also complained that it would have been great if I could move sideways.

Participant: **Also, with the right stick, the movement was choppy—you move and it's choppy. Whereas on PC it's smooth. I also would love maybe in VR game to be smoother motion of right stick.**

Interviewer: That's also related to the motion sickness issue.

Participant: Yeah. This is why I think for on the PC, on the controller, it was more comfortable.

Interviewer: Now the very important question. Because as you saw, the game design and the world design itself felt very dystopian—large buildings, robots all over, it's like feels very dead inside, there's no goodness. One of the very important thing was the heights of the buildings. How did you experience it between the VR version and the PC version itself? Because it's different in VR when you perceive the heights of the buildings in general as you're more immersed than playing from a controller.

Participant: I think in VR it felt higher and more around you. I think it was of course more immersive in some way. When you're there, it does feel like, Oh, it's really high."

Interviewer: When you look down, do you feel like, "Okay, I'm over a really high building"?

Participant: I didn't, even though I have the fear of heights, I didn't feel it in this game in particular. You saw me jumping down from there because there's no fall damage, and I cheated my way a little bit there. I mean, people are going to do that.

Interviewer: Now, one of the very important things of my thesis is the interaction difference between the two versions. In one, you're trying to do it with the controller—you're kind of playing a passive role, and in one, you're trying to, for example, climb the ladder very actively. How do you think it felt to you as a difference in the mechanics?

Participant: Okay, so first of all, maybe it's a bug, but in VR version the door was just opening when I approached it, and on the PC I had to press a button. I don't know—either in controller I also had to press a button, but I just moved in and it just registered maybe my controller as I moved it or something. But I don't think it works as intended.

It was more fun to climb the ladder, even though I had troubles at first. At some point I had fun climbing the ladder actively rather than just pressing button and waiting on the PC. On the PC, I just press a button and then I just move up and it's like... okay, five seconds, ten seconds, okay I'm up. So it was quite dull.

Maybe just also slight suggestion—I don't know if you need it, but for example, I felt like when there's an objective, I push the button, it turns green. I would love it to have the same effect for elevator because essentially it's the same button. I press it, it's green, I know it's activated. There was a sound that I registered, but at first I wasn't sure I pressed it. I'm like, "Okay, is it working?" Oh, I hear the sound, it is working. Just a small thing—because everything else does have this green effect of activation.

As I said, it was a bit fun, but I skipped this climbing part—this vertical climbing. I skipped it in both versions. I just ran because I can just run.

Interviewer: But when you tried in the VR for the first time, you tried to climb the rope and then you skipped it. But when you tried, did you feel like it's a good mechanic to include in a VR game in general?

Participant: I know that this is a mechanic—I think I played it in other games too. I think it's quite a popular mechanic. I think they even have it in Vader Immortal, in Star Wars game. Generally climbing, I think it's all right. I don't know, I think that for me it was hard though. At some point, I

got a bit too high and then this pipe was in the middle of my face and I was confused how am I going to... The ladder was much easier and this vertical pipe was hard. I can't say if it's good or not—I just skipped it.

Participant: Now also one thing about controls. On the PC version, the right stick sensitivity was way too hard. I don't know if it's the game—when I move the right stick, it was way too nuts. On VR it felt good, it felt natural even though it was choppy, but it was a comfortable level of rotation. I don't know if it's the controller settings or the game settings.

Interviewer: On the right stick, it's a game setting—it's called snap rotation. It works on a certain degree based rotation.

Participant: On the PC version it was way too fast. It was so cranked up to 11 that I found it uncomfortable to look around because it was too sensitive.

Interviewer: So now another defining mechanic between them—pushing the button. In first person version you're just pressing X, it's interacting. You're physically smashing the buttons. What do you think about that? Which one did you like the most?

Participant: Smashing button was more fun.

Interviewer: Do you also think that it's more intuitive, more engaging?

Participant: Yeah, absolutely. I think when something is up there and it's yellow and you just want to push it, this is just classic. I think, of virtual games—some interactivity. I think it's just natural to poke something or to push something. On the other hand, pressing X is just basically a button, that's it.

Interviewer: Final thing—which felt more satisfying overall? Which felt more intuitive, which felt more engaging, which felt more fun to play?

Participant: For me, probably it's PC version because of some controls maybe.

Interviewer: You struggled with the ladder of course in the beginning, and also the rope. But when you actually succeeded with the ladder, did you feel like the physical effort was worth it? Like you actually nailed the mechanics?

Participant: I think the last third or quarter of the ladder you don't climb because you have this automatic animation of getting up, which for me was a bit like "huh." I felt a bit disoriented by it because I expected that I need to go up to the top, but then in the last quarter it just teleports me without my control. So I felt like the hand of God gets me and just places me there—like the cat

mother gets her kitten and just places them. So yeah, I don't know, maybe... this was a bit disorienting.

Interviewer: You expected it to be like you physically climb the ladder, push yourself up?

Participant: Yeah, maybe even like you do this in the end and then you go up and you climbed it for real. But when you start normally and then part of this way is automatic, it was weird for me.

Interviewer: Now we'll concentrate on the controls. Which felt more intuitive to control? In general, there are many researchers about this thing in VR and between the controllers itself. In many researchers they say that the controller shape and ergonomics of the Quest or the VR headsets feel more natural to hand. Do you also agree with that, or do you think it's just the same feeling?

Participant: I don't know. **I think both of them are quite natural.** They are of course slightly different just because of the medium that you play on, but **I guess I'm just—I know both controllers well enough. I have found that the controls in both versions are largely the same, very similar. Both are natural, both are suitable for their own platform.**

But maybe on the Quest version, this EMP—I didn't really get EMP. I think for me what was lacking—maybe I'm jumping ahead, but **EMP was lacking some kind of visual effect because it was just the sound and I don't understand, "Okay, what happened?" I didn't even get this EMP because I didn't read the description or something. There's some sound happening but no visuals. Like is it around me? Is it some wave? Is it only front? Is it all the sides? Maybe add some simple wave that I would also love to see where does it end. As a gamer, if I'm fighting against them, I need to know where I can activate it and when it will reach them.** Pressing two buttons for it—I pressed it accidentally I think during climbing or something and it activated, and I was a bit confused. Maybe this was the only one control that didn't really feel natural on both versions. I'm not sure—I think on PC version if I press left stick it activates the EMP. Also, I don't know, for some reason didn't feel right.

Interviewer: This is kind of like the awkward mechanics, so to say, in the game that you didn't know what was happening. But between both versions, which mechanics do you think really adapted well in the controllers? Did you like the disabling mechanics of the robots, or did you like the rope grabbing, or did you like the ladders and stuff that you're physically grabbing between in the VR version? Or did you feel it's more easy and intuitive in just the controller?

Participant: I felt it was a bit easier in VR. Controls that I was just immediately tapping them—it's like this kid's game, you know, tag. You tap them and you caught them. On—I think even on the PC version I experienced some bugs or whatever, it didn't really register my tapping too well. Right click too well.

Interviewer: If we had to compare this sneaking mechanics between the VR and the PC version, which do you feel feels more engaging in itself?

Participant: I didn't find overall the sneaking mechanic much different. They felt the same. But then overall, I don't know, maybe it's just a matter of—I kind of cheated my way around it because I quickly realized, "Okay, I don't have to sneak around them actually" because their reaction is way too slow. I can just approach them and just stop them. I don't need to crouch. There's no need for me to do it at all. So when I realized that, I just ignored it. So I just went through. I can't really say if it's engaging or not because as I said, I quickly understood that I can just skip it and then I can just run through.

Interviewer: This was also quite kind of intentional to make them this way.

Participant: I understand.

Interviewer: Because in VR otherwise, I think, do you also feel like it could have been way too much tense if it was like the AI's were really good, really smart?

Participant: Not really. Not for me. I think, it should be fine because I think this is like—as I said, I played a lot of games and I watched a bunch of documentaries about it. I know people always get the way of least resistance. Any game you take, whatever designer has made up, "Okay, we're gonna build this crazy level and everything," people just gonna storm it in three seconds if they can, and I'm not different in this regard honestly. So why would I... if you don't give me this incentive to crouch, why would I use that? It's useless for me.

I think it should be—there's also, you always have to do it hard enough but not too hard so people can crack it. But for me it was way too easy. They actually don't have peripheral vision at all—they only look forward.

Interviewer: Yeah. It's very narrow.

Participant: Exactly, and you know, when I do it like this, I can see you. So just at least broadening this and making the reaction time higher, that would make me crouch, that would make me use this, and think about how should they move. I think that players need a bit of a challenge, or otherwise you just storm it.

Interviewer: So you feel like this crunching would have been much more enjoyable for you—a bit more tense environment?

Participant: Yeah, yeah, yeah. It wasn't, and that's why it was very easy and as I said, I just stormed it.

Interviewer: In both versions, which version felt more like when you were approaching a situation—for example, this robot situation that you're deactivating them—did you feel like in any version you preferred this mechanics or this certain interaction to be more fun? Or did it feel most of the mechanics felt the same in both versions?

Participant: I think it felt the same, and since it's a prototype, I mean it would be cool to have, I guess, some animation of actually getting them down or something. I don't know, but since the robots—you just turn them off, I guess. I don't know, maybe it was... in some interview, because it just turns red.

Interviewer: Would you prefer more violent actions in general in the game?

Participant: Violent action, maybe not.

Interviewer: You're just disabling them and they're disabled. Would you have preferred taking them down?

Participant: Yeah, maybe something like that. But since it's a robot, what can you do with a robot? You can't really break it if you're a human unless you're a robot yourself. I mean, a takedown animation would be cool. But I know it's just a prototype. It would be probably much more satisfying if there would be some animations—and the guy's just laying on the floor now.

Interviewer: Now we are going to move to the comfort discussion. Did you feel any kind of physical sickness in any of the versions? It can be motion sickness, dizziness, nausea, your eyes straining from VR glasses.

Participant: No, I don't think so. I think there was a bit of discomfort from just headset itself because of this strap and everything, because this basic strap is, you know, it's bad. I think just a bit more comfortable strap and that's fine.

Interviewer: So in itself, the game movements—the speed of the movement, the speed of you traveling on the zipline—these things were not a problem for you?

Participant: No,

Interviewer: They didn't make you dizzy or motion sick?

Participant: No, no. I feel like—I noticed that in the PC version there's a wobble which is really cool, and it was not in VR, and I think it's good that it wasn't in VR. I think if you would also leave it in VR version, I would feel sick. About the movement, I felt it too slow—it's too slow, especially in VR. I'm just barely walking, it feels like.

Interviewer: You would have preferred a bit more faster movements in VR too, in general?

Participant: Yeah, in this particular case, yeah. I would, or at least have it controllable, so if I push it down at the maximum, I'm sprinting. If I push it a bit less, then I'm slower. This kind of control.

Interviewer: So both versions were fine from a physical comfort perspective?

Participant: Yeah, for me.

Interviewer: As we already discussed, you felt like the robots were too easy—they could have been a bit more challenging. But even in the state they were, did you feel any extra anxiety due to the immersion that VR gives in the VR version? Or was it like the PC—you were trying to disable them very quickly rather than sneaking and stuff like that?

Participant: I don't think I felt any additional pressure in VR than in PC, again, because I quickly realized that they're really easy. So why would I be nervous about them? I just turned to them, press the button, they're off, that's it.

Interviewer: So after you completed the playthrough, the only complaint you had is the strap being uncomfortable?

Participant: Yeah.

Interviewer: Everything else was fine?

Participant: Yeah, I think so. It was fine.

Interviewer: Now the main comparative analysis between the VR version and the PC version. If you could choose one version that you would play—suppose I give you the option that you can play only one version—which one would you pick?

Participant: I would rather play it in VR, even though I said that PC version was more overall kind of nice. I think I would prefer a bit edited and better version of VR. In this particular case I felt like it was more comfortable to play on PC, but I would love to play in VR because I feel like this interactivity is good for VR. These ladders and tapping and pushing buttons—it's all working well. You see your hands.

Interviewer: So you think this interactivity is in general better in the PCVR version rather than the PC version because it's just... I mean, what made the difference for you? Is it just the interactions?

Participant: Yeah, I think interactions. Yeah, exactly. I think the interactions—that you use your hands to push buttons. It's satisfying.

Interviewer: So what mechanics do you think, or what in general did you feel that VR version did better than the PC? This interactions, anything else that you want to add?

Participant: Ladder. The lever pulling also. Because in PC version you just press the button and that's it. But on VR you actually do the stuff, which is cool.

Interviewer: Vice versa, what about the PC version? What did you like in the PC version that you didn't like in the VR?

Participant: Traversal—the movement. As I said, the strafe to sides and the camera rotation. I think this is why it was comfortable and more natural to play for me on PC, and I completed it faster just because of that.

Interviewer: For the ladder, which version would you prefer? The VR for the extra interactivity?

Participant: Yeah, I would prefer it.

Interviewer: For the zipline, the same? Or is it the PC version? Because you mentioned that you like the camera shake in the PC version a lot, which we cannot also put because it could make you dizzy.

Participant: Yeah I think in VR it could, I think it's fine for VR as it is, even though I don't know how would you go around it. Just the thing that—zipline, when I'm in VR, I press the button and I go backwards and I need to rotate myself, and that, at first it felt like "huh." I kind of expected just in my subconscious that I would rotate somehow automatically. That happens on PC—when I press the button, I do rotate my head towards it.

So I don't know, either for VR version it needs to be somehow made so—maybe the bulk is there, I press the button here and now I'm going forward. Or if it's here, the zipline is back, I press the button and then it rotates me towards the movement. Because when I feel that I'm being dragged, it felt weird. I'm just subconsciously expected to... I don't know if that would affect my dizziness. So this is why maybe the way is actually to activate it just differently somehow, that you design this way so I push the button and then move forward with the zipline.

Interviewer: If you want to say one moment that was the most memorable in the prototype for the VR version, what was it?

Participant: I think it was the zipline. It was cool. It was also unexpected. But even with the problem, yeah, even that, it was cool.

Interviewer: What about the PC? Overall in all the mechanics, what is the thing that you liked the most?

Participant: Moving around. I would love to have a jump though, actually, in both versions. It also felt lacking that I can't jump. It felt very limiting.

Interviewer: As we already discussed, the comfort level is same for both cases in your case. Still, do you think that the PC version—of course you're just seeing a screen and you're playing, and in the VR it's like a headset that's maybe around one kilogram hanging over your head. Do you feel like this is limiting your experience, or do you more prefer the immersion?

Participant: I think what was limiting my experience in VR was not the headset itself but the cable. Because when you're connected to the cable—I mean, I also developed some stuff, I know it's annoying, and I think you need some special straps for it not to be annoying. Because I immediately wanted to rotate and then I feel it, and I know that if I unplug it, it will just break the game because it launches from the PC.

Interviewer: Would you have preferred that if it was standalone in VR?

Participant: I think either make it standalone in VR—which is easier, I guess, to do—or with some special straps and special things that connect, that you can put your wire in, that you don't feel like that is limiting your movement around.

Interviewer: What do you think will make the VR version better than it is? The most important thing that you felt like should be in the game?

Participant: Okay, for me: movement strafing, that's for sure. The left and right strafe movement. Faster move, or this control of the speed so I can go faster or slower. Non-choppy rotation-like on PC.

Interviewer: For the PC version, what do you think?

Participant: Animations, for example maybe. Jumping—it's also for VR. Some additional traversal opportunities. It just feels to me natural. The game is about movements and interactions, and not having jump is limiting.

Interviewer: So suppose this game gets a high production value and it has all this art in a dystopian city—feels like maybe Tokyo vibe—and you have all this mechanics you can ask for, that you have this strafing movement, you have this rotation. Would you play it?

Participant: I don't know. It instantly reminded me of all of this—even in this state it reminded me of Mirror's Edge. Mirror's Edge has even this extreme parkour and you can run on walls. It'll be cool. I think it also feels natural to add it here for me. I felt while playing both in VR and PC that would be the natural continuation if you add jumps and additional traversal. It feels natural. I think even also in Mirror's Edge you don't have guns, you also kind of tap the enemies or whatever. I didn't play that much though.

Interviewer: Overall, do you think that VR is interesting in general as a medium of playing games?

Participant: Yes, absolutely. I really believe in VR and I believe that it can be one of the entertainments of the future. It's just for now—it's not enough good games. Let's be honest, it's heavy and expensive too, and just I think it's just a matter of time when either Meta or just overall... Actually, I spoke about it with someone recently that I believe someone like Apple is going to come out and make some AR glasses, VR glasses. They're going to be so intuitive, so light, and so cheap that almost anyone can afford it more or less, and I think that will start that.

I think now it's just still developing. It's kind of slowly getting there. But we just have—everyone has a phone in their pocket, but how many people have the headset? So why would you develop stuff for it? But I think VR has really great potential.

Interviewer: Is there anything else that you would like to share about the experience?

Participant: Let's see... The movements are one. The elevator getting green button for activation. Maybe some additional simple animations of the enemies. I think even if they just—for the prototype, if I press the button and they just fall, it's already better than just them freezing on the ground.

Because for example, I think that even when I scan—I use this scan and I see enemies—and even when I disable them and I scan, I still see them in the normal state, and I can't understand whether they're just standing or I deactivated them. If they would lie or the EMP would show me different color of enemies that are down, it would be much easier to understand.

What else? Yeah, right stick—I just want to remember everything that caught my attention. As I said, movement, and on PC right stick is way too sensitive. It's way too fast. I think that's it.

Interviewer: So did you like the overall experience?

Participant: Yeah, it was interesting. I was really surprised because I thought it's a really small prototype, but you built an entire level, which is really cool. What I really liked—it was really intuitive for me to understand where I need to go. I never felt like I'm stuck or "where the hell am I?" I didn't feel like, "Oh, I don't know where to go" because you got this on the floor, all these markings, and it was really intuitive. I wasn't lost in the game. So I think you really nailed it.

Interviewer: Great, thank you so much!

Participant: Thank you!

Interview – 02

Play Pattern

1. PC

2. PCVR

Interviewer: So, first of all, it's not anything like formal, I just want to know about the overall feeling that you felt playing the game, and I'm concerned about four things in general for my thesis, okay?

The first is, I'm naming it on a conventional term, sensory engagement, which is kind of like the immersion in one sense, and the rest of them are control schemes, because in your case, it's even different, because Participant-01 played both in controller, so he didn't feel much of a difference, but in your case, you played in keyboard and in the quest controller, so it makes a lot more ground in this case.

Participant: Really?

Interviewer: Yes. According to the overall surface understanding, that that's really different, rather than a controller and a controller. So, and the last thing is about comfort, okay, and the final thing is the comparative analysis between the VR version and the PC version, okay? Great.

Interviewer: So, first, let's start with some backgrounds. I mean, what type of games do you play in general, and how often do you play them?

Participant: For example, I play League of Legends, and TFD, which is the auto chess of League of Legends, like another version. I play Genshin, which is a gacha game, like these are, like these two, I mean, I play League and TFD together, like usually, so I count them as just one, but yeah, I play these regularly.

I, like, previously played some, I don't know, platform puzzle games, and, how do you call those, Under, what was it, Under something?

Interviewer: Undertale?

Participant: Undertale, like those kind of games too, a bit, previously, but I don't play these like regularly, as I say, like maybe once a year, I play something different, like, you know.

Interviewer: So, you're more into live service games in general.

Participant: Yes, yes.

Interviewer: What about, like, narrative driven games or VR games in general?

Participant: Well, I also play, sorry, I also play Dead by Daylight, lately, regularly, but also, that's also like an online game, you know.

Interviewer: So, you have tried VR before, right?

Participant: Yes, yes.

Interviewer: In general, in what kind of medium, like, have you played games in VR?

Participant: Yes, I did.

Interviewer: Or just films and stuff like that?

Participant: I played games, I think I watched one movie, I mean, movie, it's like five minute thing in VR usually, but yeah. I also, like, experienced some, for example, documentary and stuff.

Interviewer: 360s.

Participant: Yeah, 360s, those stuff too.

Interviewer: Okay.

Interviewer: So, now we'll just focus on the sensory engagement sections, okay?

Participant: Mm-hmm.

Interviewer: So, overall, which version made you feel more present in the game?

Participant: I mean, VR, I mean, of course, I guess.

Interviewer: Yeah, but why do you feel like that?

Participant: I mean, it's both, like, because of the VR headset, you are, like, seeing literally the first person and, like, feeling like you are the person. But also, like, I think some of the interactions, such as the ladder and all the other stuff, like, feel more like in real life, definitely, compared to the PC. Because in the PC, you just press a keyboard or something. But, like, the VR one, you both, like, grab it, like, hold it, you press a button too, but you also, like, move your arms and stuff accordingly, like, like, in the, in real life movement. So, yeah.

Interviewer: Okay, so, now a very important question, because there was an intended design for the whole environment, because you saw those high-rise buildings and stuff. Though it's a blackout, but the idea was there, and what I planned in the very beginning was I wanted it to feel a bit dystopic, like, it has to be very empty, isolated. It has to give you the gloomy feeling of there's, like, no light in this place, it's just total darkness, and everything is going haywire and stuff like that, and one of

the very distinct features of dystopian stuff is tall buildings and very dense areas. So, how did you perceive it when you played the game? Did you feel like it kind of captured the essence of the idea in the environment?

Participant: Yeah, yeah, kind of. I mean, it's, um, it is, it was dystopic, yeah, and also, like, it felt, it was, like, sci-fi because it had robots and, like, like, tall buildings, and you're just jumping on top of them and they have guns and stuff, and, like, the whole story, it's not really, like, a whole built story, but, like, you're trying to hack the system and stuff. So, like, it makes it more, um, sci-fi, and also, uh, it feels like we are, we are, like, trying to, um, interfere whatever they're doing. Like, we're, like, how do you say it? Like, sneak into their whole system and stuff.

Interviewer: Yeah, it's like we're kind of, like, trying to take the system down.

Participant: Yeah, yeah, take the system down.

Interviewer: Like, interfere with the systems.

Participant: It does feel a bit dystopian, too, on that sense, like, the whole, uh, story aspect of it. But the world building, uh, wise, it's, like, yeah, I would agree. Like, all the tall buildings and stuff. It wasn't just empty and it wasn't just, um, the area that we actually play, but we can see, like, the environment area.

Interviewer: What do you think about being in this dystopic feel? Is it different in the PC version and the PCVR version in general? Like, how you perceived the world? Because, for example, if you're, like, in a, above, like, uh, in the last segment of the game, the buildings are nearly, in the unreal human height, is about 80 storyed. So, it's 80 floors or 100 floors, even the last one. So, for example, in PC version and in PCVR version, you perceive the world differently, as you just said before. Like, kind of, like, you're interacting with your body. You're surrounded by the, um, kind of, like, the immersion of the VR. So, do you feel that it makes any difference in the height perspective? Like, uh, if you kind of, like, imagine yourself looking underneath over a tall building in VR and in PC, how will you, like, differentiate the experience?

Participant: Um, like, the height-wise, it does affect, especially when you're, like, in the monkey bar or, like, when you're, um, in the zipline and stuff. It, it affects, I think, in the VR, it, um, feels taller, and, like, you, uh, look down and, like, it feels like you can actually fall, and it's, like, you're in the actual height, and that's, in the sense, it affects the dystopian thingy, I would say. Like, oh, maybe, like, no difference, I don't know, in the PC and VR.

Interviewer: Great.

Interviewer: So, now, let's talk about the mechanics a bit, okay? Because, as you saw that it has a lot of active participation in VR rather than passive participation in PC. So, for example, when you climbed the ladder, how did you, kind of, like, differentiate your feeling about the ladder mechanics itself in both the versions?

Participant: Um, the VR one was definitely more fun and also, you know, more realistic, and like, the PC one is just boring. You hold the W and it goes up and stuff. It doesn't really, I mean, it's, like, like that in almost every PC game. It doesn't really capture that whole feeling. But in the VR, it was, like, much more realistic and actually fun.

Participant: Just, like, the, when you go on top, it automatically put you there. It was a bit disturbing for me because, maybe it was just too fast or something. But, yeah, that part was just a bit off-putting.

Interviewer: Do you think that it could have been better if you yourself have to push over and get on the wall or is it just the motion, the moving component that is moving you from one place to another could be just a bit slower? Which one would you prefer?

Participant: I would probably prefer the first one. But I don't know how it would work out, honestly.

Interviewer: Great. So, now let's talk about the rope. Do you think it was a good idea to have a detour in the rope? Like, you can just go from the beam rather than fully going over the rope?

Participant: Yeah, for accessibility purposes, I would say, yes.

Interviewer: Okay.

Participant: Yeah.

Interviewer: The rope mechanics, did you feel it is too hard in VR or is it okay? You just have to get a bit of practice?

Participant: Just the monkey bar or?

Interviewer: Yes, like the monkey bar.

Participant: Yeah, it was... I mean, it was technically very similar to the ladder, and, like, you need to get the handle of it. Because, like, what I realized when I was doing, I'm pushing the grab button, and it, like, gives a feedback when you're grabbing it. Like, just a small vibration, and, like, when you get it, okay, it's fine, and, like, you do it like that, like, all the time. You keep doing it. So, it helps.

Technically, it's not too hard but also, I would understand if someone would think it's super hard. I mean, I got a hard time. Like, at first, I fell down once, and then, you know, I had to, It was a bit slow. So, I have to do it a lot, and you have to be always careful and stuff. Yeah.

Participant: Okay.

Interviewer: So, now let's come to the pushing of the buttons. Because that's also, like, a distinct difference between the two versions. So, which one did you like?

Participant: Yeah, pushing the buttons. It was fun. I mean, it's, like, a very simple interaction. But even, like, just the fact that you can do that. Just do this, and it feels like a real button, instead of going there and pressing the keyboard or whatever. It's definitely, yeah, the button. It's better in VR.

Interviewer: Okay.

Interviewer: So, what will you say about if you... I mean, which version did you feel was more up to the mark? That which version would you prefer to play if I only gave you one version to play? VR or the PC?

Participant: I mean, I guess VR, because it's more exciting than the PC one.

Interviewer: Okay.

Interviewer: So, as you mentioned already that in the VR version, it feels like you are in that particular shell of the person rather than in the PC version. So, it's kind of like, did you feel like it actually gave you a sense of embodiment in the character? Like do you feel like it can kind of make it interesting in general? Like if I give you two version of the same game, will you be biased about it now, that you are liking the VR version more or is dependable on the particular point that how the game is in general?

Participant: I didn't understand the question, Sorry.

Interviewer: Okay, suppose you have played the same game, like the same overall mechanics, just the way it is done on the different platforms. So, for example if someone comes and says that I have made this game in the PC version and the PCVR version, which one you wanna play? Would you be biased towards the PCVR version? Do you have the intuition that it will be much more exciting or do you think it may depend on the particular game?

Participant: Are you saying there is just a PC version?

Intetviewer: Yes, and a PCVR version. Two versions.

Participant: Both of them?

Interviewer: Yes. The same game like this one for example. In this case, it is like a study so you played both of them. But what will be your intuition? If both version is there but you can only play one, would you be biased about it now?

Participant: It's just like the question is a bit tricky. Like, um, I don't know. I just don't understand what the question actually asks. Yeah, I enjoyed the VR more, but should I like...

Interviewer: It's also fine if you just can't put it into thoughts, it's fine you know.

Participant: Like should I think industrially or how should I think actually? **I guess it also depends on the game. Because for this particular game, you created thinking like you are gonna do it for both PC and VR, and it can not be done if you start with just PC for example. You can't really take a PC game right now, and make it VR.**

Interviewer: Definitely.

Participant: **Because of the mechanics and stuff.**

Interviewer: When I started designing it, I had a lot of intuition if this traversal idea is a good one for this comparison. I also kind of deviated towards shooting games, shooting mechanics in general. Like, they may feel different. For example, you are just pressing 'R' and you are reloading the weapon, and in the VR you are putting the magazine in and pulling the levers, so it could be more intuitive. But, I kind of like get your point, because it depends on the particular game genre, that maybe it is not better in VR and maybe it is better in PC.

Participant: Yeah.

Interviewer: Great. So, now did you enjoy the physical effort? Like, the ropes, the ladders and stuffs like that?

Participant: Physical effort? Like, when I was playing?

Interviewer: Yeah, because you have to, like, grinding towards it. Was it, like, positive? Was it new? Like, did you like it or do you, like, were you, like, really not?

Participant: I liked it, conceptually. But, um, as I said, sometimes, like, for example, **the first ladder is just very tall, and, like, you have to do it, like, for a very long time**, even though it's not very tiring or something, but it's, like, **okay, how, how long is the ladder? But, I think, you can go, I mean, look up and see, and it's also a nice thing.**

Interviewer: Okay.

Interviewer: So, now, let's move to the controls. Which one did you feel is more intuitive? Did you like the Quest version controls? Did it feel more natural to you? Or is it still keyboard and mouse that you prefer?

Participant: Um, the thing is, I always played games. Like, I mean, I usually play games on keyboard and mouse. So, when I was playing in PC, it was the basic stuff, like, moving and, like, pressing just a button and something, like, those stuff were a bit more intuitive than VR. Because, like, this game has, um, a lot of, um, interaction, and, like, it's been a while since I used VR actually, maybe that also affects, but, like, the, using the controller, okay, what am I going to push?

Uh, I didn't like the moving in VR, which is always a tricky thing, because, like, whether it's teleportation or just, like, moving like that is just, like, um, annoying. Maybe if it was just, you can, um, the turning around was not, you know, like, snapping, but also smooth, maybe would feel a bit better, moving wise.

Um, the other, for example, like, pushing the button and stuff were intuitive. But, when I first got to do ladder, for example, I asked you, oh, what do I do? Exactly, like, which button should I, um, push? Maybe it's also because, I played the PC version first, because, like, I intuitively just go, okay, I'm just gonna push one of the buttons in the controller and it's gonna go up, like, in the PC.

But, although, then you explain, then, okay, like, it's, like, more realistic and stuff, but I'm not super used to it. So, it wasn't very intuitive, all the interactions.

Interviewer: Okay, just, for the ladder point, I'll do a follow-up. Did you confused the ladder when you're climbing that you have to climb the poles or the yellow bars? Were you confused about that, too? Or just the overall mechanics? Like, how you wanna interact with it? Did you feel like you had to grab the yellow bars?

Participant: Yeah, yeah, I understand, but I think you explained. I don't remember what you exactly said, but I think I understood that I have to pull from the sides and not the bars, but, like, if you didn't tell me, I could actually, like, okay, like, maybe it's the bars, I could feel like that.

Interviewer: Okay, so, for example, you already said that the movement felt a bit awkward in the VR version for you. Um, can you also do the vice versa and tell me one awkward thing about the PC version that you didn't like?

Participant: Hmm, let me think, actually, PC version, interaction-wise, um, like, something bothered me, I remember, but, um, maybe the crouching, I don't know. But I didn't like the crouching in the other one, too, because the reason is the crouching in games, you normally, like,

hold shift, uh, no, uh, control, left control, and, like, not just press it once. That, you know, that was a problem in both of them, technically, but, um, maybe the ladder, I mean, it wasn't that bad either.

Um, yeah, just, like, the, in the PC version, sometimes, some of the interactions, you just tap. I think, in the ladder, too, you just tap it once. I didn't like that, I just have to tap it, like, tap it, like, I thought I had to hold the button.

Interviewer: Okay.

Interviewer: So, now tell me about your experience, like, can you compare the experience of EMP'ing the robots or disabling them between the PC and VR version? Like, in VR, did it felt more, did you feel more anxiety, because it's kind of, like, more immersive in general, or was it, like, just in the PC version that you're just, it's easy, you're going behind them, and like, disabling them?

Participant: Um, I would say, almost the same, maybe VR was a bit, just a bit more anxious. Because, um, because of the controllers, too, actually, because the moving controllers, and, like, in PC, I could move, actually, very fast, and, like, disable them, and I wouldn't mind, you know. But in the other one I had to change the direction, and stuff, and it, I couldn't really get into that, uh, control, uh, very fast, so, it felt a bit anxious. Okay, I have to do this, and what if they see me, and stuff, for example, in the PC version, I didn't even use the EMP, I forgot there was this EMP, uh, thing option, but, in the VR version, I had to use the EMP, because, like, at some point, I couldn't do anything, you know, it was the easier choice.

Interviewer: Okay, now, I'll just try to get an opinion about a very foundational thing that I planned, and I just want to know your perspective on it, okay? It's not in the game. I, in the beginning, when I designed the VR version, I had physical crouching implemented in the game. So, you need to physically get down, and then it will crouch in real time, but then I, kind of, took it out, because there's a lot of crouching in this game, as you have already seen, so, it's, literally, you may have to play it while being crouched most of the time, which is stressing on the body. But, do you think it would have been a good idea to keep that feature, just in case people want to try it? Do you want to try it, if it was there?

Participant: Um, yes, but, like, the game needs to be ten times shorter, and like, yeah, and if you find a way to actually make the crouching uncomfortable, maybe, like, it would be just standing and sitting. I mean, it's not the same as crouching, like, I would think that, like, it's not the same feeling, actually, but, it's more comfortable, I don't know, it can be tested, maybe.

Interviewer: Yeah, because it was, like, um, the capsule collider, kind of, like, adjusted according to your head position, in your headset, so, it was, like, um, not, uh, kind of, like, uh, state-based

situation, like, you stand or you sit. It's, like, you literally, if you do like that, you're, like, crouching way down, but it had some indicators, like, if your headset height goes to a certain extent downwards, then you crouch, the state changes. Because it also matters in the game, because the AI kind of detects you in a different speed if you're crouched. So you think this feature could have been intuitive, right? If it was implemented?

Participant: Yeah.

Interviewer: Okay.

Interviewer: So now, which version was easy to play or easy to learn? Which version was easy to get?

Participant: I mean, I'm not sure if I can, like, very, um, objectively answer this, because, like, I played the PC version first, and, like, was confusing, because my first time playing, like, I don't know what I'm doing, actually. Like, uh, but, like, also the VR version was also confusing, even though I know technically what the interactions are, I had to learn, like, which button to press and stuff, and also, I sometimes press some other buttons in VR, like, um, accidentally, the EMP, for example, so, I'm not really sure, honestly.

Interviewer: So, between these two versions, when you approached a certain situation, probably you're looking down, probably you're disabling a robot, which one kind of, like, um, felt more, like, you felt the freedom to approach the situation more intuitively or more engagingly between these two versions? Like, for example, if you are trying to climb a ladder, or you're seeing the rope from far behind, you're seeing the zipline, maybe you're going through the zipline, and you're kind of, like, seeing the area that you're going over. In general, which felt, like more welcoming in general for you in the both versions? Um, it's, like, the freedom to approach the situation. Which one felt more intuitive in general?

Participant: Freedom to approach the situation.

Interviewer: Like, would you rather sneak in the VR version, or would you rather disable them? Would you rather sneak in the PC version, maybe, because it has faster movements and stuffs like that?

Participant: I don't know, actually, like, probably...

Interviewer: They both felt the same? It's also, like, possible.

Participant: I guess. I just, I don't know, honestly, I don't know how I felt in that context. Like, they might be the same, might be a bit different, but, like, just, like, very specific context and whatever but and I just can't really find them right now.

Interviewer: Like for example this sonar functionality. PC version you just, it's really easy to move around, so maybe it's easier to detect enemies and stuffs like that.

Participant: Yeah, but I mean that one actually didn't feel like so much different for example.

Interviewer: So, now, did you feel any kind of motion sickness, nausea, anxiety in the VR version in general?

Participant: I felt a bit of motion sickness, yes.

Interviewer: Where exactly? Can you remember?

Participant: Walking. Not all the time, but at some parts walking, and maybe the ladder or the monkey bar a bit too, not a lot, not super disturbing.

Interviewer: Do you feel like the vignette effect that is given when you move in VR.

Participant: What effect?

Interviewer: The vignette. It's like, kind of like a black screen over your view so that it doesn't make you motion sick very easily. It just subsidizes the motion that you're trying to do in the game. Because when you stand still, it goes away, when you move, it kind of activates on the screen. Do you think that it kind of helped, or do you think it just didn't matter or you didn't understand at all?

Participant: No, I had no idea this existed. Oh, like, at the end of the ladder, it puts you there that also made me a bit like motion sick.

Interviewer: Okay.

Interviewer: So, now let's move to the main analysis section between these two versions okay? So if I tell you to name one thing that you felt like the VR version did better than the PC version in general, what would that be?

Participant: I would say the more realistic interaction, such as the ladder, and even the monkey bar even though like it's kind of torture, it felt you know more real, and, yeah I would say that.

Interviewer: Vice versa, what you liked in PC that maybe could have been improved or you didn't like in VR?

Participant: Mmm, like, moving and stuff like, more basic and intuitive interactions in PC were better I think.

Interviewer: So for the all the interactions that you did, the ladder, the zipline, the rope, like the monkey bar, which version do you prefer the VR version for the intuitiveness, or do you prefer the PC version for the comfort, because it's very stressing as you already said in VR? Would you like

compromise the comfort to get the immersion, or would you just compromise the immersion to get the comfort in general?

Participant: For this particular game, I would say you can compromise the, like, I mean you can choose the VR version. But some of them needs to be a bit shorter maybe, some of these interactions, and it depends, like, if it's like super uncomfortable, I would prefer the PC one for example.

Interviewer: So, if you want to describe one moment, like, the best moment in the VR version. What would that be?

Participant: Best moment?

Interviewer: Yes. Like you were like, okay this is so cool, this is so good, like, that kind of moment?

Participant: The ladder one was cool. I thought, oh, this is actually so cool to do it like this. Because also it was the first interaction that actually like changed a lot in the VR version, and felt realistic. When I came to do, for example, monkey bar, like, I knew I would have to do it, like, by hand, so it didn't feel, like, as cool as the ladder one. Also, like, the, not the interaction part, because it doesn't have many interactions, a zipline, it's almost the same, but like, uh, moving with the zipline was also cooler in VR definitely. Like, like, whoa, I'm flying, and i didn't feel like motion-sick or something, but like seeing that you're getting away from those robots, or all those tall buildings was definitely a better experience in VR.

Interviewer: What about vice versa, what about the PC version, what do you think was the best thing about the PC?

Participant: Best moment?

Interviewer: Yes.

Participant: Nothing. I don't know, it's, um, yeah maybe just seeing the, like aura of the things when you, the sensor thingy, I don't remember the name, when you press 'Y'.

Interviewer: The Sonar?

Participant: Yeah, the sonar thing was nice, that you can see the auras of the stuff.

Interviewer: So, what do you think, about what could make the VR version better, like suggestions or anything you have in your mind at this moment?

Participant: The movements, definitely. Uh, the motion sickness parts, some like super fast parts, like ladder thingy, and not like specific to VR, but also like in general, it felt a bit long actually.

Because, there was a lot of traversing, and but like there weren't many like new interactions all the way. You know, it felt like, I'm just, okay, I'm moving again, I'm going up the ladder again, I'm taking this whatever like the lift again, and this again, and then again. It just felt a bit dull after some point.

Interviewer: It felt a bit repetitive?

Participant: Yeah. Yeah, very repetitive.

Interviewer: What do you think about the PC version, like if you could improve one thing what would that be?

Participant: Yeah, my last comment. just, was about actually the both version. In both versions it felt that way.

Interviewer: A bit repetitive after some time?

Participant: Yeah, yeah.

Interviewer: So, when you're over the beam, at the last segment of the game. Do you think the beam is a better mechanics, or did you enjoyed the monkeybar even more?

Participant: Beam?

Interviewer: Yes, where you need to balance yourself, and just cross over the very tall building.

Participant: Oh, yeah, for example, I didn't even remember that part actually until you said it. Because it was just once, um, unlike the other interactions, and, um, it was pretty easy for me in the both versions, so yeah.

Interviewer: So, as you have tried both of the versions, will you be interested in playing more VR games in general, like will it spark your interest?

Participant: Yeah.

Interviewer: Anything else that you want to add about about the project in itself, like any comments if you have any?

Participant: I don't know. I don't think so. I said, like, all of my suggestions.

Interviewer: Any suggestions? Any improvements? Like anything that you really liked, anything you didn't like at all, anything you could have changed if you were the developer yourself?

Participant: I mean this is just a master project, and like not a commercial game, and like you have a lot of time constraints, and you're doing this alone, and stuff. So, it's, it's not like you know a game that you would play always, or just like play in general. Because like, it doesn't

have like, super exciting, um, features or like a story, or super cool custom designs of robots, and everything. **I don't expect them at all, so I wouldn't, I don't know, I, I mean, I don't see the reason to comment on those stuff just saying.**

Interviewer: So, you think that for a prototype this was good?

Participant: Yeah, yeah. For a prototype it was fine definitely.

Interviewer: OK, great. Thank you so much for your time.

Participant: Thank you.

Interview – 03

Play Pattern

1. PC

2. PCVR

Interviewer: Okay, should we start?

Participant: Yes.

Interviewer: So, first of all, thank you for your time and thank you for playing that game.

Participant: Sure, it was fun.

Interviewer: Because it took a lot of time.

Participant: Yes, I can imagine.

Interviewer: So, I'll just take occasional notes, but it's mostly, I just want your raw opinion about it. Okay, and this is the reason I'm recording, because it can be more interactive when we're like just concentrating on the thing rather than writing its stuff out all the time.

Interviewer: So, let's have some background first. What types of games do you usually play? Like, it can be anything.

Participant: Usually RPGs, fantasy RPGs, and doesn't matter if it's an MMO, like multiplayer or single player.

Interviewer: Okay.

Participant: But, even though I play both, I like single player games more.

Interviewer: Okay, sounds good, and how often do you play?

Participant: Daily.

Interviewer: Daily?

Participant: Daily.

Interviewer: Great.

Participant: Daily everything.

Interviewer: So, have you used VR before?

Participant: Yes.

Interviewer: Okay, and do you have experience rather than just not games, like in other types of mediums in VR? Like films and stuff, 360s and all those stuff, or just games in general?

Participant: I would say slight experience in creating 360 experiences, like the medium doesn't matter if it's the hexadome or VR or something else.

Interviewer: So, we will kind of divide this in five sections, because my research is about four of the certain topics that I'm focusing right now, and the first one is the sensory engagement, I'm calling it in the so-called coating terms. So, it's more about the immersion and the presence that I'm meaning in general. Okay? So, what do you think? Which version? VR or PC? Which made you feel more present in the game?

Participant: Presence. If it's about presence, it's hard to say, both, but there are some aspects about VR that make it a bit more human.

Interviewer: Okay. Like what?

Participant: So, there are, like in this game, it was also about being sneaky, doing a job and not failing and everything, and in VR, there were some silly things you cannot do in PC version. Like, for example, if you try to be sneaky, you want to look around corners, and you cannot do that in classical, like in usual PC games, and this was something very satisfying in VR, because at this point, VR is more beneficial, because you can do more physically, if it makes sense.

Interviewer: Intensive actions.

Participant: Yeah, like more precise actions. Like, I feel like in usual PC games, you cannot be as precise as looking around corners.

Interviewer: True.

Interviewer: So, as you already seen, the heights are like a cool design inside the game, in both versions, because it's the same, and as I already, I was discussing with them that it kind of, I kind of wanted to give a dystopic overall feel to the whole thing.

Participant: Yeah.

Interviewer: Because tall buildings are one of the distinct features of the dystopian environments in general.

Participant: Yeah.

Interviewer: So, how do you think the experience differed in VR and PC, like the heights in general?

Participant: For me, I had no problem with the height itself, like that I was in fear or something, or in fear of my character, with the PC version. But it was just more immersive in VR, because the PC, like the desktop version, the PC version was just not, you didn't really care about the height. It was just nice visuals, but in VR, it was just more personal, like I'm affected by the height. I mean, you're not, but it felt like it.

Interviewer: So, let's talk about the mechanics a bit, because one of the reasons I chose this kind of genre, rather than doing something with shooting kind of mechanics or something else, because it kind of, traversal is a very good way to differentiate between versions, you know? So, how do you kind of, like the ladder, how do you compare the latter interactions in both versions?

Participant: I guess the PC version, it felt almost a bit redundant, because you just press one button, or you usually, in usual games, don't need to do much to climb a ladder, and in VR, it was more, oh God, I really need to, Um, I need to put effort into climbing, but it was just a completely different thing.

Interviewer: Okay, and were you confused with the ladder in the beginning? Did you think that the rungs you need to climb, or the poles, did it create a confusion?

Participant: Yes, but not because it was complicated designed, but because I need to remind myself that VR is actually so realistic, that you need to all the time adjust your hands to actually climb. It's, I was still used to pressing only one button. It was just this.

Interviewer: Okay, and what about the lever interactions in general?

Participant: Just in more satisfying, because, yeah, because you, you need to do a whole movement with your hand instead of just pressing E or something.

Interviewer: Okay. Okay.

Interviewer: Did the zipline made you hazy in VR, or was it satisfying the PC version more, because you had, like, a wobbling effect, if you noticed, in the PC version?

Participant: During what interaction?

Interviewer: The zipline. It had, like, a camera shake, you know, to make it realistic. But did you enjoy the VR version, because in the VR version, you could move your head in real time and see?

Participant: Yes, that was actually, I didn't even notice the wobbling effect. It was just, I was glad that I could look around. I don't know for the PC version if it was intended, but I think you only had an angle of, I think, 100 degrees or something like this, and that was a bit limiting.

Interviewer: Okay.

Interviewer: What about the buttons?

Participant: In both versions?

Interviewer: Yes. How do you compare them?

Participant: I just needed to get used to it, in, like, for the VR version, both worked fine in the end, after I got used to everything. I like to have all the most important buttons very close to my thumbs. So, for VR, it was the one above, on both sides, and the deactivating button for the robots, the oh shit button, basically. I wished it to be the one below, on the right side, for example. Stuff like this, but, as I said, you got used to it. But, otherwise, it worked out very well.

Interviewer: So, I'll just kind of ask this question, just to be sure. So, you personally felt the VR version was most satisfying, right, in general?

Participant: Yes, it was a bit more. I personally didn't like the way you, the locomotion, it was just, I mean, of course, you could also tilt your head and then you change direction as well. But, to be very fast, and sometimes you needed to be fast, maybe because of the robots, and then it was a bit annoying to change direction with, with, what was the, how was the button called, where you, thumbstick?

Interviewer: Right, thumbstick.

Participant: Right, thumbstick, thumbstick. Yeah, that's the only thing, the locomotion, otherwise, it was more satisfying in VR.

Interviewer: Okay, so, this is like a follow-up question, because the other people that tested the game had a say about this locomotion too, but, in general, the rotation itself, do you think it would have been more satisfying to have a smooth rotation rather than the snapping of the 30 degrees?

Participant: Um, yes, like, I think there are some people who don't like the smooth rotation or smooth movement in general.

Interviewer: It could make you sometimes motion-sick.

Participant: Yes, I don't have a problem with it, but, um, maybe a suggestion, um, and I, I think this would be even more complicated for some people, I would be comfortable with it, that if you, because if you move your head, then you also change direction instead of using the thumbstick.

Um, but, um, but to not have to use the thumbstick at all, **maybe even if you only move your head for some centimeters, maybe in VR, you turn around for, for even more degrees.** Yes, I mean, it would be maybe confusing and, but, but that would make it more dynamic and fun, if you want to be fast and sneaky. Um, yes.

Interviewer: So, this is for the immersion and interactions, in general. Now, let's talk about the controls, okay? Because in your case, it's even more, um, interesting to talk about it because you use keyboards and mouse in the PC version and if you used controller, it's basically two controllers, but still there could be some different factors to the likeness of both of them. But, um, but in general, which one felt more intuitive or which one you kind of, like, caught really well and easily too?

Participant: Um, you mean, uh, the keyboard compared to.

Interviewer: The motion controllers?

Participant: Um, the keyboard because, but I think only because on a regular basis I use the keyboard at home. Um, that's the only reason I feel I probably, if I used, um, a gaming console, um, a PlayStation or so, maybe I, I, then I wouldn't be used to the keyboard. Then I guess I chose the controller and there wouldn't be any difference.

Interviewer: Okay. Okay, so regarding the comfort zone between them, because as you mentioned, if I'm not wrong, that in the motion controller, it's, and just the buttons are very close and stuff like that, so you have all of them in handy and the whole mechanics is just in your hand, rather than controlling with mouse or a keyboard. So do you think this is more comfortable, not easy to catch, but comfortable in general, or do you still prefer the keyboard is better in this regard?

Participant: Um, I guess. For VR, I'd always expect to, to have the controllers from the meta quest, like, especially this design, because we know there are ones that are much bigger and even, like, more uncomfortable to hold in the hand. Um, I can't really tell, um, it depends on what you want to do, I guess.

Interviewer: Um, so, any interaction that felt awkward in either versions, that just, you just couldn't get it wrapped around your head?

Participant: Um, not awkward, but, um, when, like, uh, I pressed, I regularly pressed the, the mechanic to, to see objects behind walls, like in red, green, yellow, um, where the enemies are, where the cubes are. Um, and what I wished was, um, that I get, for example, when I forgot, okay, **this one robot there, did I already deactivate it or not? But when I pressed, uh, the button for this signal, it was still shown in red, like, all the others that might be already, um, still active.** So, I mean, I know if you deactivate it, they didn't have any animations anymore, but if they were far

away, then I wasn't sure, is this one still active or not? I can't really see it because it's, it's red, and then, even when you got close, it was still red, so it took away the information because they were also red. Um, when they were disabled and you did not activate, uh, the radar, um, if you know what I mean. **Um, so just an extra color indicator for this.**

Interviewer: Okay, so this is, uh, for both of the versions in general?

Participant: Yes, for both of the versions.

Interviewer: Anything in particular that felt really smooth, like, out of the box, you just kind of, like, uh, naturally got into it?

Participant: **Uh, I guess, um, the PC version, everything, the whole, um, like, every mechanic. Um, also because, maybe it's just because of Unreal Engine, but, um, the gameplay of the PC version was very smooth, everything very, very nice, very same as well.**

Interviewer: So, now let's compare your experience between disabling and EMP'ing the robots in VR and PC. So, what do you think about them? How would you compare the experience of disabling the robots in both versions?

Participant: Um, you mean in terms of mechanics or immersion?

Interviewer: Um, Both.

Participant: **Um, in the PC version, it was more like, um, you were more strategic. Um, and it was also, it, it still felt like an achievement when you disabled one, but it, there was no, it didn't really feel like a threat. Um, and in VR, it was more fun to be more risky.**

Interviewer: Mm-hmm. Okay. But, like, as you already mentioned, that you need to physically peek in VR. So, was it, like, a problem during the enemy interactions, or was it, like, made it more interesting in general?

Participant: That you used your, uh, that you need to use your whole hand.

Interviewer: Yes.

Participant: Yeah, that was also much more satisfying instead of just pressing one button.

Interviewer: Okay.

Interviewer: So, in the beginning, when I designed the mechanics, I had physical crouching in VR, where you had to crouch in real life, you know?

Participant: Mm-hmm.

Interviewer: As you already played the two versions, you know that there is a lot of crouching in the game.

Participant: Yep.

Interviewer: So, that was the reason I kind of changed it to a button-based crouch in both versions. But, do you think you would have liked the physical based crouching more?

Participant: Um, since you needed to crouch a lot, I think it's better that you changed it to a button. Yeah. Because, I guess, um, people would appreciate it, but crouching all the time, but actually not really crouching, because it might be stationary, like, because the experience is stationary, I think it would get annoying.

Interviewer: Okay. Okay.

Interviewer: So, let's move to comfort. Yeah. Did you feel any kind of dyslexia after you played the versions or Nausea, or it made you emotion sick in any of the mechanics in VR?

Participant: Um, not the game, like, no, just, sometimes I get a headache, but from the headset itself, from the weight, or because I did not adjust properly, or whatever, but not from the game itself.

Interviewer: Okay. Okay. During the zipline, the movements are a bit faster in the VR, rather than your moving speed, because it's very slow, and it's intentional. But, did it make you dyslexic, or was it fine, the speed was fine in your case?

Participant: No, I did not care, it was, everything was fine.

Interviewer: Would you prefer the movement speed to be more than what it is right now, in the VR version?

Participant: In VR? No, I think it was fine.

Interviewer: Okay, and, I don't know if you noticed it, that there was kind of like a vignette effect when you moved.

Participant: Mm-hmm.

Interviewer: Do you think it was better to minimize the motion sickness in general? Or, did you feel like it just didn't matter much, it was fine from all angles anyway?

Participant: For me, personally, it didn't really matter much.

Interviewer: Okay. Great. So, which version was more physically comfortable?

Participant: Probably the PC version.

Interviewer: Okay, and, when you kind of played the VR version, did you feel that, after some interactions, you got a bit tired, or was the playtime fine for your case? Like, it was around 15 minutes.

Participant: So, since there are much more sensors included in VR, you definitely get exhausted faster. Yeah, but not in a bad way. Just because you are just more engaged, in any case.

Interviewer: Yeah. This was kind of like a follow-up thing also. So, it was a bit, of course, more demanding on the physical interactions for the VR. But, do you think it was also more satisfying?

Participant: Yeah.

Interviewer: Because of that?

Participant: Yeah. I guess for me that's a good point.

Interviewer: Okay.

Interviewer: As you said, you felt more present in the VR version, more immersed. So, did you feel more anxiety while disabling the robots?

Participant: Yes.

Interviewer: Okay. So, I mean, why do you think, because it's the same mechanics, you just sneak in and you just press the right trigger and it gets disabled. But, why do you think that it made you more anxious in the VR version?

Participant: I guess, two reasons for me. Because I needed more time to be really comfortable with pressing the right buttons and everything, and, that's why it was a bit more of a challenge, and, so, you're more prepared. But, like, from the immersion, everything is just bigger. Because, on PC, everything is just on your small screen. But, in VR, it's just, I know it's just the default Unreal Engine models. But, if it's something, if it's life size, it's just more threatening.

Interviewer: Okay, and, do you think the controller in game that you can see on your hand, it just made it more easier to grasp the controls overall?

Participant: Not necessarily, because, also, when you use a normal keyboard, at some point, you don't look at your hands anymore. I don't know. Or, don't want to.

Interviewer: So, now, this is, like, the main core of the discussion at this point. The comparative analysis between the both versions. Okay. So, as you played both of them. Now, if I give you the choice that you have to play, and you can play only one version. Which one would you choose?

Participant: It's hard to tell. Mm-hmm. I guess, the VR version, just because, like, genre-wise, it's rather being sneaky, assassinating robots, and, that's why I want this mechanic of looking around corners, and, I can't do that in PC versions.

Interviewer: So, it's just because it has more, it's kind of, like, involving you physically in the environment, so it's much more enjoyable than the PC version?

Participant: Yes. For example, if it was a strategic game, then I wouldn't care about the VR version.

Interviewer: So, you think that genre makes a lot of difference in genre?

Participant: Yeah. Genre makes a lot of difference.

Interviewer: Cool, and, can you name one thing that you felt did much, much, much, much better than, much, much better in the VR version than in the PC? Like, one certain mechanics or one interaction that you really, really liked in the VR version than in the PC?

Participant: The deactivating part, because you needed to touch the, the enemy.

Interviewer: Okay. That was, yeah, and, what about the PC? That did something miles good than the VR version.

Participant: The general locomotion.

Interviewer: Okay.

Interviewer: So, now, for the climbing, you already said that you really, really liked the VR version, because it kind of, like, makes you physically interact with the ladders, right? Like, ladder poles and stuff, and, the zipline, as I already discussed with you, that they have this kind of, like, camera shake movements when you get on them in the PC version, and, this kind of, like, you can look freely on the VR version, and, then, for disabling the robots, you, as you already said, you just need to touch them and, in the PC version, you just go behind them and you just press a button, and, for the levers and stuff, it's all the same. So, overall, I just want to reflect one more time. Which version would you prefer regarding interactions, in general?

Participant: If it's about interactions and not locomotion, unless you regard locomotion as interaction, but I don't think so, the VR version.

Interviewer: Yeah, okay. Do you have any suggestions what could make the locomotion a bit better, or what you want to see in the game itself, in the VR version?

Participant: As I said, the extra color for which robots are disabled, and, I think, the idea that I already mentioned, that snapping with the right thumb stick is not necessary, because, maybe, if you

move your head, you move even faster and turn even more. Like, yeah, if you understand, if you understood, then just this.

Interviewer: What was the most memorable moment in the PC version for you?

Participant: In the PC version? To be honest, in general, the PC version did not have that of a big impact on me, compared to the VR version. Most stuff I remember from the VR version because it was just more impressive, but the PC version, I guess... hard to tell, nothing specific, to be honest. Because all the interactions seem very familiar from other games I played, for example. So, everything was fine, I don't know.

Interviewer: Vice versa, what is the most memorable moment for you in the VR version?

Participant: Definitely, when I was almost shot, because the animation was like this, or, actually, I don't remember what it was, but this.

Interviewer: Pointing the gun at you.

Participant: But, in the right moment, I was able to disable him, and that it was frozen in this frame that I almost got shot was just very... How do you say? How do you say in English? Exciting? Thrilling? Dangerous? Yeah.

Interviewer: So, would you sacrifice... Because, in general, in the PC version, there isn't much physical interaction, so you don't get exhausted. You are seeing it from afar, so it doesn't feel that much... It doesn't hit you with anxiety that much, and stuffs like that. But, do you think you will sacrifice all this just to play the VR version?

Participant: In general, or for this game?

Interviewer: For this game.

Participant: For this game. Yes.

Interviewer: Like, for this particular genre?

Participant: Yes.

Interviewer: Like, traversal?

Participant: Yes.

Interviewer: Stealth mechanics?

Participant: Yes.

Interviewer: Okay. So... What, in general, will you sacrifice to play the VR version? The comfort, the familiarity of the PC version? Because, as you said, the keyboard is kind of like very easy for you to map in your hands, and stuff. But, would you still prefer, from a control perspective, the PC version or the VR version, in general?

Participant: I wouldn't mind getting used to...

Interviewer: Motion controllers?

Participant: Yeah. Like, I would sacrifice the keyboard.

Interviewer: Okay.

Interviewer: So, what is the one thing that made the VR experience better? If you just have to name one single thing. Could be the interaction, could be how it immersed you, could be the heights that you felt, especially during the beam, and stuff like that.

Participant: Always 360, that everything is, like, human scale. The robots especially, that they have your height, and look you directly into the eyes if they had one.

Interviewer: What about the PC? The movements? As you mentioned them quite a few times, I think.

Participant: The productivity, because you're just... everything is a bit more fast.

Interviewer: Okay.

Interviewer: So, after trying this VR version, would you be interested if it's like a full-scale production game, that's made into a stealth-based traversal game, and maybe a bit more fast-paced, or something like that? Like, it has a good production value, will you try it out?

Participant: Yeah.

Interviewer: Okay. Okay.

Interviewer: The last thing that I want to ask is, is there anything else that overall you want to say about the whole development in general? Like, for the both versions, could be anything that you have in mind.

Participant: Rather a question, because in the beginning you had the option to include something not in the game?

Interviewer: The robots.

Participant: The robots. Why? Isn't that kind of really important?

Interviewer: Okay. This was because, in the beginning, when I tested the game, the AI's were a bit harder. Yeah. You know? They had more detection range, they had more peripheral vision angle, they were more faster, and stuff like that. So, at times, because as you already have mentioned multiple times that the VR locomotion gets some use to, getting some use to, you know? Like, it's a bit harder to grasp it well. So, it, at times, was really, really overwhelming when I tested the game.

Participant: I see.

Interviewer: You know? Because of the enemy difficulty, and that's one of the reasons the AI was made a bit dumber than it was before, and I also included the option that I thought maybe some people will get too overwhelmed by the AI itself, and they will just don't want to play the game at all. So, they have at least the option to disable it, because I know it's a very important mechanics in itself, but without it, you still had all those traversing mechanics in the game that you could, that I could use as a differentiating factor between the two versions.

Participant: So, I said, include the AI, like, right? I think for the user testing, this was completely fine, like, the difficulty.

Interviewer: Okay. But, what do you think? Is it good to have, like, a difficulty level based system?

Participant: Like, after the level we just played, it should definitely get more tricky.

Interviewer: Okay. So, thank you so, so much for playing and for your time.

Participant: It was interesting. It was very cool. You put a lot of effort into it. I mean, it's basically two games you did, and they were very well done.

Interviewer: Yeah, it was kind of like, at times, it was a bit stressing, because I, because they're really different, as you already know, and I tried to keep it in one project, so that I don't have to jump all the time between projects, the PC version and the PCVR, and I tried to keep as much common elements as possible, so it's a bit easier for myself to manage it. Like, the enemies, it's the same for both versions, the same code and everything. It doesn't have anything specific to PC or VR, you know? So, kind of like this kind of things, and there's also this, I try to make an indicator where I can choose which version I'm building the game for, and that applies some settings throughout the codes in general. Kind of like a switch, you can say. Like, I'm switching at PC or I'm switching at PCVR and stuff like that. So, but I think, yeah, having it in one project could be a drawback for some people, that it's too much to manage in some cases.

Participant: Maybe.

Interviewer: But I think that also gives you a very distinct advantage that you will not forget the things you want to add easily.

Participant: Yeah.

Interviewer: Because you just, I just kind of change it in PC, and then I instantly change it in PCVR.

Interviewer: Yeah. So I Don't forget, you know?

Participant: Yeah. It sounds pretty convenient.

Interviewer: Mm-hmm. So, anything you want to add about the whole thing? About the whole experience? Anything else?

Participant: No, other than it has potential. **Because I wonder why is there no VR Assassin's Creed? Actually, I think, isn't there VR?**

Interviewer: There is one.

Participant: **There is, there is, okay. Because maybe I should try that now.**

Interviewer: Yeah, it's a good one.

Interviewer: Okay. So, thank you so much.

Participant: Sure. I'm glad I could help, and good luck with the rest of your master's project.

Interviewer: Thank you so much. Okay. I think we're done. Thank you.

Interview – 04

Play Pattern

1. PC

2. PCVR

Interviewer: Okay, first of all, thank you for taking all the time and attending the session.

Participant: You're welcome.

Interviewer: So let's, this whole thesis idea is divided into four soft focuses that I have and I want to study throughout the two games, okay? Just let me give you some background. So it's kind of like, one of my focus points is sensory engagement between these two versions. By sensory engagement, I'm meaning the immersion and the presence between the two versions, okay?

Participant: Yeah, what is the presence?

Interviewer: The presence is more like, it's kind of like you can say goes par with the immersion itself, but it's also the feeling of when you're doing an activity, you feel more present in that thing, you know?

Participant: It's very similar to me, to be honest.

Participant: Yeah. Kind of like, yeah.

Participant: It's very similar to me.

Interviewer: The second thing is user control, and by user control, I mean the two control schemes that you're trying.

Participant: Okay, I know this one.

Interviewer: Okay, motion controller and the gamepad.

Participant: Yeah.

Interviewer: The comfort, of course.

Participant: Which will be obvious, I think.

Interviewer: But still.

Participant: Yeah, we really get into it.

Interviewer: So, let's just get some background about you. What type of games do you generally play? How often do you play? Like, it can be anything. It doesn't have to be VR.

Participant: I play different genres. Racing. Sometimes non-racing. Sometimes maybe casual action adventure. I play different. Different genres. I think I'm different. But sometimes I also... What do you say? I stick to maybe one genre or one game for some time, and then maybe I give up. It's a little bit difficult to explain. That's true. But what was the other question?

Interviewer: How often do you play video games?

Participant: VR?

Interviewer: Video games. Just normal video games.

Participant: Non-VR video games. VR games. It is very rare. It's almost non-existent. But other than that... So, let me think a little bit. Maybe recently in one week it was... The last week maybe it was more than five hours or even maybe more than ten or something like that. Like, between five or ten...

Interviewer: Does it fluctuate a lot?

Participant: Does it fluctuate a lot? It fluctuates also. Maybe sometimes it is non-existent. Not at all. So, maybe it can be for more than one week. But maybe it can get also like almost, for example, ten hours in one week or something like that. I'm not quite sure to be honest.

Interviewer: That's a good number for me at least.

Participant: But the thing is that I'm not sure about the number.

Interviewer: Yeah. That's fine.

Interviewer: So, now let's talk about VR. Have you used VR in general before?

Participant: Before this I used... Yeah, I used... One of them was for PS.

Interviewer: PS VR?

Participant: PS VR, I think. Yeah, I think. Also, the one that is by HTC, I guess.

Interviewer: Yes. HTC Vive.

Participant: But I'm not sure about the version. I don't remember exactly. It was a long time. Many years ago. More than... More than 3 or 4. 4 or 5 years ago. I don't remember exactly. But it is definitely more than 2.

Interviewer: So, you didn't use any VR in at least 2 years before playing this game?

Participant: Before this... The one that I told for the experience. The 360.

Interviewer: Yeah, that one.

Participant: Maybe that one was the last thing, I guess.

Interviewer: Right. So...

Participant: Or... Or... Or... After that or before that. I'm not sure exactly. But I also had the experience of... Something VR in... For one of the language course. In one of the language course, we had the... For one session, we had for sometimes something VR.

Interviewer: Okay. So, you would say your VR experience is in general quite beginner, right?

Participant: Very beginner.

Interviewer: Okay. Yeah. Sounds good. Yeah.

Interviewer: So now, let's talk about the immersion inside the two games, okay? So, which version do you feel like you felt more present inside the environment?

Participant: Well, for being more present and immersion, the VR one was better. I felt it much better, and maybe even it was a little bit too much sometimes. Because I'm not used to VR. So, yeah, I don't know what else I can add to it.

Interviewer: Okay, and... As you've already seen that the game kind of plays with verticality a lot.

Participant: Yes.

Interviewer: Because it has varying heights of buildings until the end. So, that was kind of like a distinct feature. That the environment itself had to give you a vibe of a dystopian district. Okay? So, a bit of dystopian inside it, and... So, one of the very distinct features of dystopian is very tall buildings in general. Okay? Like these social divisions between them. You know, the five districts that you've visited, they're kind of like also... The building is kind of giving you a notion that it's kind of like a hierarchy. That you're going from a low caste to a high caste society.

Participant: Yes.

Interviewer: You know? So, there is kind of like dystopic thoughts inside it, and there's also this environment lighting, which was very dull, not very vibrant, not very inviting.

Participant: No, it was mainly with... There wasn't much of color variety. Variety. Variety. Variety. Yes.

Interviewer: It also... The background of the story was the robots that had gone rogue and taken over the city. So, it kind of like gives you a futuristic dystopian feeling. So, the varying heights were a very distinct feature of the prototype.

Participant: Yeah.

Interviewer: How do you think it differed on your experience in, say, the VR and the PC version?

Participant: The difference between...

Interviewer: Like how you perceive the heights. Yep. The dystopian feeling and the heights of the buildings because it's more important to the core.

Participant: So, the VR was more evident, the difference between heights. It was much more evident because of the depth that you can feel in the VR that you cannot feel it that much in non-VR version, and the dystopian part, well, I think similarly in the VR version, it was more, it was because of the embedded immersion. I think you could feel it more.

Interviewer: You felt more in the environment.

Participant: Yeah, yeah, exactly.

Interviewer: That makes sense.

Interviewer: So, now, let's talk about the very interesting thing in these two projects, the interactions itself. Okay?

Participant: Yeah.

Interviewer: So, regarding the ladder, which one did you enjoy the most?

Participant: The ladder? The normal one.

Interviewer: Can you elaborate?

Participant: Yeah, I will elaborate, yeah. Well, in the VR one, I wanted to use the ladder. So, I got too close to the wall and to the object, and being too much close doesn't have a much good feeling to me.

Interviewer: Okay.

Participant: Yeah, I'm also explaining about my experience, but on the non-VR version, that was just with button, and you could, it was, it was, how to say, it was a more familiar experience to me. I'm kind of being used to that one, and that was easier, but on the VR, it was more difficult, and at first, it wasn't that much of a good feeling. Maybe a little later, it got better.

Interviewer: But, was it like a very distinct feature to you that you have to literally physically stress yourself to climb the ladder rather than just pressing a button in the fast-person version?

Participant: I think, the VR version, maybe an option to just do it easily also could have been, could have been better for the user experience.

Interviewer: Okay.

Participant: That's just my opinion. We're just doing it in a simple way, not in moving of the controller. But also, I have a comment on that one, that I felt, doing, going up and going down in the VR one, it is better to doing it like this, than like this.

Interviewer: I get your point. Okay.

Interviewer: So, now regarding the rope.

Participant: Yeah.

Interviewer: Okay. So, what's your thought about the rope mechanics in the VR version? In the two versions, both of them.

Participant: Okay. The non-VR also, it wasn't, it was a little bit slow, or maybe more, yeah, it was slow. The steps were not long enough, in my opinion. They were not long enough, and the process was slow. But in the VR version, it was a different experience. It wasn't similar, and it was, it was entertaining. It was entertaining. It was better than the ladder. Ladder.

Interviewer: Okay.

Participant: But it took some, took some time to get used to it.

Interviewer: Okay. So, if I want you to rate it on a physical-based stress factor, you would say that the VR one was more immersive and stressing physically?

Participant: Yes. Yes, definitely.

Interviewer: So, now, one of the other features that the two versions had a difference on was the button. The button was quite physical, the buttons you pressed.

Participant: Oh, yes.

Interviewer: So, you kind of like pressed it in real life?

Participant: Yeah. Other than pressing it, other button in the controller itself, right?

Interviewer: Yeah, that's correct. So, how was the experience regarding the buttons?

Participant: This one was convenient compared to, for example, ladder. It was that you feel that you are doing something similar to a real world when you want to press a button. So, I think this one was good. The interaction was good, and it was also similar to real life.

Interviewer: Like, did you like the button mechanics in general in the VR or the PC version?

Participant: For the convenience, PC.

Interviewer: Okay, and for the interaction itself?

Participant: But the interaction in VR, this one, the implementation, if I want to compare to ladder, I think this one was better.

Interviewer: Okay, and what about the lever?

Participant: The lever also similar to that one. That one was maybe even better than the button. But I think for the button, that was done right and correctly. Also, the lever... What was it? Lever?

Interviewer: Lever. Lever.

Participant: Lever. That one also was, like, similar to real world, and it was done in a good way, and it was convenient also.

Interviewer: But regarding these two interactions that you are kind of, like, physically involving yourself when doing this stuff, right?

Participant: Yes. That's correct.

Interviewer: Did it feel much immersive rather than pressing a button and be controlling?

Participant: Yeah, it felt more immersion. I felt more immersion.

Interviewer: Okay.

Interviewer: So, overall, which version felt more satisfying to you in general? Regarding everything?

Participant: That's a challenging question.

Interviewer: Like the physical interactions or the button-based...

Participant: Ah, you're just talking about the physical interaction? Or you're taking the whole overall concept?

Interviewer: No, not the overall concept.

Interviewer: The interactions.

Participant: Yeah. So, if I want to say about the interaction, if you are going to consider just by convenience, the non-VR. It's much easier. Much easier. But if you want to think about immersion and entertainment, then the VR version could be more entertaining.

Interviewer: Okay.

Participant: Because you are imagining that you are in that world and you are part of the world. So, this feel is better presented in the VR version.

Interviewer: So, you kind of like felt more in the environment and the mechanics itself when you kind of did it yourself rather than controlling a character. If I put it right, right?

Participant: In the VR version, yes.

Interviewer: Okay.

Interviewer: As we already know that there was a lot of physical constraints in the VR version and a lot of stressing. But when you kind of did it felt way too overwhelming or did it felt like it was enjoyable at times? Or when you put the physical stress over your body and you kind of like get over an obstacle, did it felt like neutral? Did it affected you negatively or positively? What's your emotion?

Participant: Sometimes it was overwhelming. So, it was overwhelming sometimes. Not all the times. Sometimes, and I just wanted, for example, to slide a little to left and right.

Interviewer: Okay.

Participant: I couldn't do that easily. So, this was challenging. It is repetitive. I'm sorry that I'm saying. Also, the ladder part was challenging. But the rest, it was, it was, it was, it wasn't that much overwhelming, and also the rope was also a little bit difficult. But that was fun. But with the ladder. With the ladder, it wasn't that much fun. But sometimes even not having fun was, I don't know how to describe it. But somehow that was also entertaining, but overall it wasn't that much fun.

Interviewer: So, now regarding the controls, which one felt more intuitive, and which one you think that you, like, which one did you grasp really well? So, out of the box, like, it was not much stressing for you to kind of, like, have a good control over the game mechanics?

Participant: Non-VR.

Interviewer: Okay. Can you explain why you felt that way?

Participant: By, by, by, because I'm used to it. So, when I want to open a door, I press a button in a video game. When I want to go, like, for example, for a ladder, it depends on the game also. So, so, so, in some games, it's just a combination of first pressing a button and then going up or down. Uh,

when in other games, it can be different. Uh, but overall, because I'm used to the non-VR version, that one was easier for me to get the control, to have the, uh, how to say, to implementation of the control was easier for me to understand. With the VR one, it was more challenging because I'm not, I'm not used to.

Interviewer: You're not familiar with it.

Participant: But also, it has the entertaining part also. So, so, the way of doing the interaction in VR, not maybe for, but overall, it was, uh, entertaining process.

Interviewer: Okay.

Interviewer: So, um, regarding the, um, kind of, like, you can say the ergonomics, did you felt any difference between the two controllers? Or is it just the same?

Participant: Uh, the two controllers.

Interviewer: Like the motion controller in VR and the Xbox controller.

Participant: Yeah, uh, the ergonomics. I mean, first, I have some issues to understand how the controller works in VR because I'm not used to it. But the ergonomics was just the controller, right?

Interviewer: Just the controller. Like, don't consider the interaction.

Participant: No, just the controller itself. Xbox controller was always ergonomic. That was, that is good. Maybe not the most ergonomic controller, but that's good. The other one, VR one, also, it felt good in my hands.

Interviewer: So, you'd say relatively, they're, like, kind of similar.

Participant: It is almost similar, yeah.

Interviewer: Okay.

Interviewer: So, any awkward interaction in either versions that you built gave you a really bad time?

Participant: Interaction?

Interviewer: Yeah. In the PC and the PC VR version, both of them.

Participant: For the VR, again, it is repetitive. The ladder. Also, the rope.

Interviewer: Okay.

Participant: The rope also, I mean, I also had difficulties with that one.

Interviewer: But was it awkward for you or was it quite natural rather than the ladder itself?

Interviewer: Ladder wasn't very natural to me. To me. The rope was better in that regard. I could understand why it is implemented like this. In VR, I think these two were the main issues for the, for the, yeah, for, in that regard. The PC, when I think, then I guess I didn't have much problem. I mean, now, I don't, I think that, that's it for now. Or, just a moment. Hmm. No, I think it was good overall.

Interviewer: Okay, so, any mechanics that you want to mention that you felt was really smooth on both versions? Like, you felt it, it was quite smooth, it wasn't awkward, you just understood it quite easily. Or get a good, get a good grasp on it very easily.

Participant: I mean, the PC version, most of the mechanics were done in a good way. But, uh, the VR one was, uh, so, for the VR, the zipline, zipline was, was nice. Also, the rope was challenging, but it was also nice. **The, the feeling that you are, uh, grabbing that rope and going forward, that was similar to real world, and I liked it.**

Interviewer: Okay.

Interviewer: So, now, one of the distinct features of the game was disabling the robots or activating your EMP, right? So, how would you differ it between the two versions? Did you play, like, did you kind of, like, felt more, um, I'm gonna say, like, anxiety in the VR version, because it's much more immersive, or was it, like, similar experience in both of them?

Participant: At first, maybe it was more challenging in VR, but after some time, I got used to it. But the way that you interact with, in that part, is, in fact, same. You press a button in non-VR, and the same button, in fact, I think, and also, in the VR, you press the same button. So, it is mainly because of the feeling of being there in VR, and, in that regard, it can be more challenging, but I think it can get used to, you can get used to it, I mean.

Interviewer: So, you would rate the VR version to be a bit more anxious, you know?

Participant: Yeah, a bit, but not , a bit.

Interviewer: Got your point.

Interviewer: So, as you have seen, that the game has a lot of crouching to stay hidden.

Participant: Yes.

Interviewer: In the beginning of the design, the crouching in VR was implemented to be a physical crouching. Okay? So, you literally have to, like, get your head down like that to crouch, and you have to play it on standing. Okay. So, then, as there was a lot of crouching overall in the whole game, we kind of, like, changed it to a button based crouching. Okay?

Participant: Uh-huh.

Interviewer: So, do you think that the physical crouching, like, dropping the physical crouching was a good idea, or would you have enjoyed it? What do you think?

Participant: I mean, that's a good question, but if there was an option to test it, I think then I could answer it in a better way. Mm-hmm. **But I think that is even, that can even make the VR part more challenging for me, because I'm not used to VR. Maybe for someone who is more used to VR, it can be more entertaining to do it like a real world.**

Interviewer: Mm-hmm.

Interviewer: So, overall, as we have always discussed, that the disabling the robots in the VR version does make the player a bit more anxious, in your sense, in your case. So, would you say, like, it's also the same for approaching any situation? For example, the beam at the end, like, when you look down, you're, like, feeling the height of the building in the VR?

Participant: **Yeah, in the VR, the feeling, that feeling is more intense. That was more intense.**

Interviewer: Okay.

Participant: **So, in the normal game, or, I mean, not, sorry, sorry, in the non-VR. In the non-VR, it's not very, how to say, I mean, it is less intense, much, or maybe much less intense. But in the VR one, it is more intense.**

Interviewer: So, do you think, like, it has something to do with the freedom of approaching a situation, like the beam, for example? Like, in the PC version and the PC VR version, between them, do you think, like, it just made you more anxious? Anxious, it just made you more, like, kind of, like, make it feel like, okay, I'm really excited about this thing, and stuff like that? Or was it very similar? Like, approaching the situation in general?

Participant: Any situation?

Interviewer: Yes, in both the versions. Like, the freedom of approaching. It's like, when you saw the beam, you may have felt like, okay, this looks scary in VR, for example. Or, in the PC versions, maybe you could have done it with a lot of ease. So, this kind of, like, the freedom of, kind of, like, moving towards this, approaching a situation, you know?

Participant: **So, overall, the VR is, the VR version is, isn't, doesn't have that much of convenience or easy, I don't, I mean, it isn't as, ease of use of the non-VR one. One of the examples, what the interaction that I want to mention, or I also want to mention, is that the, the, the way that you can move the camera. Or, in point of view, in the VR version. You, it was, like, based on some degree,**

that you could, kind of, move it. But I would, maybe, maybe it was easier to have more freedom when you want to move the camera, with the right stick.

Interviewer: Okay. So, if I don't get it wrong, you are suggesting that maybe it could have been a smooth rotation, rather than a snap.

Participant: Yeah, but, yeah, that, but I'm not sure about the feeling.

Interviewer: Okay.

Participant: That's, that is also very important in VR.

Interviewer: So, the very important question now, did you experience any kind of motion sickness throughout the game? Nausea on any of the parts, or, like, a lot of physical strain, or eye strain in general?

Participant: **Well, at first, I had dizziness.** It was more, my dizziness was more, and it was a, a bit challenging for me. **After some time, I got used to it. It became much better.** But then, after some time, I got a little bit tired. Maybe some strain, or.

Interviewer: Physical strain?

Participant: Yeah, that's the overall thing.

Interviewer: So, you would just say the PC version is not physically demanding, and, of course, is much more comfortable in the long run, right?

Participant: Yes. I agree.

Interviewer: Okay, so. Now, was there any particular portion in the VR version where you feel way too much disoriented?

Participant: Disoriented, like, like, what?

Interviewer: Like, it just kind of, like, made you really, really uncomfortable, overall.

Participant: Getting too close to the ladder. It wasn't a good experience.

Interviewer: Okay.

Participant: I don't, also, I'm not sure why, why, but, yeah, it wasn't more comfortable. It wasn't comfortable, yeah.

Interviewer: So, now, this is kind of, like, the gist of the whole thing that we discussed until now, which is the comparative analysis between these two versions, okay? So, if you have played both of them, if I tell you that you can play only one, which one would you choose, and why?

Participant: Oh, this one is a challenging question. Only I want to choose one.

Interviewer: If you want to do that, what's your justification for it?

Participant: Well, I'm more curious to see how the VR version looks, okay? Well, I'm kind of, uh, I mean, I haven't much experience of VR, and I am also kind of curious to see how is this, how is this VR games? So, I guess I will choose that one, but not for long time, to see how it is, but for long time, playing long time and convenience.

Interviewer: Overall, you, for curiosity, if there's, like, for a moment, if we take out the comfort part, you would choose the VR.

Participant: If there isn't any comfort?

Interviewer: Yes, like, for example, if you choose it that way, there's no comfort constraints.

Participant: So, if the convenience part and the comfort is same as the PC, then I will go with VR.

Interviewer: Like, not the same as PC, but for a moment, if we disregard the comfort and convenience, okay? So, I don't consider it at all.

Participant: I think VR version is more fun.

Interviewer: Okay, great.

Strengths and Weaknesses

Interviewer: So, what do you think, mention me one thing that the VR version did better than the PC version?

Participant: The implementation of the mechanics, like, how do you use a rope, how do you use a zipline, maybe, and, for example, how you push a button, press a button, and also the lever. These are better compared to the non-VR.

Interviewer: Also, what about vice-versa, like, what you liked in the PC version that was not good in the VR.

Participant: So, the easiness of the use of the controller, that is more easier, and it's more convenient, and it doesn't have that much of that, the, how to, how to say, like, in the VR version, at first, I had, I had challenge, it was challenging for me to get used to it, but in the PC, I don't have, I didn't have this.

Interviewer: So, you'd say the comfort, is much, much better in the PC?

Participant: Yeah. That's better, and it is easier also to progress in the game for me. That is also another part. It is easier to, to play the game.

Interviewer: So, I think this will be very obvious, but I will still ask you, for climbing the ladder, which version would you prefer?

Participant: For the convenience PC, non-VR.

Interviewer: Yeah, and, if you, kind of like, if we take out the problem that you mentioned, that you are, kind of, getting inside the ladder, and it's just uncomfortable for you. If that is taken out, would you rather enjoy the VR version, or the PC version, what do you think?

Participant: For climbing up the ladder, or as the overall experience?

Interviewer: Just the ladder.

Participant: The interaction, if it was, uh, less challenging, I think the VR version could have been more fun. If it was less challenging, it was challenging for me at first. Later, it got better, but still, it wasn't perfect.

Interviewer: I think, um, what about the zipline in both versions?

Participant: But, zipline, in PC version, it is also, in the non-VR, it is also nice, and the VR version, uh, the interaction part, that you want to start the zipline, I think, there is a space for improvements. Like, you should get to that, kind of, cube thing, and touch that, and press that, and, um, I think, maybe, there can be a better alternative.

Interviewer: Okay, and, for disabling the robots, regarding the robots, did you feel the VR version, like, the interaction is basically the same? Like, you press a button, and then you go behind the robot?

Participant: Yes, that's the same, in fact.

Interviewer: But, did you feel like the VR version just felt more engaging, or the, it was just the same in all the versions?

Participant: Yes, it's almost the same, almost the same. Just because of being more, more, having better immersion in VR version, yeah, that's, that, that is the main, main difference.

Interviewer: So, now, what was your most memorable moment in the VR version?

Participant: Uh, I can say some of them. Uh, ladder, again. The ladder part, again, and, also, the rope, the rope, that, that was also fun, and, there was a part that you go to, from one of the tall buildings to other tall buildings.

Interviewer: The beam?

Participant: Beam. There was a beam, yeah. That was also interesting. Mm-hmm. That's, that's the main, these are the main.

Interviewer: Okay, and, what about the PC version, like, the best moment you felt that, in the PC version, it did better than VR.

Participant: I'm thinking about that. Like, these moments, they were more memorable, they were more, how to say, they were more special moments in the VR version, compared to the non-VR one. Mm-hmm. The PC one, like, uh, for example, sometimes interaction with the robots, but, uh, that, that interaction, I, I like that part. You know, you know what I mean? I should explain more.

Interviewer: Like, you can really go very fast and disable them, like.

Participant: Yeah, yeah, yeah. Like this. I, I like this part. Um. Um. I'm not sure at the moment about the other.

Interviewer: Okay, so, if you kind of sacrifice the comfort and the convenience, as you mentioned, you would rather prefer the VR version, between these two?

Participant: Uh, if I don't consider that, VR can be more engaging.

Interviewer: Okay, and, what about, the vice versa, that if you wanna sacrifice the immersion of VR, would you rather, for comfort and convenience, you'd rather choose the PC version any day, right?

Participant: Hmm. Can you say the question?

Interviewer: Like, for the PC version? For comfort and convenience?

Interviewer: Yes, that's better in PC. No, no, or non-VR. That's better, yes.

Interviewer: So, um. What do you suggest that will make the VR version better, for instance, when you play it? Like, what are your suggestions that could make it better?

Participant: Mm-hmm. So, that camera movement?

Interviewer: Like, the snap?

Participant: Yeah, that one. Mm-hmm. Uh, ladder, I'm sorry, that's repetitive.

Interviewer: No, no, no, it's fine. It's fine.

Participant: Maybe even, oh, the zipline also? The interaction with the zipline? I think it can, there are other ways, maybe that can be better. The rope, the rope part was, no, the rope part was good, I

think. But it was challenging to reach the, I mean, to, maybe it was, I need more time to get used to it. I felt that the speed of the movement wasn't enough.

Interviewer: Mm-hmm.

Participant: But I'm not considering the dizziness and, and, uh, I think that's it, I guess.

Interviewer: What about the PC version? Any solutions that could make it better? Any interaction that you felt could be changed?

Participant: For the PC version, uh, I like the, when you take the zipline, I like to have more freedom about moving the camera and seeing other place.

Interviewer: Mm-hmm.

Participant: That you have it on the VR, but it, it doesn't exist on the non-VR version. Yeah, and, uh, the ladder was, the ladder was good. Ah, ah, ah, also the rope part, I, I, in fact, I told it when I'm, I'm repeating it, this step wasn't long enough, mm-hmm, then it was a slow, or a bit slow, and, these are the main things.

Interviewer: So, after trying the, trying both the versions, would you be interested in playing more VR games in general?

Participant: Um, um, and that's a good question. Now, my question about VR is, uh, a little, maybe a little more, I'm not quite sure, but, but, uh, still, I'm not that much, uh, how to say, uh, still, uh, well, maybe, maybe, but, uh, at least there are, maybe one, the minimum is one title that I like to play on VR, and, yeah, but, still, maybe, maybe it is better, I'm not sure, exactly.

Interviewer: So, um, it's like, the VR version, as you say, it felt more immersive, so, yes, would you be more interested in trying this kind of stuff in general?

Participant: No, I, what I, I'm saying, I'm saying about my personal opinion, so, this, kind of, for example, dizziness, and similar feelings, I feel, well, of course, I'm just saying, I'm, I'm just speaking about myself, maybe, if this feeling was much, much less, and it was much easier to use, also, the, also, the dizziness is not the only feeling, there are also maybe some others, but also, uh, it depends also on the, maybe, like, if you could feel that you are more immersed in the world, like, for example, uh, by the very high quality, how to say, maybe resolution, very high resolution, that you feel, that you are, that you feel that the immersion is better, with the higher resolution, but also, maybe, **the depth, I don't know why, but I felt that the depth is not too much**, the depth of the, like, when you are, when you are in the VR, VR, and, that I was using, I felt that the depth is not enough.

Interviewer: Okay, like, by depth, do you mean, like.

Participant: the depth, for example, **for example, here is a building, and then, almost in 100 meter, is another building, the difference between this one and that one, the depth, you don't, it is not same as the real world.**

Interviewer: Okay, the distance doesn't feel the same.

Participant: So, technically, the difference between distance isn't, uh, optimal, or, at, it's not perfect.

Interviewer: Okay, yeah.

Interviewer: So, is there anything else about the, experience of either version, that you want to add, like, any suggestions, anything that you did like, anything you didn't, at all?

Participant: Um, yeah, for the suggestion, I think, I'm, in fact, I mentioned, um, um, right now, I think, I think I told most of them, or, yeah.

Interviewer: So, is there anything else, like, you want to add, above, from that, like, is there anything at all, regarding the two versions?

Participant: Yeah, also, something, I just, want to point it down. **The, uh, HUD, I feel, there is also, space for improvement, in both versions. Okay, whether it is, the non-VR, or the VR. Mm-hmm, like, in non-VR, I felt that, for example, one of the texts, I felt that is, too long, and, I felt that, there could be, maybe, sometimes, a better way of showing, what you, what you can do, or, what you should do in the game, or, what's better to do, also, VR version, similarly.**

Interviewer: Okay, thank you so much, Participant, for your time, and your patience.

Participant: You're welcome.

Interview – 05

Play Pattern

1. PC

2. PCVR

Interviewer: So, that's all then. First of all, thank you so much for your time.

Participant: You're welcome.

Interviewer: I will also give you some background, though we've already done it, but I'll still give you some background about the thesis. So I'm trying to kind of like focus on three points that have some subcategories inside them, which is sensory engagement, and by that I mean the immersion in general in the game, between the two versions, and the control schemes of the both versions, and the convenience in general. So, let's start with some backgrounds and I would love to know what type of games do you usually play and how often do you play?

Participant: So what I play is often times a first-person or third-person shooter, something like The Last of Us, Horizon Zero Dawn, these are third-person. Something like your Quake, like... I haven't played much first-person lately. Yeah, like your Crysis or stuff like that. This is something that is a good chunk of my gaming. At the moment I'm playing Hades 2, which is kind of like a roguelike, very different top-down isometric dungeon crawler. What else to say? I play a lot of adventure games, basically point-and-click stuff that's really not high immersion, but story-wise pretty heavy on the story. I do play like your JRPG, like Final Fantasy or like Chrono Trigger or Octopath Traveler, stuff like that. So, very much not a twitchy game or highly immersive game, but more like a top-down world exploration game.

Interviewer: In general, how often do you play?

Participant: As often as I get the time to, so during the semester basically not at all, and during the off-lecture part of the semester I might play like two, three, four times a week if I get time to that, and then it might be anywhere from like sitting down for an hour or also maybe on a weekend maybe I play for four or five hours straight if I get the time. But overall I would say I play maybe during the semester maybe three or four hours a week at most, maybe probably even less, and during the break, more quote-unquote break, I might play 20 hours a week just for a short stretch of time.

Interviewer: So, have you used VR before, and it could be like for anything, not just playing games?

Participant: So, in general I've been experimenting with it, but it's not something that I've played a lot with. In terms of games, basically your standard Beat Saber, you're Half-Life Alyx only to some degree, but at least that much. I have tried a couple of things in VR. I'm doing a course on the WebXR thing, so it might be something like a web application with interactive components in VR. So, more in direction of applications. So, one of these is something like simulation of a building that you might sell to someone in VR. I test a lot of student projects here and there, but only basically like 20 minutes of that and then it's off to the next project. So, I wouldn't really count that to be honest. So, I would say it's probably half gaming, half experimentation.

Interviewer: Okay. So, regarding the two versions, was there any difference between the immersion that you felt on both of them?

Participant: For me personally, I would give a slight edge to the VR version because, in general, I can be very immersed in any type of screen-based gaming as well. So, I totally can lose myself in a Deus Ex as one of the other first-person shooters and that's perfectly fine for me. Or, The Last of Us stuff is good sound, usually. In this particular case, for example, like looking over the edge of something that's a very steep fall I could fall down from. This is something that is definitely more. I feel this is more something that could happen to me in VR than in the keyboard and mouse or controller-based stuff. Also, basically, with a controller-based game, you don't get like this type of leaning forward looking over the edge and looking straight down. That is something that you just cannot do in most games or in most control schemes and that is something that actually I would say is better in VR. Overall, immersion. Again, like this gives a slight edge to that one.

The going over one of these transportation lines, I forgot the name, but this is something that has... In the screen-based one, it's kind of just an animation that happens, and in VR, it's something where I feel like, oh, this is doing something to me. So, I kind of have like this feeling of being actually moved in some way. It doesn't really feel like on a slack line, yeah, for sure, but at least I have this feeling of, oh, yeah, something's happening here. So, this would make me say I think VR has a slight edge.

The rest of the game elements, they don't do all that much for me. So, in terms of difference with regard to immersion, but I also kind of just plain out found it interesting to have like the ladder movement part. Not sure that counts for immersion, but because I also kind of felt the disconnect because this is not... Well, this is part of what I do on a ladder, but it's not actually how a ladder works. So, like the missing of like the physical exertion of myself or with the overhead climbing

rope line. I don't know what the name is, sorry. The one that I fell down so often. This is also not really how that works, but it's a fun interaction. It's a fun thing to do. So, I would say that these elements combined, I would give a slight edge to VR version, yeah.

Interviewer: Okay, sounds great. So, what about the interaction of physically pressing the buttons in general within the two versions?

Participant: I do need some more feedback there. I do think that even like a slight vibration might help a little bit, but also kind of... I kind of want my hand to be stopped and I know that's not quite possible just now. But this kind of makes these interactions less satisfying that I would like them to be, and again, that's not something that I would fault you personally for because you can't change physics and stuff. How dare you? But it's still something that in general I think VR needs to find some way of making this possible. We had one of the games that we had a hackathon just now, just a couple of days ago again, and one of the games was like a whack-a-mole game and it looks the part and it's well made. It just is not great fun because you're just pushing air around and it just feels like... Yeah, like there needs to be something stopping me from actually pushing through the floor.

Interviewer: There should be some backward force, that's kind of like disrupting you.

Participant: Exactly. I need to be feeling like something is actually there. So that is... It sounds weird but I think it's half the fun of actually hitting something, and again, I don't have a solution there. I'm just saying why it sometimes doesn't quite work for me and beyond.

Interviewer: So regarding these interactions with the levers, how is the view on that side?

Participant: This is better I think because there's... Of course these are like pretty obviously interactable element big levers. So not like in a flat where it's like a dilly dilly switch on the wall or something. So you can recognize them from far. So I don't really have an expectation how these would feel, and in some regards I have like an expectation how a button should feel or react. But for these levers I don't. So I don't... At least I don't mind as much. I think they were great. Also I think they had a little bit of amount of vibration going on, right?

Interviewer: Yeah.

Participant: I think this helps a little bit. These I would say work pretty well.

Interviewer: So regarding the physical exertion you mentioned on the ladder, on the rope, and kind of like you were pulling yourself on the rope and stuff like that.

Participant: Yeah.

Interviewer: When you did that, did it make like the feeling... Was it positive or was it negative or neutral in the sense?

Participant: I'm not really sure how to answer that. So positive or negative like with regard to immersion interaction or just how I generally feel doing that?

Interviewer: You generally feel about it.

Participant: Okay. Pretty neutral I would say. So it's for one thing yeah it's kind of fun to get something different in the game. So in that regard it's positive but overall it's not... I don't think it's like... I'm not sure if I would just go and get a game to play this part or something like that. It's a nice interaction but it's not something that makes or breaks a game I would say. So I think this is why I was kind of happy about like the in-between messages and dialogues and stuff like that. Because I think having the idea that this world somehow is weird or somehow what I do matters for whatever reason. I think this is a much stronger way of keeping me engaged with the game to be quite honest.

Interviewer: Okay. So which version regarding the controls did you prefer? Like was it any difference between the motion controllers and the Xbox controller? Was it like similar on your hands and the feel of the game?

Participant: I have a little bit of a caveat there because I'm very used to the Xbox controller. That is the layout that I'm very familiar with. It's the same one on the like Arrow GLI or on the Xbox that I play at home and stuff like that. So that is something where I know oh I press X. That's just memory. What's it called? Muscle memory basically, and on the quest controllers I constantly needed to read oh I press X for that. Oh where's X again? Oh it's over here. So that is a disconnect. That is a little bit unfair because I'm just not used to that one. If I would play the same 100 hours on a quest that I did on an Xbox probably more than 100 hours. Then probably this disconnect would go away and then it would be much fairer to compare the two. Right now let's say this is something where I realize in the moment yeah I need to look up the button layout. So I'm back in the game person playing a game not person sneaking around in a detective game or whatever. Like a spy game probably more fitting. So I would give a slight edge to the Xbox controller there.

Interviewer: But did the mechanics on how the locomotion worked, did the VR version gave you better control or the Xbox version gave you better control regarding the locomotion?

Participant: For the most part the Xbox controller also because of strafing because it's just a style that I play in. I'm basically never going in a straight line in a shooter type game. Also in a third person type game I'm probably also constantly doing the left and right thing around corners and stuff like that. So with that I was more used to it and it felt more like the default I'm used to. The

default that is established probably for a reason because it's just successful at achieving the goal that you're trying to get to, and with the quest for one thing I'm not as used to like physically looking around corners. This is a great, this is a big part of games like these in my opinion. Like the oh what's over there. I think the sonar is helping a lot in that regard to not having to do that as much. But I still think it's something that I actually like in these games. So this was hindering me a little bit.

The headset was easier in one particular place because the balancing thing was much much easier. Because I had much finer control over like tenths of a degree of movement where I was actually going as compared to the controller. Also it's much more direct in that regard. So with the controller getting to the exact with the dead zone that the controller intrinsically has, and with the sensitivity setup that you will have it's you can get used to controllers but it's always kind of like a step in between, and I think the head movement is just hands down so much more precise and direct. This was much much better control this aspect of it. So overall I can't really say it's a little bit of a toss up though. Mostly I think the Xbox controller came easier to me and this one place is much much better to control in a headset.

Interviewer: Were any of the interactions felt awkward between the both versions?

Participant: It took me a while in the controller based run. In the first run it took me a while to actually recognize oh I need to get to these robots from behind, and then basically I was kind of looking for not so much what's the active area of the robot. I was more looking like what do I need to aim at. So basically I was looking for like something like a crosshair. What to exactly align with the robot in particular. So I think I spent the first couple of minutes in the controller based game figuring out how exactly this part works, and by the time I got to the headset I already figured out how this works, and it was much easier to just sneak more or less sneak up on them, and just try to basically tag it, and also I think I did this with the hands particularly. I'm not sure if I would have needed to. But it also kind of was something that I kind of felt I wanted to do. Like something where I would like need to grab the robot and do something to them. Even though I probably could have sat here and just trigger the button I'm not sure. But also with the representation of a virtual hand in there it kind of felt natural to kind of like do something to the robot somehow. So that is definitely something where I would say it was easier in VR. But also because I already had memorized how this game is played.

So possibly having like a... I'm not sure. This is probably ridiculous to do. But playing it like a minute on PC, a minute on the headset to get acquainted with these mechanics, and then doing the actual longer run when you have already understood all the mechanics. Might be a more fair comparison here. I'm not entirely sure. But yeah.

Interviewer: So as you already mentioned that you edged the VR a bit on the immersion side.

Participant: Mm-hmm.

Interviewer: So was sneaking and disabling the robots felt more like... Did it made you more anxious than the VR version in general? Or was it the same?

Participant: I think it's... I think VR is sabotaged a little bit because by the time I got to VR I already understood that these basically don't pose a threat to me. So I think the very low difficulty and the getting used to where they are and having been through the level already. So for example also in a game like Deus Ex where it's a similar mechanic of usually being sneaky and evading enemies. I sometimes played the level the second time around just because I already know and have memorized where everything is and what triggers what kind of reaction, and basically the second run is never quite as exciting because you already... Basically you have your whole problem solved already and you already know where you want to go and what... Around this corner this is going to be safe so I don't worry as much I don't need to... I don't need to worry that anything happens after that I just need to get to the checkpoint basically, and this was the same for the VR run through so it's an unfair comparison I think.

To be quite honest the VR run wasn't like sneaky spy exciting in any way. Because I already knew what the robots were doing but they basically are too dumb to really hurt me in any way. Also there's not really a big penalty here for dying. So in some games like you have your Super Meat Boy or something that you have a very very very quick repeat cycle on. You die and you just start again it's like not even a second or half a second it's just instantly restart. As opposed to your Tomb Raider Shadow of the Tomb Raider for example. You die and you restart but there's like two minutes of loading time before that, and that alone is kind of like takes dying from being a nuisance to being like oh dang it I need to do this again, and this was not quite the case here so there's not really any downside to getting caught. So these two things in combination basically meant that there was no real stakes to being caught or something like that.

I think a little bit of story fixes that and I also think that a little bit of stake for example maybe the last checkpoint is not as nearby. The checkpoints were kind of convenient I don't hate that there were checkpoints I think it's a good idea. But also the checkpoints basically meant that whenever I died I didn't really lose anything. I didn't really get hurt by that. I didn't need to complete something that I already collected or something like that. Not that I'm a particular fan of that because it kind of is unpleasant to do that again. But it's kind of making dying a little bit more, it raises the stakes on dying a little bit. So to some degree I think I want this in a game. For example in The Last of Us you might need to replay like half a chapter or something if you die, and that means that you need

to do a lot of sometimes very, very hard to figure. I know the figuring out part has been done but the, like you need a little bit of luck and a lot of good execution in *The Last of Us*, and if you die late in one of these action bubbles then doing it again this good is sometimes just hard to do, and to some degree I think you need this in a game like this.

Interviewer: So just for the record I know your opinion about it but I'm going to ask it again.

Participant: Yes, absolutely.

Interviewer: As I already mentioned that I wanted to include physical crouching in the game. I had implemented it but later when I tested it felt like it was stressing just to crouch all the time to not get affected by the enemy and also the enemy was quite hard at that time.

Participant: Yeah, yeah.

Interviewer: So what do you think? Would you have physical crouching or would you have preferred the option to have them? Or would you just prefer this button based crouching that was inside the game?

Participant: So from a would I actually play the game standpoint I think sit down VR is what I would choose. Just because I kind of come here for relaxation and for being told a good story or for experiencing something nice. From an interaction standpoint as a person who likes to explore what's possible **I would absolutely freaking love to play this in a big big hall. In a big room where I could actually walk all of the distance. This would be amazing I think.** So and then if I would have to walk everything and basically in that case also crouching. Sorry strafing is not an issue because I'm actually doing the whole movement. So walking around and then I absolutely would love to also do the crouching part. I think disconnected from the movement crouching doesn't make a whole ton of sense to me. If I'm kind of I'm sitting down here but I'm moving the stick to move. This is kind of weird a little bit but if I get to do the whole movement everything, and it really matters that I crouch because only the crouching is what's controlling me. Because only my bodily movement is what's moving me around the room here. Then I think I would absolutely love this. This is kind of like your laser tag hall style experience then. If we had any kind of space where we could try something like this I would absolutely try this, and I'm pretty sure this would be this combination would be would be pretty awesome.

Interviewer: So after you completed the VR version did you feel some kind of motion sickness, nausea, dizziness or vertigo?

Participant: Yeah. **Like 20 minutes of VR gives me a very slight dizziness always. So this is not really tied to this experience but I had this here too. So I did have like this this moment where I'm**

like yeah I'm kind of it was enjoyable but I was also kind of glad that I now got to take off the headset again. Because I think if I think if it was twice as long I probably would have needed to pause at this point. So like after like half an hour or 45 minutes for sure I think I would have just needed a break. So overall I would say slight dizziness but very manageable, very much not a problem yet.

Interviewer: Okay and was there anything that you kind of felt a bit discomforting regarding both of the versions? Like you already described that in VR, it's of course hard that you have a one kilogram or two kilogram of headset dangling on your head. But regarding you also mentioned the kind of like looking controls of the controller it's too fast. Would you prefer it to be a bit slower or would you prefer control over it that you can just adjust it yourself?

Participant: Yeah. **In general the headset didn't bother me at all so this was fine. I could have worn this for a while longer of course. This is not an issue.** At some point I kind of ran into this table a little bit so I was kind of close by and I wasn't sure which way to turn right now. So there was a little bit about the setup I would have preferred to have a little bit more space around me. I just kind of neglected to basically push back a little bit more before starting. This was kind of something I would have changed if I were to do it again.

Control scheme was fine. Control in VR in general I think was pretty fine. **I would have preferred in both versions for the walking speed to be slightly higher. I think it's kind of it feels like a slow walk and in games like these in the in between spaces between two things that are happening I kind of would usually press shift and run a little bit of stuff like that.** For the Xbox controller part I would say the same thing again like this walking speed is something for both. For the controller part I would have preferred the sensitivity of looking around the right stick sensitivity to be a little bit slower so I kind of had a little bit hard time controlling where I was looking at. But also I'm not a controller type first person shooter gamer so I think a person who's used to first person games on a controller probably didn't have this problem. This is something that I just choose not to play a lot. So shooters are very much mouse and keyboard for me normally, and this would fall under a first person mechanic for me so I don't think I would have had the same problem in mouse and keyboard setup.

Other than that I don't think I would change anything. I do think once you're doing this as a game you wouldn't have like the collider box visible. I think that is something that I don't mind it because I know what it is. If I didn't know what it was I might find it weird or annoying or whatever. It didn't bother me and I do think we need for the two balancing beam acts I need to know where my feet quote unquote are, and I basically used the circle of the middle point there to basically keep that on the beam and that's good. So for the game itself if you were to disable these gizmos then you

absolutely need something like a harsh shadow in this place or actual feet animated there or something like that. Just so that I know exactly where I am. In a third person type game I think usually games that have this kind of mechanic they are more in a third person type than in a first person type. I would say I would wait or guess I am not sure. But basically you need the reference where the body is in the relation to the object that you are balancing on or that you are avoiding in that case.

Yeah but basically walking speed is the only thing that I would slightly change and maybe right thumbstick sensitivity. But the controller layout other than that is pretty much fine. I did need to look up the buttons a while but I think that's something that I would have had to do anyway. So I don't really fault you for that. I don't think that was a bad choice or anything. It's not like there would be a better, clearly better choice or something. These are interactions that are not very established so that's not like oh you always press A for jump. We don't jump here so there's no established thing. I think B for crouching is just fine. I think X for interaction is also probably pretty popular. X is also often attack in some types of games. But in general I think it's a good choice. I wouldn't change anything about it.

Interviewer: So as you play both versions now, if you had the option to play only one, which one would you choose and why?

Participant: Hmm. So for a demonstration of like 20 minutes I could choose either. I would probably choose VR for the novelty and for the slight edge on the immersion. If this was something like a 10 hour story game or something, I would probably at some point switch over to mouse and keyboard just because I can't play this for much longer without it being a problem for me. But it also depends on, for example, if there's very interesting interactions in here like the ladders, like the rope things or the rope interaction with the button thing I press that's usually behind me if I want to look in the direction. That is another one I, sorry, I forgot this audio. This is something there that I need, that I think needs a slight alteration because it does work, clearly it works, but I kind of want to look in the direction that I'm going. So I kind of need the button to be somewhere else or I need to be able to grab the rope and that starts the traveling process. I think this was my first try also to try to do the same thing as for the, for the other rope, basically trying to just grab there and hold the, the not shoulder button.

Interviewer: The grab button.

Participant: The grab button, yeah. Exactly, and this is something that I would try if people come to this conclusion naturally without the big red button. Yeah, in general, these kinds of interactions, this is something that might lead me to try this game actually in VR first, and I might actually prefer

this over the mouse and keyboard thing because this is actually something that I think, yeah, that can be fun, that can be novel or unique enough that it's actually preferable over mouse and keyboard to be honest. Yeah, I think I would probably prefer it in the VR headset. It's also basically something that, you know, **Half-Life Alyx is something that they do very good. I think the amount of stuff you actually get to do with your hands in that game is really just amazing, and I think this is, this is going this very direction and there's good things to be done here.**

Interviewer: So what do you think of, if you have to name one thing that the VR version did better than the PC, what would that be? Because it's kind of exactly the same environment, same enemy positions and everything.

Participant: So I want to say, like fine motor control is definitely something that's much, much, much better. So the, it comes down basically back to the sensitivity on the sticks or the limited amount of what I can do with a stick, as opposed to, oh yeah, I'll just put my hand here. That is definitely better, and also, and I'm pretty used to first-person shooters. So I'm not generally having a problem with that, but **I think VR gives me a much better sense of scale. I realized that, no, I didn't realize, I noticed that kind of, I was kind of trying to look around much more in VR than I was in the, in the mouse and keyboard thing. So basically I was, in one place I was just standing there like looking over the level and being like, yeah, this is kind of a big area here that I get to occupy,** and that is something that I also sometimes do in first-person games in a Horizon Zero Dawn, which has very pretty landscape. I also might just stand there, look at the landscape for a while or take a screenshot or stuff like that. But I do think that this is much more, this feels really much more real in VR. **There's just a stereoscopic view of something and the micro-movement that I get to do that gives me a sense of scale of the whole environment. I think that's much better in VR.**

Interviewer: Can you do the same for the vice versa? What do you think the PC version did better than the VR?

Participant: I had an easier time controlling it in general, I would say. So even though I like the sensitivity and the precision I can get from a headset, I like this part better. But overall I'm much more used to the Xbox controller layout. So this is basically something that just, this is something that just disappear into my body. So I don't really need to think about buttons or anything. I just sit there and I control myself running there, and with the VR headset where I much more exist in the space, I was much more often like looking down at my hands. Yeah, this is the X button. So something that I don't do with the controller at all basically.

So **the weird thing that, again like this takes me much better into the place and I'm embodying this avatar much better in VR. I still kind of have to think back at, yes, I have something in my hands**

that is buttons that I need to press, that I need to up, down, left, right. Okay, no, this is, and basically only with the X, Y, A, B buttons, not with the thumbsticks because the thumbsticks just work basically. These also disappear into my brain and this is just a continuation of my body basically. This is not as bad. But the X, Y, A, B buttons were something that I struggled with, but mostly for how used I am to this kind of controller.

The interesting part would be, and to some degree I hate this, but to some degree I can understand why a lot of games choose to not really use a lot of buttons, where you basically only have the trigger for everything, and I kind of don't like that because there's so much things I could interact with or that I could do differently with these buttons. But also now I kind of get why they choose to do it. **Because if you start thinking about the buttons then these are no longer my hands. In that moment these are my controllers and then I'm not really part of this world,** and that's kind of weird too because I think in that way it was kind of like a bit of a revelation, because these buttons in particular, that is just something that took me out of this one in particular, and I think it's a testament to how good this game already is, because a tiny thing like that, there was nothing else that I noticed to the same degree, and that's I think a good thing for something that's still a pretty new development here, a pretty new level, a pretty quote-unquote untested thing, because basically it's not a AAA game that's been tested to death by a hundred people. So that's a pretty, I don't take this the wrong way, the buttons, even though I don't agree with how I controlled this, but yeah, not for your choices, more for how used I am to them. Everything else just worked, I would say. Everything else was very good.

Interviewer: So regarding the interactions, how would you kind of like defer the particular refinement of the ladder climbing?

Participant: It worked pretty well. I think at the beginning one time I kind of fell down again, because I kind of didn't grab in the correct space. I might imagine these hit zones to be slightly larger than they actually appear in game, but also after... Oh, I noticed something about what I did. So basically what I did was I was always looking at my hands. In the real world, basically I would just know, oh, I'm touching the ladder, so I don't need to look at it. So this haptic feedback again... But again, it was like in the button example, where I were to push something with the ladder, I would like to know when my hands are indexed to the sides. This is just something we cannot really, really do, and even the vibration feedback wouldn't solve this part of the problem. So I was constantly like looking at my hands left and right for each rung.

I also, I kind of had the impression in the beginning for a ladder, even though for a ladder I would probably also do the left and right outside grip, I kind of... **My first try was kind of going on the rungs, on the step things. I think it's rungs, right? So I'm not sure if this is something worth**

adding, because you don't have to go either or. You could just offer both if you want. But I'm also not sure if I'm like the only person or if it's just something that's universal that people would try this.

Interviewer: No, you're definitely not.

Participant: Okay, interesting.

Interviewer: Because many people, among the five of you...

Participant: I could imagine this...

Interviewer: I think four of the people just instantly went there and grabbed the yellow bars of the rungs.

Participant: I was about to say yellow. I would love to do the exact same thing with another five fresh people and just have the bars be silver and the sides be yellow. I would love to make this tiny change and I would love to see if it's... I could see this go both ways. Sometimes people are just like, yeah, this is obviously how I do this, because I do this in real life, I'm not sure. But I could totally also see like the Tomb Raider style. Oh, this is yellow, I'll just grab this.

Interviewer: Exactly.

Participant: You could totally see this go both ways. I don't know how it would turn out, and that's why I would think it would be very interesting to do this with three or four people if you get around to that. Because this is basically... Oh, what's the English word for that? **In German, you call this Produktsprache. So a product talking to you how it wants to be used. For example, this bottle, it's very clear that I kind of... It's made for my hand. I can grab it or I have this handle here.** I would hold it right here because it's a slight indentation, stuff like that. **The product tells me how it wants to be used, and in VR, you get the same thing. So if you haven't looked at stuff like Don Norman's The Design of Everyday Things, this is absolutely a book for you because I think real-world products and how they are designed, they can inform a lot about how you would design stuff in VR as well because it's the same thing.** This ladder speaks to me how it wants to be used, and maybe swapping the colors would be all that's needed.

Or maybe, for example, in a very nice hi-fi set, you have like this volume knob and this knob basically from the way that it's... The size it has, you know, how you grip that. The way that it's maybe has fine ridges around it, markings around it. Or maybe it has big, huge chunking markings where you're like, oh, this is like a chunk, chunk, chunk, like on a washing machine or whatever. So these tiny things, these tiny details tell you so much about how this will feel if I grab it, and we are so used to this in the world. So for example, this one here on this, this kind of talks to me in a way

where I say, oh, this is probably a smooth button, and one with slight ridges is probably something that says click, click, click, click, and one with big ridges on it is more like chunk, chunk, chunk, chunk, and we know how the world works, and if you see this in VR, we kind of, even though we don't get the same feeling, we kind of still feel like it's a button like that.

So for example, I could also imagine that these levers, depending on how they are designed, they will feel differently, even though it's exactly the same motion that I perform. This would be also interesting to see in this. But I think the ladder are something that I would absolutely, if you get around to it, I would absolutely test it if it makes a difference.

Interviewer: Yeah, because just what you mentioned, I think it is very important. Because when I was designing the level, it kind of like I had this indentation that I wanted to base the whole environment according to color codes.

Participant: Good idea.

Interviewer: That yellow means you just grab it.

Participant: Ah, yeah. So you're... But then the rungs of the ladder, I think they were yellow, right?

Interviewer: Yeah. Because then... That was kind of like something that I just missed.

Participant: Yeah, that's fine.

Interviewer: Because anything else that you see in the world, yellow means you grab it. Yellow means you push it, yellow means you interact with it, and anything red, you just know it's a ramp. So I tried to produce this kind of color codes to guide the player through the environment.

Participant: I think it works, and probably the ladder tells you that it works too well. Or that you actually basically a little bit broke your own rule, and that it works so well that people started grabbing this ladder instinctively. But again, this is a pretty cool achievement already, I would say. Because I do think this is something we can absolutely learn from this. This is very interesting, I think. Nice.

Interviewer: Thanks. So what was your most memorable moment in VR?

Participant: All right. In VR?

Interviewer: Yes.

Participant: Okay, in VR. That I would probably have to give to this moment when I was standing there and admiring the view for a while. I really do think that it's something that I enjoyed, just taking a couple of seconds to just like, yeah, this is where I come from, this is where I can go. That is kind of fun, like having the overview, and also, I rarely get to play stuff

that's more than two or three minutes. So that was kind of nice, and the standing there looking over the whole map is kind of like the, yeah, that's nice. The moment where I could honor that it's actually something quite, quite far developed already, I would say. This kind of stood out, and I don't think I did this in the controller run, in the first run. I think I only did this in VR. I think I enjoyed the tag your it mechanic a lot in with this robot. So I'm not sure if this would qualify, but I also kind of enjoyed this part. What else did I? Favorite moment. Favorite moment specific to VR, I think. Yeah, I think it would be probably the like, like having a sense of scale of this whole, whole thing.

Interviewer: What about the PC version?

Participant: What did I enjoy most for the PC version? I generally enjoyed it in that sense that kind of it's something you can totally play and that has no obvious errors of any kind. I'm not sure if I can point at something in particular where I'm like, oh yeah, this was very special. So in the PC version, and don't get this the wrong way, so in the PC version it didn't stand out all that much. So basically, you have had ladders in games since Duke Nukem 3D or you have had things like these lines that you slide over in like a Tomb Raider. I play a lot of Tomb Raider also. So these are not really stand out special. But of course, doing this on your own in a very limited amount of time is already pretty special. So that is not to diminish the amount of work that went into this, but it's just like the PC version didn't really, with the very spoiled view like playing all these AAA titles of 100 people, there was nothing where I would say, oh, this was beyond what I would usually get from a game. But also, hey, it was already pretty, pretty amazing from what I would get for a student project where usually you don't get around to all these details. I think for the PC version, I would probably say that what I liked the most is that actually it felt like being in one of these well-produced large games where you get like, oh, I'm entering an area. I get like the radio message that I have to do this and that. Yeah, so the overall sense of having a very complete game was pretty good, I would say there. Nothing in particular, nothing single thing, not one single thing.

Interviewer: So, as you tried and it's kind of like you can quote-unquote say it's still traversal genre-based game.

Participant: I would say it is, yes. I would say it is.

Interviewer: So, would you be interested in this genre after playing it in VR if it's kind of like mass-produced and made to like a complete like AA or AAA standard?

Participant: I didn't quite catch the beginning of the question, so.

Interviewer: It's kind of like, would you be, as you try the prototype?

Participant: Yeah.

Interviewer: Now, just think about it this way that it gets mass-produced and it's like a AA or AAA standard, would you love to delve on it? Yeah. Because there are games like the climb where you just climb, stuffs up, it's a traversal game.

Participant: Yeah.

Interviewer: But would you just love this taste of stealth where it's kind of like very limited on what you can do to harm the enemies?

Participant: Yeah.

Interviewer: Would you just prefer this genre or...?

Participant: I would absolutely give this a try. I do think it's, from what I feel like playing this, I do think it's similar to what a Deus Ex does or what a Splinter Cell does, and this is definitely a type of game that I enjoy a lot, so I would absolutely try and play this also. I think it's a very interesting combination. It's also something that neither Deus Ex nor Splinter Cell has. So, you have like, maybe the balancing part, that is something that's relatively common in games like these. The climbing or grabbing onto stuff part, of course, is not really in any of these that I know of at least, or that I've played. This part felt a little bit like a sweet spot between your Splinter Cell Deus Ex or your Tomb Raider, because Tomb Raider absolutely has these. Your Tomb Raider 2013 and onwards, like the Tomb Raider with no numbers and the Tomb Raider, Shadow of the Tomb Raider and these have this climbing mechanic with these hooks and stuff like that. This feels somewhat similar to that, I think, and I love these games a lot, so this is a good testament to having this in there. I would absolutely play the crap out of this if it was like a full game.

Interviewer: Is there anything else that you want to add? Any compliments, any suggestions that would make it better?

Participant: So, again, in general, I really like this. I really think it's a good achievement so far. It's something that I would easily see myself playing. I think it's interesting to get something this refined this early in a project. So, having like 15, 20 minutes of gameplay in something is a pretty good achievement already. I could see mechanics like, for example, right now it's basically you have like your to-dos, you press buttons, and then the to-dos are done. I could also see like Quake 2 does this a lot. Quake 2 has a tiny level, but it makes you go over there, get a key, go over there, press a button, go over here, go do that, and you basically traverse around the level like 15 times to achieve something, and it still feels pretty fresh. They have a very good eye for how a level looks different if you come at it from a different direction, and also, they modify it slightly in the sense

where you press this button and now this whole area here is flooded and looks completely differently and stuff like that.

So, this is something I could easily see for this type of game as well where you would, for example, you disable communication and now something about the level also changes. Or basically, all the robots are now like, oh, we can't communicate anymore. We are now like running around like chicken and we are now much easier to get, I think it's called aggro in some games where you would basically activate them much quicker to follow you. I could see some environmental changes like that that would make it easier. Or maybe it starts raining and when it's raining they can't hear me as good and then I need to wait for the moment when it rains in this particular area so I can sneak by, stuff like that. Right now it's pretty much one path that I can take, at least the only path that I could find, maybe there's another one. I could, for this type of game, I usually, especially Deus Ex is very good at this offering you like two or three paths and sometimes they are so well hidden that you think, oh, this is the only path and you play it two or three times and then it's, oh, over there there's like a trash can if I move it over there's another pathway. So this style of game I think really needs different pathways around, around the level. This is something I could see done.

Then generally I would totally love to play more of this, so having a longer story, more level to play, more levels. Then even though all of these are buttons of course and all of these just check off a box, in most games it's the same way but the button is not a button, the button is something you collect or the button is something, some area that you have visited so you have stood in front of the surveillance monitors. That's just also a check mark, you've been through this area and this unlocks some other area or I have, yeah, you have the levers that activate the elevators of course, but right now they're always next to the elevator that they control which makes sense in the real world. You would put the button next to the elevator of course, but in games like these you often times, yeah, like they make you go to the control panel over there activating the power, then you go to the elevator that now has power and like, then you get to actually get the elevator down to your level or stuff like that. So for example, Half-Life you need to complete a circuit first and then you get to get the elevator to you.

Yeah, so there is definitely a lot of meat still on that bone, I think there's still a lot more to be mined. Also this, of course in a game that's produced further, you for example have like, like there's enemies that you can just walk by and they don't even notice you and there's enemies that you need to sneak by because they kind of know that you are there, and then maybe there's enemies that have such good hearing that even sneaking doesn't work for them. For example, there's something that a lot of games, for example, Crysis did this. Crysis has these normal enemies where you just need to do invisibility and just walk through and then later on you get enemies that still see you even though

you're invisible, and that's kind of raising the stakes ever more. Now that's something that you can do.

Then depending on where you want to take this, of course like extending range of your EMP or being better at sneaking up on robots or maybe for the first couple of levels you can only basically temporarily disable them and later on you learn how to do this permanently. So this is changes that you can do that might raise the stakes or maybe it's something that you, maybe you collect something from these robots, maybe you steal some of their power or something that reloads your EMP or whatever, I don't know. So there's, I think there's a lot of things that make sense in this kind of universe.

That also means I think a good step for this, well maybe not right now but in general I think a good step would be to basically write a couple of short stories in this environment. So what could be the story that's being told here? What could be the overall, because you're hinting at some of these, oh there's something that we didn't expect here, and I kind of now, we have talked about this earlier but from this game that I just played now I don't really know why there are robots, why do I care about these, why am I on this mission. So having this back story or not having this back story does a lot for games usually. I need to watch, oh I do need to get to a bus in a couple of minutes, would this be alright with you? Because I'm feeling already in the last part of the stage, right?

Interviewer: So I'm just going to ask one last question.

Participant: Yes, please. Absolutely.

Interviewer: I kind of like, as I discussed with you before, that this has to be a setup that feels dystopic, and the environment itself, some of the features of the dystopian cities, really tall buildings, and then there were kind of like robots that have gone rogue.

Interviewer: Yeah.

Participant: This kind of muted color atmosphere.

Interviewer: Yeah.

Participant: So did you kind of like feel it was empty and desolated, like a dystopian city, with the minimal block-outs? Did you like at least get the feeling?

Participant: That is an abstraction that I'm not very good at, to be quite honest. So I can, if I'm in this environment, it feels like a gym hall with these blue mats and stuff like that. This was kind of an association I had, so I do feel like I'm in some kind of a training program right now. So this might prepare me for something later on. So this block-out aesthetic kind of invoked this kind of feeling in me. The blocks themselves could totally be like a skyscraper part where I'm going from

one to the other. For that I would say the distances between them would need to be even larger because in a regular big city like skyscraper to the next one is like 50 meters, not 5 or 10 meters or something. So looking at something like Frankfurt, if maybe the only German city with a skyline, or if you go to something like New York where you get like really back-to-back huge buildings next to each other, I do think there would at least have to be a street between these. So maybe at least two lanes for cars, or like a pavement and one lane for a car, that's at least 5 or 10 meters, I would, yeah, at least 5.

So this is something that might be spaced out a little bit more, but overall the blockiness and the different heights, this worked very well for me. I would say this can be made with a little bit of, yeah, with replacement of assets basically. So I don't need to change the layout in any way, but the blocks that I'm standing on, they of course need to be more like concrete and glass and steel and whatever. Yeah, also stuff like, there's just shit on the roofs everywhere, so there's like these heat pump, motor, rotary, what's that called, I have no idea.

Interviewer: Like the essence of the roof so that it makes it feel lived on.

Participant: Yeah, to some degree, but it also depends on if this is like a contemporary city and this is happening now or in the near future, or if it's like far future stuff where we don't have this at all and it's all clean and like Star Trek future where there's no machinery visible anywhere basically, and that's up to your world building basically. I think in this place, in this, these aspects basically inform a player how utopian your world is or how well developed the society is and stuff like that, and you also get, plainly you get to choose what works for you the best, so for example if you need a lot of detail to have people be engaged in your world or to have a lot of places that people would need to look around corners or basically stuff to take cover behind or whatever, then you basically want a lot of these and if you don't want to have that or if you want a lot of wide open areas, that's also possible. It just needs to fit the world at your end.

Interviewer: Okay, thank you so much for your time and patience.

Participant: It was pretty amazing, I would say. Honestly, I really enjoyed that.

Interviewer: Thank you.

Participant: Very cool.

Interview – 06

Play Pattern

1. PCVR

2. PC

Interviewer: First of all, thank you so much for playing the game. Now I will conduct the interview, and my research study topic is comparative analysis between sensory engagement, comfort, and control in virtual reality and non-virtual reality games. I'm kind of focusing on five points in general for the discussion purpose, which is the overall control schemes between the two versions, the overall sensory engagement—and by sensory engagement in generic term I mean immersion and presence in the game—and the comfort section and the overall comparative analysis between the two versions. So let's start.

Interviewer: Let's get some background about you and tell me about what types of game do you generally play and how often do you play?

Participant: I generally play like action games, like mostly shooting, first-person shooter, or rogue-like games—these kind of games mostly.

Interviewer: How often do you generally play?

Participant: I generally play regularly. I recently play Marvel Rivals regularly kind of and, mostly I play Valorant, that's it.

Interviewer: Have you used VR before, and if you have used, what kind of medium have you experienced in VR? It can be anything like games, movies, or 360 videos or anything like that.

Participant: I did use VR before, not on a regular basis, but I have used it to play video games. But I'm not fluent in that—I'm not regular there.

Interviewer: Just think about the immersion in general now and disregard everything. So regarding this, which version do you prefer—the VR or the PC—which made you feel more present in the environment?

Participant: I enjoyed both of the games, for PC and VR, but I felt more present in the VR actually because I felt like the environment was created specifically for VR. Like, the environment when I look around and interactive objects like the ladder and other things, like interacting with the enemies also, it felt like it was made for VR and I enjoyed that.

Interviewer: As you have already seen, this game has varying heights of buildings all over the map. There was this kind of design decision that it has to be very dystopic, and this building structure also kind of speaks that language to the game. It kind of gives you a social hierarchy—the first section, the buildings are pretty low, and then it gets a bit higher, and then on section three it gets a bit higher, and so on and on. So, It gets very high on the fifth section, which kind of gives you this social phenomenon that it's transitioning from the poor to the rich genres of society, which is kind of like a very distinct feature of dystopic environments in general. So how did you perceive the height in general in both versions, as it is very crucial to the design itself?

Participant: Well, this was a great question actually. I didn't feel it when I was playing that way, but when you were describing the question, I felt like this was actually a great idea of that height comparison. **To be honest, when I was playing in PC, that height didn't matter actually, to be honest. But for the VR version, I felt it—really felt it, like when I'm going up and looking down from the high height, and the environment was really great, and I felt that height comparison in the VR actually.**

Interviewer: Let's talk about the interactions now.

Participant: Yes.

Interviewer: How do you compare the ladder in both versions? How was it physically climbing the ladder rather than just pressing buttons in the PC version?

Participant: **The PC version was usual—as I am just interacting with it and going up, nothing fancy. But for the VR version, I was a bit confused why I am holding the side bars and going up instead of holding the steps and going up. So it was new to me, to be honest.**

Interviewer: What about the rope, the middle-section?

Participant: The rope and zipline version was good actually. I enjoyed it in VR because when I was going from one point to another, I was looking around and seeing, and it felt good.

Interviewer: You also like, did a very distinct interaction of pressing the buttons, or pushing the buttons I should say, in the VR version, and then there was this button press and the interaction happened. How would you compare them?

Participant: **It was really good because, for example, for the lift I had to pull the lever and then interact with the lift. I felt it was really good, and also for the button when I am pressing it and it works. Compared to the PC version, it felt good to me.**

Interviewer: Overall, regarding the interactions, which one did you think felt more satisfying to do?

Participant: In the VR, I guess. It's more satisfying. For PC, it's normal interaction things, but for VR it's always new—it's always something new.

Interviewer: In the VR version you were physically interacting with the objects and stuff like that. Did you feel like it made a difference that you were performing the actions yourself rather than controlling a character in the PC version?

Participant: I actually did in the VR version. I actually felt it, to be honest. For example, in the last section when I had to disarm the robots—that was an intense moment when there were three or four robots going around and I had to sit and go slowly to interact with them, to hide from them and to interact with them. That was quite a fascinating moment in that game which I didn't feel in the PC. Also, using the zipline and the ladder was good. Though, in the lift, I felt a bit—it was a bit jittery, like it was shaking, so I didn't feel like using the lift much. But the ladder was good and also the rope. Yeah, that's it.

Interviewer: Now I want to ask about your experience as you were doing all these tasks in VR—climbing the ladder, trying to grab the rope and climb yourself forward and stuffs like that. This requires a lot of physical effort in general. Did you feel like when you are doing this stuff, was it stressing? Was the feeling positive, was it negative, or was it neutral?

Participant: It was like I am really interacting. It was not in a negative way but in a positive way—like I am actually interacting. For example, using the rope when I was interacting with it and going forward, it felt good, like I am interacting in the real world.

Interviewer: Let's talk about the controls. Which version, VR or PC, gave you more control over the movements and the actions?

Participant: For the movement, it is easier for me to control in PC, of course, as I play mostly in PC. But in VR, I didn't feel like I am being stuck or I can't control the player at all—I didn't feel like that. But in some cases in VR, I couldn't find out which way to go. Because, after re-spawning mostly, I couldn't find which way to go, so that was a bit—I had to find out where to go. But in PC I didn't feel like that. Overall it was good.

Interviewer: Were there any interactions in both versions that felt awkward to you?

Participant: Not same for both versions, but I'll say for the lift in VR, it was a bit awkward because it was shaking continuously from starting to end, and I didn't feel like using it. So I used mostly the ladder. In PC it was generally good.

Interviewer: What about vice versa—were there any interactions that felt really smooth, that you really loved it?

Participant: Yeah, using the rope, the zipline, and the ladder—it was flawless. I didn't feel any problem at all. It was really good. I was holding the ladder and climbing up, and using the zipline I was looking around, and it didn't feel any shaky or jittery or anything. It was smooth.

Interviewer: Can you compare the experience of sneaking behind the robots and disabling them?

Participant: Oh, this was a good one actually. As I described earlier, in the last phase there were four robots I guess, and I had to sneak behind them to disable them. It felt like I failed two to three times, and then I had to use the sit button—I had to sit and look around using the sonar to find out where the enemy is going, and then I had to sneak behind them and disable them. It was quite fun actually.

Interviewer: Do you think that VR made you more into the environment when you were trying to sneak and disable?

Participant: Yeah, the VR actually made me more interactive with the environment and the robots basically. It was really fun in VR because the PC version was like I'm just doing it, but in VR I was actually interacting with it—it felt like that.

Interviewer: Now this is kind of a hypothetical question. This game has a lot of crouching in general if you don't want to get detected, as you already mentioned that in the last section it is near impossible without crouching to end the game. In the first versions of the game, we had physical crouching implemented in the game where you literally had to crouch yourself and you had to play it while standing, not sitting, which is now a sitting experience also, and the height kind of adjusts according to your headset position. So it was like you have to stand and you have to physically crouch in this real space to make your character crouch in game. Do you think this would have made sense as this game involves a lot of crouching in general because it's a stealth game, or do you think it's better as it is?

Participant: As I played, it was good. But as you mentioned that I had to stand up for playing the game and I had to crouch for the crouch movement, it would have been better, I guess, because as I am sneaking around, as I am interacting with the ladder and the rope—as I said, I had to physically interact with my hand movement—it felt really good and interactive. So for the crouching, if I had to really sit down, I think it would be fun.

Interviewer: Regarding both the versions and the control schemes that you had, which version gave you more sense of freedom when you're approaching a situation? For example, there are three robots that you can see from far, and you're thinking, "Okay, maybe in PC this is really easy—I have the freedom of looking very quickly on all the 360 sides of my character and stuffs like that." Did you feel more freedom in the PC version or the PCVR version?

Participant: In this case, it's of course PC because it was really easy for me to interact in PC. In some cases in VR, when I am interacting with the bots and we are face to face, I can't go behind it and disable him. So if he is facing me, it's certain that I am dying and re-spawning. It was a bit challenging for me to do that. But in PC, the freedom was perfect.

Interviewer: You felt like much more at ease when you are approaching a situation?

Participant: Yes, yes, exactly.

Interviewer: Let's move to the comfort section of the conversation. Did you feel any motion sickness, dizziness, nausea, any eye strain, or any physical discomfort during the VR version?

Participant: From my previous experiences, I feel some motion sickness while moving. But in this case, I didn't feel that, to be honest. I actually didn't feel that. I moved smoothly and rotated around. Even I looked down from the height—I have height phobia—so when I look down, I should have felt something, but I didn't. So it was good. It was a good experience.

Interviewer: Which version would you credit to be more physically comfortable in general?

Participant: For the comfort one, I will say the PC. But for the interaction side, I will definitely say VR—it was really fun in VR interactions.

Interviewer: What do you think—how long can you play on both versions if you play non-stop?

Participant: I can play for an hour in PC, of course. But for VR, I guess half an hour or less, I guess.

Interviewer: Regarding the robot interaction in both the versions, did you feel more anxiety in the VR version in general than the PC version, or was it the same?

Participant: Of course I felt more interactive in the VR version. It was anxious when they are noticing me and I am getting caught, and I have to sneak behind them. So it was more fun and more anxious in the VR. But in PC it was normal—I am seeing them and I am disabling them. It was normal for me. But in VR it was really fun and interactive.

Interviewer: After removing the headset—because you played for nearly 25 minutes—were there any kind of issues, any unusual sensations, any disorienting feelings?

Participant: Not really. I removed the headset and walked around here fine. I didn't feel anything.

Interviewer: Now let's move to the core of the discussion, which is the comparative analysis between both the versions. Now, this is one of the very interesting and toughest questions that I have in the questionnaire. As you have played both versions now, just think for a moment that you can play only one—you have the option to play only one then which one will that be?

Participant: I'll definitely go with the VR version.

Interviewer: Why would you choose the VR?

Participant: Because it is interactive. I felt like interacting with everything there is, and it felt fun. It felt interactive, and the last part with the bots, it felt really good and really challenging, and I didn't feel that in PC. So I'll definitely choose the VR.

Interviewer: Can you name any particular thing that you felt the VR version did way better than the PC version?

Participant: I guess there are multiple—the ladder system, the zipline system, and the rope also. Except the lift, of course—it was not good for me, but interacting with the bots, sneaking behind the bots and interacting with them—this is the best part in VR.

Interviewer: So you will say that all the interactions in general were better in the VR?

Participant: Yeah, exactly.

Interviewer: What about vice versa? Did you feel anything that felt much better to do in the PC version rather than VR?

Participant: Moving around. Moving around and interacting with things was easy—not interactive but easy.

Interviewer: So the ease of use was much higher than the VR?

Participant: Yeah, exactly.

Interviewer: Now let's be more specific and talk about the interactions itself. For climbing ladders, which version would you prefer, the VR or the PC?

Participant: VR.

Interviewer: For the interactivity you mentioned already?

Participant: Yeah.

Interviewer: What about the zipline?

Participant: VR, of course.

Interviewer: So you felt the zipline in VR was more exciting?

Participant: Yeah, exactly.

Interviewer: Why do you think that is? Is it because in the PC version you cannot move your camera while you're in the zipline, and in the VR version you had this freedom to move your head?

Participant: Kind of like that, exactly. **Because when I was using the zipline, I was looking around, looking below, seeing the scenario overall, and it felt good.**

Interviewer: There's another very distinct feature in both versions regarding the zipline. The PC version had a camera shake to make it more believable when you were in a zipline, because the VR version didn't have it for obvious reasons like motion sickness. Do you think that would have been a good addition to the PCVR version too? Like you have some camera wobbling and effects like that?

Participant: I don't know how much it will affect the motion sickness or things, but I guess the shakiness might be a good addition.

Interviewer: What was your most memorable moment in the VR version?

Participant: The last part—interacting with the enemies and finally finishing the thing. It was the most memorable part.

Interviewer: **What was the most memorable moment in the PC version?**

Participant: **Overall it was good, but nothing specific.**

Interviewer: **Will you be willing to sacrifice the comfort—because you mentioned that for the ease of use you will choose the PC version any day—but for a moment, will you sacrifice the comfort and ease of use to play the VR version? For this game?**

Participant: **I definitely will.**

Interviewer: Do you think that this particular genre matters in both versions? This is like a VR stealth traversal game, to be very specific. Do you think this traversal thing makes a very big difference in both versions? Because it could have been an MMORPG, it could have been a hack-and-slash game, maybe in VR, maybe in PC, and it could have been also something that has a VR version and a PC version which exists in the market right now—maybe some shooter game. Do you think this particular mechanics of using the traversal mechanics in general, climbing and going forward with ropes and stuff, do you think this is more fun in VR. Because the genre matters in this particular case, or do you think it would have been fun anyway if you played it in VR in any of the genres?

Participant: Well, I think interacting in VR in any case is interesting. **For this particular genre, I had a lot of interaction parts—for example, the ladder, the rope, the zipline, and of course the buttons and other things. It matters. It actually matters because these things make VR feel good. These things make VR games feel more interesting.** So these things matter I guess.

Interviewer: What is the one thing that could make the VR experience much better than it already is?

Participant: To be honest, nothing in particular. I think the things there are is already good, and nothing else should be added.

Interviewer: Vice versa—what is the one thing that you think could make that difference in the PC version?

Participant: I guess post-processing and some extra additional camera shakes for things—interaction things, and some effects would be good.

Interviewer: Did you feel lost in the environment when you are traversing it or when you are traveling around? Did you feel like you couldn't find your way in any of the places?

Participant: Not mostly. It was specifically when I respawn—then I just couldn't find which way to specifically go because I was in motion and then I suddenly re-spawned and then I lost that track. So I had to find out which way to go in that particular time. But in general, when I was going around, not mostly. It was smooth.

Interviewer: After trying both versions, would you be interested in playing more VR games?

Participant: Yeah, I would be.

Interviewer: Why do you think this kind of sparks your curiosity about trying more VR games in general?

Participant: Mostly for the interaction parts. Interacting with things felt really good in VR.

Interviewer: Is there anything else that you want to add regarding the total development—any kind of suggestions, any kind of things that you really liked, or anything in particular?

Participant: I overall like the VR version, and I think when you develop it further, you can add some environment. When I was playing it, I felt like if it was a night environment, it will feel really good—like the Batman games. It would feel really good if it was a night environment. As it is already a stealth game, it will be really fun to play, so you can add that.

Interviewer: One last question before we wrap up this interview, regarding the game design. As this is a very rough blackout version of the game, there isn't any particular high-quality assets in it. I really wanted to nail it down to color codes to guide the player. When you see anything that's yellow, you try to grab it. When there's anything that has these rectangular boxes over boxes, you know that you need to interact with that—like the consoles in general, and then when you disable

the robots, they turn red. When you are disabling them with EMP, they turn yellow. Do you think that this was like—did you feel this made a difference, the color codes in general?

Participant: **It really felt like it made a difference. The instructions were really good and specific. They didn't vary over time and stayed constant.** It actually felt like, as you described, when I see things I know exactly what to do. So the instructions were really good.

Interviewer: Anything else you want to add?

Participant: Nothing else.

Interviewer: Okay, thank you so much for your time and patience.

Participant: Thank you.

Interview – 07

Play Pattern

1. PCVR

2. PC

Interviewer: First of all, thank you so much for playing the game. I'm going to give you some background over the whole thesis topic. So my research study is about comparative analysis on sensory engagement, control and comfort in virtual reality and non-virtual reality games.

So by sensory engagement, I am mostly targeting the fact that it's the immersion and presence that you felt between the two versions, and the control and comfort, it's just what it means that the control schemes between the keyboard mouse and in your case the motion controllers, and for the comfort, it's just how you perceived it in virtual reality and PC version.

Interviewer: So let's get some background about you first. So can you tell me like what type of games do you generally play and how often do you play?

Participant: I usually like to play story based game, and it doesn't necessarily have to be AAA games, you know, the good games like Last of Us. But sometimes I really like the indie games as well. Sometimes the games from each Itch.io, where developers put their games. I like to play those games as well.

However, I try to avoid playing the multiplayer games. I don't know why I think maybe I do have some kind of trauma with it in my past life. That's why I never play multiplayer games for now.

I also play games on VR as well. But in that case, it's most about, you know, the immersive experience and how the game is played as I'm a game developer, and I also want to be a VR game developer as well.

So, and I think I play once a week to three to four times a month. I'm a really casual player. I don't play that much, you know, if I talk about playing a specific game. However, if I talk about like I'm playing at a random game just for checking out. But in that case, I have to say three times a week.

Interviewer: Okay, cool, and do you have any experience with VR, and if you have, then what kind of media have you perceived in VR before this game? Like it can be anything. Could be a film. Could be a 360 experience. Could be an immersive experience. Or could be a game itself.

Participant: No, for me in VR, I think the first experience was the game, the best game at least I know. At least it is for me for VR, which is the Half-Life Alyx.

Interviewer: Okay.

Participant: That game I think is the most immersive experience ever for VR, and other than that, I did play some farm game, Farm Frenzy type games. I just don't remember the name.

I also had an experience in a hotel actually. I went to this hotel called Palace. There was a, they made a sort of a spaceship like that. Like in that, they just put a headset on and they just follow on that. They have an experience with the VR and they also, you know, just try to give it a motion, and that's all I have.

Interviewer: Okay. So now let's move to the next section of the discussion. So regarding the sensory engagement, I mentioned that presence is one of the things that I'm focusing on my thesis, and which version, VR or PC, which version made you feel more present in the game and why?

Participant: I think for me the presence was more, you know, I felt the presence significantly in VR. However, if I talk about, you know, the comfort or immersiveness or that aspect, I think it was better in Windows PC. However, the presence, you know, itself, I mean, this game, I'm inside this game, this feelings was better in VR.

Interviewer: So regarding the game design or the environment design itself, I think you kind of perceived it well that it has varying heights of buildings, and it's mostly based on rooftops of the buildings itself. So, of course, as you said that you kind of felt more present in the VR version itself, and the heights are kind of like, the building gets very high in the end sections of the game. So did you like, had any perception about the height itself during the VR gameplay or the PC gameplay? Like, how did you perceived it?

Participant: I think height wasn't actually that kind of an issue to talk about because I didn't really feel anything like significant here. Like, that's something I have to talk about. I think it was all quite normal.

I think the most thing which I felt problematic was the control, actually, with the game. In the VR version, of course, not the Windows version, which somehow made the whole experience a little bitter in VR, which wasn't really in Windows, and I'm not saying that it was the feelings of presence because it was better in VR, of course.

I think, like when I played other games in VR, where I personally had the control to go, you know, move left or right, and it wasn't really present there, and I was always going forward and backward and moving with this, and it wasn't really, I mean, I wanted the right and left movement. I think if I had left and right movement, I would have chosen VR over Windows game for this project.

Interviewer: Okay, cool. So there are like many distinct mechanics between the two versions, which are like the ladder or you can say the levers, the lifts, how you disable the enemy and how you go on the zipline and the rope also and stuffs like that. So let's come one by one. How did you kind of like compare your experience with the ladders between the two versions? How was it like physically trying to climb the ladder versus pressing the button in the PC version?

Participant: I think if I talk about immersiveness, in this case, I have to say, you know, the Windows game, you know, the PC gave me the better version when I'm like pulling the ladders. With VR, it was, I think I felt like I'm, it was sort of pulling the ladder. However, I didn't feel that good in VR, you know, when I'm pulling the ladder.

But the experience with a PC was really good because, you know, you just went there, you press the button and while like pressing on the button, you just got, the experience was really smooth. The thing, yeah, I think that word is smoothness. I think the smoothness was better in Windows. However, it's not, wasn't really that good in VR.

But the lift experience, if I talk about it, it was, I mean, quite the same for PC or VR or even, you know, the pulling the switch to unlock the lift. So, that was quite the same, just the difference I found was in the ladder, like going up, upwards.

Interviewer: Okay, so, as you mentioned the rope mechanics, did you like, felt more into the game in the VR version in the rope or was it kind of like the same in the PC version?

Participant: No, no, no, no. Sorry, I forgot to talk about that, but it was the experience was more lively in VR version. When, when I'm like using the rope to go from one place to another.

Interviewer: Okay, cool. So, there's also another distinct feature that you need to physically press the buttons in the VR version, rather than pressing a button to press the button in the PC version. So, which one did you enjoy the most?

Participant: I think it should be the VR version, the VR version.

Interviewer: Can you, can you say like why, why did you felt more, why did the VR version felt more enjoyable to you?

Participant: I think there is a reason, because you know, when I'm, when I use in VR version, there was a little bit of motion there, which made me feel like I'm really, you know, and there was also a sound, that there is something happening. So, if I combine with these two values together, I feel like, yeah, I'm really swinging through it.

However, if someone is not really used to with VR, and he doesn't, I think there's an issue. I mean, if you just press a button here, then you could just swing from one place to another backwards, or

the position you're looking at. So, you have to be really subtle about it, like where you're looking at it, and if you have that, I think it's better than windows.

Exactly that, that experience, and I was going, I think from, at first, I made a mistake when I tried it from the first time, because I really didn't understand it quite. So, at that time, I sort of swung backward. But after that, I always used the rope technique, you know, the properly, in the forward, forward way, and it was really good, the experience was good. But the first one wasn't, that's the thing.

Interviewer: Okay, so, it's kind of like, you're describing, if I'm not wrong, your experience about the zipline, right?

Participant: Yeah, zipline.

Interviewer: Now regarding the buttons that you press, like in the console, or in the lifts itself, right? After you turn on the lever, and you press the button, to go down or go up on the lift, you also kind of like, go to the console, and press the button to complete the objectives, right?

Participant: Yeah.

Interviewer: So, did it like, felt different in either versions, or was it the same?

Participant: It was the same.

Interviewer: Okay, cool. So, overall, which was more satisfying, and why do you think, which was more satisfying?

Participant: Okay, I have to talk, I think I have to talk about two or three things here, but let me tell you the result first. The thing is, the Windows version was better.

Interviewer: Okay.

Participant: Then it, and I think the reason behind this is that I'm really much more comfortable with Windows version as I'm playing it. I think I was in, I think my age was four, three or four when I first started to play computer games. So, I think there's a comfort, of course.

However, I think when, oh, you are playing this kind of games, like where you have some objective, and you have to just complete it. There, all of the movements, or the experience you're having, like the functionalities really impact a lot on you.

So, in Windows, this whole experience was really smooth. From, you know, pulling the ladder, to sipping or interacting, the overall experience was really smooth, I think.

For VR, however, it wasn't really smooth, like when you are trying to pull the ladder, you will see that the mouse was sort of going this and this, which is, I mean, overall the smoothness wasn't really good there, and also, when you are trying to move, you can't really move left or right, which sort of giving you a sense that you can do this or that.

Like, in games, we try to be free. That's the thing, and with VR, with these kind of things, I was feeling a little bit congested there, like I can do this and that. So, I was trying to switch the movement to, you know, just, you know that movement where you don't need to move, but you just point out to the place and it will teleport you there. I was trying there, but it wasn't that good, you know, when I was teleporting. I didn't like, I don't like it, actually.

So, I usually try to move with that, and so, when the movement wasn't really smooth for me from the first and I felt, you know, a sort of negative sense at the first in the VR version, and also, I have to say that sometimes, you know, there was a little bit of lag happening in VR, which also had an impact that, which made me choose Windows over VR.

I think overall, it's all of the hardware requirements and some functionalities. I mean, the smoothness in general with both of them.

Interviewer: Okay. So, now regarding the immersion category, I have a question for you that in the PC version or in the PC VR version, you're kind of like, did you felt like you were controlling the character yourself? Like, you are the character in the VR version? Or was it the same? Like, it was, the experience was kind of like, subpar to both of the versions? Or did you feel like more immersed that you were the character itself? You're not controlling a character. Do you get my point?

Participant: Yeah. I think for me, for me is that I feel like I am the character more on Windows version. Not on the VR version.

In the VR version, it's like, I was in that game and I was trying to find out everything, but in a way, yeah, I was feeling like I'm sort of stuck there, in a way. But yeah, the experience was, if I think that if I'm in that person or not, yes, I felt it more in VR, however, I felt stuck out there. So, you know, the experience was much better in Windows.

Interviewer: Okay. So, you kind of like also felt that controlling the character was much more immersive than having this kind of like feeling in the overall, as you already said, but this smoothness made you felt much, much less delighted to play the VR version, right?

Participant: Yeah. Okay.

Interviewer: So, now let's move to the control schemes between the both versions. So, which one kind of like gave you better control over the movements in general?

Participant: Yeah. Yeah. The PC version Windows.

Interviewer: Okay. So, can you like elaborate a bit? Like exactly why?

Participant: Okay. Yeah. Of course. The reason was that, first of all, I told you that I'm really comfortable with Windows. Of course, that's the sole reason, I think.

But, however, there are some add-ons there. When I'm playing in the Windows, there was a lot less bug. First of all, I have to mention this one, and when I'm playing in the PC, everything was smooth and the movement was really, you know, comfortable for me. Like I'm really playing it. There was everything is going the way I want to. Like I don't feel stuck out there.

I don't think it was a reason that I don't know anything about the game prior to that. In VR, not only the controls, I think when I'm trying to like go from one place to another and there was a severe lag happening that made me, you know, think that the VR version is trash after all.

After all, I think if that experience, I think the lag wasn't there, I think I could have compared really properly with the both games, and for me now, I think the VR game, which the VR version really lacks the, you know, mainly the smoothness. I mean, the interaction I didn't really liked that much in the VR version. That's all.

Interviewer: Can you like elaborate a bit what kind of lag you face? Are you like mentioning the rotation mechanics in general?

Participant: No, not only rotation, the game itself, all the controls. Like you can't really move forward or backward or move left or right. For five seconds, plus forward and backward for two to three seconds, and next you're again on, and in between that time, I was getting caught by the AI.

So which made me frustrated a little bit. I think it was more of an experience, and how the game was, you know, objective based, I thought the VR experience would have been so much better for me than Windows, and from the very first five to ten seconds, I felt like that, like the VR is going to be better than Windows. However, the overall experience made my decision change.

Interviewer: Okay. So were there any interactions that felt awkward in either versions?

Participant: I think I have to say it isn't really awkward, but a little bit like different. Like I never actually played this kind of game before. That was, you know, going to the rope with Windows in PC version. Like it felt like I just went there and I pressed E and I tried, I started swinging.

So yeah, in Windows version that, but that exact experience was far better in VR. The whole, you know, swinging in with the rope there was really good.

Interviewer: Like the zipline.

Participant: The zipline is better, and that experience is far more superior than Windows experience. I have to say that.

Interviewer: Okay. So can you compare your experience disabling the robots in either versions?

Participant: Yeah, I think it's, I think if I have to compare this, this is the VR version, this is the Windows version for this, this functionality. I think it has to be VR.

Interviewer: Like you felt the VR version is much, much superior in the sneaking mechanics itself of disabling the robots and sticking your way up. Right?

Participant: Yeah.

Interviewer: Cool. So this is kind of like a hypothesis question for now, as there is a lot of crouching in this game, because you need to kind of like get past the robots, and if you sneak, if you crouch, you generate less sound. So it's harder for the AI to catch you. Okay.

Though the AI is intentionally made dumber in the VR version so that it's easier to complete the game. Because as you already mentioned that it's in general hard to move in VR version rather than PC version. Okay.

So there is, there was a lot of crouching involved in this game and right now you kind of like controlled your crouch with a button. Right? In both the versions. But before this, the first iteration of the VR version was physical crouching. So you need to crouch in real space to crouch in game. Okay.

So do you think this was a good idea to drop the idea of physical crouching and put the button based this crouching, or do you think the physical crouching would have made more sense?

Participant: Yeah. I mean, it would, I don't think it would made any sense if I think about in a game perspective. Like the main aspect of a game is to, you know, make the players comfortable with it. Like if you have to crouch there, like in your real life to complete a task, I didn't, I don't think anyone would like that in a game.

I mean, when you're playing a game, you have to be really comfortable. Like you, and I think it's better that you chose this version, you know, the button press.

Participant: Okay.

Interviewer: That's for sure.

Interviewer: So, in the end, which version, VR or PC, which was easier to learn and why?

Participant: Yeah, I think it should be the Windows version was easier to learn because everything was, because I'm really more comfortable with Windows than VR, and as I've said, I think multiple times during our interview that, you know, the whole experience or the, this interview would have been different if I could have, you know, left and right movement in VR, and also, you know, there wasn't any, lag maybe for me, the VR experience would have been far more superior than the Windows.

Interviewer: So, now let's move to the comfort section. Did you experience any motion sickness, nausea or any kind of dizziness, eye strain during the VR gameplay?

Participant: No.

Interviewer: Was everything good?

Participant: Everything was good.

Interviewer: Okay. So, you didn't feel any kind of, you didn't feel like the speed of the movement or the speed of the zipline was making you motion sick?

Participant: No.

Interviewer: Cool, and do you think it's fine as it is or should it, should it be a bit faster, the movements in general?

Participant: The movement is quite good, but I think it would be sort of a suggestion if you're making a game out of it. Uh, I think you should, you could use the interaction or, you know, moving by, you know, you can use a black screen to, you know, just make the smoothness a little bit better. You know, the experiment, you know, make the game a bit more cinematic, which we can make the, you know, VR experience really good.

Like, uh, when you're swinging, uh, yourself there, uh, the character sort of, like, uh, bumped from one piece to another and started swinging. So, you know, try to give it a, some kind of animation or something like that.

Interviewer: So, in the end, which version do you think was physically more comfortable?

Participant: Physically?

Interviewer: Yes. Because you have a lot of physical actions in the VR version itself, right? Because you have to climb the ladder.

Participant: Yeah, I think it's the VR one. It's the VR one. I felt more alive there.

Interviewer: But, regarding the comfort, which version would you choose?

Participant: Comfort, yeah, Windows.

Interviewer: Windows.

Participant: Okay.

Interviewer: Regarding the VR headset, did you feel like the headset was fine or do you think it, you have, like, weight based issues that it was slipping or it was very heavy on your head or anything? Any comment on that?

Participant: No, I don't. It was really good for me.

Interviewer: Okay. So, you didn't feel any kind of disorientation regarding that?

Participant: No.

Interviewer: Okay, cool.

Interviewer: So, now let's talk about the overall comparative analysis between the two versions, okay? So, now, as you have played both of the versions, now think of, think like this for a moment, that you have the chance to play only one version. So, which one would you choose, VR or PCVR, and why?

Participant: Yeah, I have to say, it should be the Windows version, and I will play it just because, you know, the whole experience was really good. From first to last, I didn't feel stuck anywhere, it's not because of a bug or something like that. It's like, you have to say that, the whole experience was smooth, of course, and also, I was playing it really comfortably. Like, this is happening, and that happening, and I'm getting really hang of it, and I think that's the main thing here.

Interviewer: Okay, so, can you name one mechanics or one certain thing that you think the PC version did better than the VR? It can be multiple things, you can mention multiple things also, it's fine.

Participant: I, so, I didn't, I think, it was, it's really hard to say, I mean, there wasn't really significant difference in both things. Like, if I'm thinking about any functionality, it could be, and every, if I talk about, you know, specific functionality, every functionality is better in VR, you know, the experience.

But the overall experience is way much better in Windows, just because, you know, I think the design, game design.

Interviewer: It's how you play the game in general?

Participant: It's how I play the game in general, and the game design for VR wasn't really good. Just, as I've said, I'm saying multiple times about the, uh, the movements, and that, really, you know, made VR in a very lower place, so. But all the functionality was better in VR. All, all of them.

Interviewer: But, uh, you kind of, like, felt more freedom to approach a situation in the Windows version?

Participant: Yeah.

Interviewer: Okay. So, do you think then the PC version did the overall comfort factor better than the VR version, right?

Participant: Yes, I have to say that.

Interviewer: Okay. So now, okay, can you just say some things about what the VR version did better than the PC version?

Participant: Okay. Uh, in the VR version, the, as I've said, you know, swinging the rope was better. Uh, and, you know, pressing the button, it's like, you don't have to do anything. You, you have a hand here, and just press the button, and the button is pressed, and also pulling the lever. You just go to there, and you feel like really pull, uh, you know, uh, holding the...

Interviewer: It felt natural?

Participant: Yeah. It was natural, and, I think it's all of the functionalities there. Like, disabling the AI or everything. That was much more alive in the VR version.

Interviewer: Okay.

Participant: Uh, however, I have to say another thing, which I forgot to mention when we're having this interview. As I was really focused on a single thing while I was playing the VR, I wasn't really looking at all of the environments out there. So, maybe that could be a part of reason why I didn't feel any motion sickness or anything like that. I was focused on one single thing.

So, there could be issues like which could have an effect on me. Uh-huh. But, I didn't feel it just because I was really focused there. So, I have to say that if I talk about this kind of game, your game design, at least was good that the VR player was focused in one single thing. Like, he didn't feel motion sickness even though he was moving or using swinging or anything like that. Like, everyone, I was really looking at that one place.

Interviewer: Yeah. So, you had like a good visual anchor, you would say.

Participant: Yeah.

Interviewer: So, now let's talk about some specific mechanics between the two versions. So, regarding the ladder itself, which version would you choose?

Participant: Windows.

Interviewer: Can you like say why?

Participant: The reason that was, uh, you know, I feel more comfortable in Windows version, you know, the experience was really good. Mm-hmm, and in VR version, I was really feeling, you know, I'm pulling the ladder. Mm-hmm. The experience was more lively than that. However, you know, the experience wasn't really good. You know, I didn't feel really good while doing it in the VR.

Interviewer: Okay. So, you kind of like felt the physical effort was not good itself, right?

Participant: Yeah.

Interviewer: Okay. Cool. So, now regarding the zipline, which version do you prefer?

Participant: VR.

Interviewer: Okay.

Participant: No question asked.

Interviewer: Can you like, say why?

Interviewer: Okay. I have to say this, sorry. I am in an interview, I forgot that. It was mainly because I was trying to, uh, you know, use a zipline properly, you know, in the forward direction, and there was a little bit of movement and a bit of motion, which made me feel more alive to this, uh, specific functionality. Mm-hmm. So, I have to go with VR.

Interviewer: Okay. So, regarding the rope mechanics?

Participant: Uh, rope. Yeah. The rope, you meant the slinging the rope mechanics, right?

Interviewer: Yeah. Kind of like, you are trying to climb yourself forward to the rope, you know?

Participant: Uh, yeah. I think that that also should be VR. You know, it felt more alive there.

Interviewer: Okay, and regarding the buttons and the lever?

Participant: It was quite the same for me in both.

Interviewer: Okay, cool.

Interviewer: So, can you like, say, uh, which was kind of like, your most memorable moment in the VR version? What would you say?

Participant: Uh, you know, slinging that rope or, you know, the zipline. Yeah. That's the most thing. Because, you know, the motion really made me feel connected to the game.

Interviewer: Okay. So, what was your most memorable moment in the PC version?

Participant: Uh, I think, there is no, you know, the PC version hadn't anything which is, you know, I remember properly, like, there was severe difference than the VR. However, the overall experience was really smooth. That's why I really like the PC version, you know, I can move anywhere I want. I felt a little more freedom there.

Interviewer: So, now let's kind of like, ask you a superficial question, okay?

Participant: Of course.

Interviewer: Would you kind of like, sacrifice the comfort and the control? Like, if, just imagine for a second that you can move left and right on the VR. You can also rotate smoothly rather than having that snap rotation that we implemented, and there is no comfort issue in the VR itself, okay? So, would you like, sacrifice the mentioned things to try the VR version rather than the PC?

Participant: I would, I would try it on VR. However, you have to say that I can move left and right there as well. If that's there, I mean, you don't have to, you know, move the character smoothly, which is really problematic, but the movement is quite good. There is lag, but if I don't have a lag and I can move left and right, I think I have to go with the VR version.

Interviewer: Okay, and vice versa, would you be willing to sacrifice VR's immersion to play the PC version?

Participant: If, you know, as you said, the scenario is that, a bit of hypothetical in that case. No, I wouldn't really sacrifice VR for Windows if that was right.

Interviewer: Okay. So, what is kind of like the one thing that made the VR experience better than the PC version itself? Like the overall interactions?

Participant: Yes, I have to say overall interaction for this specific game, of course.

Interviewer: Yeah. So, this kind of like gives a good follow-up. Do you think that genre matters in this kind of games?

Participant: I have to say yes. Genre matters, I think. Because when I'm actually going to, going on, you know, the racing games or FPS shooting games or something like that, in that case, I think I would be really comfortable in Windows games than VR.

Interviewer: Okay. So, what do you think is the one thing that could make the PC experience better? Like what improvements can I bring in the PC version that could make it better? Can you like place some possible suggestions?

Participant: For PC, actually not the VR version, I think, a really good environment. You know, the environment is a little bit, you know, I think it's really good for research purpose or thing. But when you're playing a game on a PC, you, of course, really want something in the background. Not the background, you know, like a really good environment where you can see some other things. I mean, overall, if you're playing a PC, in that case, it's a really boring game. It's really boring. So, you would need a little bit of details there.

Interviewer: So, you're talking about more prop kind of details.

Participant: Yes, prop.

Interviewer: Like making the environment feel more lived in, right?

Participant: Yeah, and you're interacting with it, like the button or there is some kind of...

Interviewer: Animations?

Participant: Animations and also some kind of... I think it's a sort of short game type of thing. It could be a puzzle or something like that to, you know, add when they're going to an objective. You know, they're pushing a button. So, you could add a puzzle there maybe to, you know, to unlock the... If they can play the button, not only using the pull up that thing. That's the thing. I think it needs a little more entertainment there in PC version because they don't have that feelings of presence.

Interviewer: Okay. So, as you already mentioned that you would love to have sideways movement in VR version like left and right. Do you think this is the only thing that you need in the VR version to make it feel better or do you have any more suggestions that could make it possibly better than the PC version?

Participant: That's... That's one thing. I think I do have another suggestion, which is that, for me, it was... I was sure about that. **That's why I use the zipline swing properly. But there's chance that sometimes people will not understand. So, like try to make a system where you just push that button. You always start from the forward direction,** you know, the movement. There's an animation there, of course. The animation like started and then the camera is in the forward direction, always. **So that the experience is proper.** You know, the player can have the proper experience there.

Interviewer: Okay, so...

Participant: and it actually applies to all of the functionalities. Even when climbing the ladder, sometimes my body was touching the ladder, and I wasn't really trying to do that, you know.

Interviewer: Like you are kind of colliding yourself with the ladder?

Participant: Yes. **I think if there was an animation there, and the experience was sort of similar to windows. That it's happening very smoothly up and down in the VR, then the VR implementation would be better than the Windows version.**

Interviewer: Are you kind of implicating that the VR version should also have this thumbstick movement rather than the physical movements you do in the ladder?

Participant: Yes, I am implicating that.

Interviewer: Okay, so after trying both versions, would be interested in trying more VR games in general?

Participant: Yes. I like to play different games, and for VR we can see that most of the games are story-based. As I am really into that kind of games, so I would choose VR games any day.

Interviewer: Okay. So lastly, is there anything else that you want to add? Any suggestions, any remarks regarding the development, or anything at all?

Participant: No. I think I sort of said everything when I was talking to you. I sort of said multiple times some things, so no.

Interviewer: Ok. So thank you so much for your time and patience.

Interview – 08

Play Pattern

1. PC

2. PCVR

Interviewer: OK, so first of all thank you so much for enjoying the, for joining the test and kind of like contributing to the thesis. So I'm going to give you some background about it first. So my topic is comparative analysis on sensory engagement, comfort and control between virtual reality and non-virtual reality games. So by sensory engagement I'm kind of like I'm targeting the meaning of immersion and presence in both the versions. On controls, I kind of like imposing the control schemes, the motion controllers and the controller itself which you used to play the game, and by comfort, I'm meaning any kind of issues that you may have faced regarding two versions, any motion sickness, nausea or vertigo or any kind of problems at all. OK, so let's get some background about you first.

Participant: OK.

Interviewer: So can you like tell me what types of games to generally play and how often do you play?

Participant: Okay, so um usually I play lots of video games. So I over the years I believe I've played almost every genre of video games. But right now if I have to focus on a certain type of game then I would say currently I'm playing like action-adventure oriented third person or first person video games, a little bit of RPG and hand-to-hand combat or FPS, TPS like all kind of games. But currently I'm playing the Assassin's Creed series. So mostly yeah third person single player games, okay.

Interviewer: How often do you actually play?

Participant: Um, usually I play on daily basis unless I have something super important to do at night. But yeah, usually I play on a daily basis.

Interviewer: So have you like used VR before, like it can be any kind of medium like it can be games, it can be 360 movies, it can be immersive experiences like anything at all?

Participant: Well my hands-on experience with VR was very limited, maybe I played a cricket game in VR which in which basically I had to just hold the controller and just you know use it like a bat to swing to hit the ball. It was very basic actually. There were like a little bit of camera movements and like very limited functionalities. So my exposure to VR, I would say it was very limited, so yeah.

Interviewer: So now let's uh talk about the sensory engagement section in general. So regarding the presence in the game, which version do you prefer, the VR or the PC version? Which version made you feel more present in the game and why?

Participant: Um, if it's in terms of presence, uh I think the VR version was more appropriate to me. Um, I think um the first question was which version do I prefer and I think there are certain circumstances or certain points in which I think uh both of the VR and non-VR version have their advantages and disadvantages. So in terms of presence I think I prefer the VR version because in that version I feel more immersed and sort of like more present there.

Interviewer: So as you have already seen in the environment design that there is a lot of varying heights in the game.

Participant: Yes.

Interviewer: In like they're literally the same level in both the versions and there is a varying heights of buildings and you kind of like play over the rooftops of the buildings in general, that's the idea, and there was this dystopic idea behind the design that I was kind of like focusing on when I was designing the environment itself. So one of the very distinct features of a dystopian environment is hierarchical buildings, okay? So it kind of like gives you this societal hierarchy that in the very first sections the buildings are low which means low society, it gets higher and higher and the last portion is like elite. So there's this, there's this social discrimination between the overall phase of the environment, okay? That was kind of like the idea when we were designing it.

So the height in general was a very important feature of the game itself. So how did you kind of like perceive the heights in both the versions?

Participant: Um, all right, so um basically for me it was like um, um yeah the world was definitely in a dystopian setup. But for me it was more like the higher i rose in, in certain areas it became more difficult for the player in general. So for me it was like, um basically an ascension of difficulty. Um, but yeah if you look in further detail, in the lower areas there were not uh, basically very linear design or like the objects around them were not very complicated at all. But the higher we rose there were like more robots or more positions to take cover from etc. So yeah, for me definitely felt a change when i rose to a higher position and so yeah for me it was like the difficulty was getting a little bit more difficult or something like that.

Interviewer: Okay, and regarding the, as you already said you felt more present in the game in the VR version.

Participant: Yeah.

Interviewer: So did you like perceive the height of the buildings a bit differently or was it the same in both the versions?

Participant: Um, yes definitely the perception was a bit different. Um, I felt like um when i was playing in the non-VR version for me it was um mostly all the areas felt a little bit of similar to me. But when i played on the VR version, I sort of felt the differences a little bit more in general. Like I used to pinpoint certain areas like okay this is a little bit different than the other. But in the non-VR version more or less the areas felt a little bit of similar to me.

Interviewer: Okay. So now let's talk about the mechanics a bit. So the mechanics are all kind of like the same in the idea of the design itself. So there's like ladders, there's ziplines, there's rope, the lift and levers and you can disable the enemy, you can press buttons and stuff. But there are some distinct differences between the two versions on how you interact with that media.

Participant: Yeah.

Interviewer: So let's first talk about the ladder, okay, ladder itself. So what is it like physically climbing the ladder rather than pressing buttons in the PC version?

Participant: So, uh, like i said earlier my experience with VR is very limited, was very limited before playing this game. So uh for me when i first when i played the non-VR version it was like um like muscle memory for me. I've played a lot of video games in which you climb a ladder, so you just press a button and you interact with it and then you climb up. So climbing a ladder after playing this game in the VR version, before playing this game I did not have thought that climbing a ladder would be this much you know, uh, impactful or you have to put a lot of effort in this. So this was a new experience for me definitely, and um yeah definitely it was fun, it was fun, and also like when i had to put an effort on this particular action it felt a lot more meaningful for me. So yeah definitely it was a good experience. I had to learn first, I was failing a lot, but when i finally did it that was a very good feeling of accomplishment, yeah.

Interviewer: Okay. So regarding the ladder were you confused when you first approached it, like do you have to grab the poles or do you have to grab the rungs which are in the middle?

Participant: Yes, I was definitely a little bit confused because, um, I believe there were no like text based or clear instructions when i was climbing the ladder, and as someone who haven't played many VR games for me that was new. So yeah it was a little confusing for me at the first, at the beginning.

Interviewer: So now let's talk about the levers, okay, and the lifts. So you're kind of like pulling the lever physically like you do in real life, and you're also like pressing the buttons like in real life, like you're literally smashing the buttons in the VR version rather than pressing a button to press the button in the game, right?

Participant: Yes, Yes.

Interviewer: So how would you like kind of like differentiate between your experience with the lever and the buttons itself?

Participant: Yeah, so um, um again I would say like in the non-VR version it was like, uh, effortless. Like, uh, I knew what i have to do before even going there. Like I saw a lever, I know if I just press the interact button the lever's gonna go upwards and I'm gonna go to the lift and I'm gonna press a button again, but in the VR version there were a lot of this interactable moment in which you have to do certain actions. In each of these um individual moments you have to do different sort of action. Like for the lever you have to pull it up, for the button you have to press it down. So you're sort of using your gesture, you're using your hands, you're using that to do it.

So, um, in terms of experience these are, I think they are, these are, um, little experiences but i think these are very fun experiences. So like in terms of a puzzle based game or sort of like, like a game like this, I think this sort of features which I faced in the VR segment, i think this makes the game a lot interesting than the non-VR version.

Interviewer: Okay. So now let's talk about the zipline, okay? So which one kind of like you preferred between both the versions?

Participant: Uh yeah, so basically I faced two types of zipline in the game. Like the normal one and there was this rope section. Um, um should i tell about that also?

Interviewer: Yeah, yeah.

Participant: OK, so basically, so basically yeah that portion was also uh um. I, I got difficulties with, I got difficulties with. But um after I, again after I got the hang of it like how I should do it, so it gave me a sense of accomplishment again at that time. So yeah there was a little bit of learning to do. But in

terms of like, um, again immersion I believe the VR version did it better, but if in terms of, um, less complicity or in terms of like um, um sort of like what should they say like, accessibility, I believe the non-VR version was better, like yeah.

Interviewer: So now as you have interacted in a bit different way in between the both versions, which would you rate us more satisfying to do?

Participant: Um, I would say the VR version is more, more satisfying, because like I said earlier because, um, there are a lot of factors in here I believe. Um, um, since this is the same game which has VR and non-VR version, um if you count all the aspects, uh, I believe the VR version is the more suitable one. Because in the non-VR version, I believe like the actions that the player has to take those are very linear or those are very non-complicated. So it's like, um, it's like very simple or easy thing to do. Like there is, I think a very little factor of accomplishments or like someone who plays video games, for them I think a little bit of, um, there's very small things of accomplishment or to do.

So in the VR version I believe there are things that um when you interact with it gives you a more purposeful behavior. So yeah, overall if I count everything I think the VR version will get the upper hand for me.

Interviewer: Okay. **So now, you're kind of like in both the games, you are kind of like controlling a character. But in the VR version you're performing the actions, and in the PC version you're kind of like controlling a character which is performing the action. So did you like perceive it this way or was it kind of like different to you? Like did you feel more embodiment the VR version, like you are the character itself rather than you are controlling a character?**

Participant: **Yes. Definitely, definitely.**

Interviewer: Okay. So you would say that the physical effort that you had to pull in the VR version was positive?

Participant: Yes. At first it was a little bit difficult but when I got used to it I believe it was really fun, yeah.

Interviewer: Okay, cool. So now let's talk about the control schemes between the both versions. So which version VR or PC which gave you more control over the controls itself? Like which was easier to perform movements and actions?

Participant: **Um, definitely the non-VR version was easier. Because, um, once again I have, uh, familiarities with the controls with the gamepad or with the non-VR games. So like it was, um, sort of**

like a muscle memory to me. So I didn't have much difficulties controlling the player with the controller. But in the VR version again I had to learn a lot of things. Um, there is nothing in my muscle memory. So the camera movement and the, uh, the rotational movement and the character movement, I had a little difficulty with the synergies, to perform the synergies with those things.

So, um, in a lot of segments like where I have to like disable a particular robot, i have to move in a certain way to get behind that robot. So in the VR version I had some difficulties like, I have to, um, you know like move my head, and also rotate the camera and then move forward. So those things were a little bit of difficult for me but I enjoyed it, I enjoyed it. But in terms of accessibility and difficulty wise I think the non-VR version was easier for me.

Interviewer: So were there any interactions that felt awkward in either versions?

Participant: Sorry.

Interviewer: Were there any interactions that you felt awkward in either versions?

Participant: Um, basically, the one on the lift i think. Um, whenever I was pressing the button there's sort of like jittering effects. So apart from that, there's also the little experience, when I was trying to climb the ladder and I got too close to the ladder and sort of like I was inside the ladder or something on the other part, that portion, and apart from these two experiences everything was fine.

Interviewer: So would you say that everything apart from these two were particularly smooth?

Participant: Smooth. Definitely, yes.

Interviewer: So now let's compare your experience of sneaking and disabling the robots. So did it felt like, um, how would you like compare them between the two versions?

Participant: Um, the non-VR version one was like very straightforward and simple. Basically you use your sonar to detect the enemies from behind the wall and basically you track their movements and you try to go sneak up on them and you just disable them. It's quite simple, any stealth-based video games have this sort of segment. But in the VR, the one thing that was very interesting to me was like, I can sort of like peek behind a wall and sort of can see, like the enemy can't see me but I can see the enemy. In the non-VR version i don't believe you can do that. So that part was really interesting to me.

When I found out this feature, I used it, and I think this was very interesting. Like I can see the enemy and I can track his movement. I can, I don't need to use the sonar. I can yes, I use the sonar to track the

enemy like where he is, but then once I got behind the wall and sort of like peeked onto him that gave me a sort of like very immersive experience I think.

Interviewer: Okay. So now this is kind of like a hypothetical question but I would love to ask and know your opinion about it. So as you already know that this game has a lot of crouching, you know to not get detected by the robots. So in the beginning, uh, when I was developing the game, you play the final version which kind of like incorporates button-based crouching for both the versions, right? But in the beginning of the development I had, uh, implemented physical crouching in VR. So you had to crouch in real life to crouch in VR version, okay? So it was not button-based at all. But then I kind of like discarded that feature because, it was a lot of crouching and it was very physically demanding.

So, do you think it would have been a good feature to include or do you think it's just better this way on how you played it?

Participant: I think I would have liked it more if there was like a physical crouch feature for me personally. But just as also you said, um, there are a lot of crouching movements in the game. So, yeah I think it also might have been a little bit of tiring, because you have to like sit there in a crouch position for a long time. Um, but definitely I would like to play but I would have want to play that version also, like physical crouch one.

Interviewer: So, which version would you say is easier to learn?

Participant: Easier to learn? Definitely, non-VR version.

Interviewer: Do you kind of like give the credit to the muscle memory that you have?

Participant: Definitely, yeah. The years of experience of playing video games, that's definitely there.

Interviewer: Which version did you felt kind of like invited you to be like, you had more freedom when you were approaching a situation? Like for example, if you were trying to disable a robot which version made you feel like, uh, you kind of like was not restricted in any way when you were trying to disable it?

Participant: Um, I think my, I think my opinion will be a little bit of biased because, um, in the VR version like I said earlier that I had a little difficulty with controlling my player or myself. Like the camera movements, and the, um, XY movements, the coordination wasn't there at the beginning. So I faced a little bit of difficulties there. So yeah I think that's because I don't have a lot of experience with VR most likely because of that. But, um, generally I, I would say both version did well, but I'd give credit to the non-VR version on this, because I had easier accessibility there.

Interviewer: I kind of like want to ask you a question because, uh, the tests I performed before this, um, most of them had this as a suggestion to me. Would you have preferred that you could move just like you move in the PC version, in the VR too? Rather than having this head-based movement would you have preferred to move like a normal controller thumbstick movement, left right, and forward, and backward in any direction?

Participant: Uh, I think that would have been, um, much more easier to control I think. Because that's the control scheme that, uh, we usually use in non-VR games. So for me, I think, uh, I think that would have been a better experience for me personally. Yeah, that would have been a better experience for me.

Interviewer: Okay, and what about the way you kind of like rotate your character in the VR version. Because it has kind of like this varying degrees of snapping movements. This is kind of like a design that is also followed in VR development. But there is also the option to have like a smooth rotation. But it's kind of like when I was designing the game, I thought people may get motion sick because I tend to get motion sick very easily, and when I kind of like implemented this smooth rotation feature, I kind of like got dizzy very soon. So I then discarded the feature and I implemented this snap rotation that you kind of like move your controller, the right thumbstick, and you're kind of like rotating 30 degrees rather than having this smooth motion.

So do you think you would have preferred like the smooth motion, or was the snap rotation fine in your case?

Participant: Um, I think at first I need to experience that myself, because I don't know, if like, uh, people get dizzy or motion sickness in general, in that smooth camera movement. But I think I would have preferred the smooth camera movements. Definitely, yeah.

Interviewer: So, let's move in the comfort section now. Did you feel any kind of motion sickness, dizziness, nausea, eye strain, physical discomfort during your gameplay?

Participant: Well, I, uh, no not necessarily, but I felt a little bit of weight on my head and a little bit of eye strain. Because, I think, I, um, sort of like messed up with the focus thing, I felt like I did it well. But at some points some particular angles or some particular things did become a little bit of blurry. But, um, those are not very big issues, very small issues. But overall, yes I had a very good experience, nothing that severe.

Interviewer: But you would certainly rate the PC version to be more comfortable?

Participant: Definitely. Definitely, yeah.

Interviewer: So, do you think you kind of like went, uh, around 40 minutes in the VR version straight. Do you think it was fine or do you think it would have been better if you could take some rest in between?

Participant: Um, I think it would have been better if I took some rest.

Interviewer: Okay. So when you were approaching the robots, did you feel both of the version had the same kind of psychological impact on you? Like did you feel more anxious or stressed in the VR version because of the presence you mentioned?

Participant: Yeah. Definitely I felt more anxious because, because yeah, it was very up close with the robots, and also like the robot caught me quite a bit of times in the VR version, and when the robot, um, got to me it felt like a little bit of threatening, like more threatening than the non-VR version. So definitely the interaction with the robots were, like, felt more real in the VR version.

Interviewer: So, after you removed the headset did you feel any physical discomfort or disorientation?

Participant: Um, like, a little bit of eye strain I believe, or i think it occurred because of the weight, I believe because of the VR. Because I don't have that much experience with the VR and also wearing a VR headset. So I think it happened because of particularly that reason, and I believe if I use VR more often, VR headset, I believe that issue will no longer occur.

Interviewer: Okay, now let's move to the comparative analysis between the two versions, okay? So, as you have played both the versions now. Now if i give you the choice to play only one, which one would you choose and why?

Participant: Um, I think I would choose the VR version, because I had more fun playing it, and also the sense of immersion, I think works better with the VR version than the non-VR version.

Interviewer: Okay, and can you like name multiple or a single thing that the VR version did better than the PC version in general?

Participant: Um, yeah, because like I said the, the game basically had a set of actions right? Like you pull the lever or you press the buttons. So, uh, in the non-VR version all of this, uh, felt pretty streamlined and like, like pretty simple. But, I think I have never believed that this simple sort of actions can be like fun and engaging, all right, when I've played the non-VR version first. But after playing the VR version this little bit of actions and tasks, like you have to climb a ladder, and you have

to use the zipline, you have to press, um, button to activate the elevator. All of these actions they seem really fun and engaging.

So I think that's a really good aspect that's a, that's the part of the VR segment that I liked, and I think you cannot have those kind of experience in a non-VR video game. So, for me those sort of particular little bit of things made the game a lot more interesting than the non-VR version.

Interviewer: So you kind of like, the physicality of the VR version much much better than the PC version?

Participant: Yes, definitely.

Interviewer: Okay, so can you like do the vice versa for me. Can you name one thing that you felt the PC version did better than the VR version?

Participant: Um, I think accessibility, that like I've speaking about it a lot, because, uh, and also, um, yeah the accessibility the first thing. Because the control schemes and the tasks are like, those are very easy to do and you don't have to like look around and find stuff. You can just you know use your right stick to like control the camera and everything. So basically, um, it's a very relaxed way to play a video game, like the non-VR version was a very relaxed way. So, yeah there were not much of physical movements and everything. So, yeah I think in those portion you know, the non-VR version was quite good.

Interviewer: Okay, so let's, let's talk about the specific mechanics one more time. For climbing the ladder, which one would you prefer in the end, and why do you think that you would prefer that?

Participant: Um, for like um, uh, I think for the ladder, I think for the fun aspect I would prefer the VR version definitely. Because, um, I had to synergize both my hands in the right position to climb up the ladder, and I think that was, that was kind of fun. But in the non-VR version is like, you press a button and you just climb upwards. So I prefer the VR version, yeah.

Interviewer: Okay, so for the zipline, which felt more exciting the VR or the PC?

Participant: Definitely, the VR one, because when I press the button, and the zipline starts, and sort of like my camera was on the opposite direction. So when I moved my head and it felt like, I am on the zipline, so it was immersive, so yeah.

Interviewer: Just for clarification I'm going to ask this one more time, for disabling the robots, you felt the VR version was more engaging?

Participant: Yes, yes, definitely more engaging but it was also more difficult. Yeah.

Interviewer: So, can you say what was your most memorable moment in the VR version?

Participant: The most memorable moment would definitely be, um, the rope, using the rope from the position A to position B, like I had to focus a lot, because I only failed once and I got dropped, uh, down. So, I think that portion was like very exciting for me, like I had to do it, I have to complete. So that sort of motivation, so yeah that for sure.

Interviewer: What about the PC version, were there any moments that you felt particularly special in the PC version?

Participant: Um, the thing that I loved the most on the PC version, um, disabling the robot segment. Like, the level was designed in such a way that, um, you can like disable multiple robots without getting noticed or without getting seen, and that, that thing was implemented very well I believe.

Because, I play a lot of Assassin's Creed games, so there's a lot of stealth based sections there in which, you have to go completely still, then nobody can see you to sort of assassinate your targets. So, I felt a lot of similar vibes in those segments. So, for the PC version I believe those were the most fun segments for me.

Interviewer: Okay, so would you be willing to sacrifice the comfort and accessibility to get VR's immersion?

Participant: It depends I believe, it depends. Um, I think VR can definitely be immersive, but I don't think it can be immersive in every bit of genre, I believe. I think VR has sort of like a particular genre of video games that can feel very immersed with VR definitely. But there are also a lot of different type of video games or genres, which I believe a lot of players are, including me would prefer non-VR or just normal desktop version.

Interviewer: So you think that genre makes a lot of difference?

Participant: Yes, yes, definitely.

Interviewer: Vice versa would you be willing to sacrifice VR's immersion to experience PC's comfort and familiarity? So it's kind of like also the same genre based question.

Participant: Yeah, definitely the same similar answer.

Interviewer: Great. So if you want to suggest one thing that you think will make the VR experience better what would that be?

Participant: Um, particularly for this game or like in general?

Interviewer: For this game.

Participant: For this game, um, uh, okay, uh, first, firstly I think, um, when I, uh, used the sonar like it pinpointed the location objectives for me. So those were very, uh, very small green cubicle things. So, I think, I at first, I had a little bit of problems with finding those because, um, and, I believe I didn't find any clear instructions or maybe I've missed it. But **I think the objectives should be marked a little more like, um, visible or like more prominent to the gamer.** I think that would be a really good addition.

Apart from that, um, apart from that, well the robot AI, yeah those are a little bit easier in the non-VR version. But in the VR version I think they're in the perfect difficulty mode. So that's also good. So yeah, I think basically those objectives if they could be a little bit more visible, I think that would be a good addition.

Interviewer: Okay, and what would you say about the PC version, what could make the experience better for you?

Participant: Um, for the PC version, I think everything is, everything is quite good for the PC version. I haven't found any sort of like thing that could be upgraded. So, I think it's all good in the PC version.

Interviewer: So, as you have tried both versions, would you be interested in playing more VR games?

Participant: Yeah, definitely.

Interviewer: Okay, and why do you think that it sparks your interest?

Participant: Um, um, basically as I've said earlier, I don't have many experience with VR. But like this is probably the first game, which has different sort of mechanics. Like I had to do a lot of things in VR, and I found it very interesting. **For me, it is the interesting part, like I said in the comparison earlier, like a very normal thing in a non-VR game can be a very interesting thing in a VR game, and that is the first time I'm experiencing this.** So, definitely I want to try out more VR games with this type of experience.

Interviewer: Okay. Is there anything else that you want to add about your experience in either versions?

Participant: Uh, no. I think I've literally spoke about every aspect of my experience, so yeah.

Interviewer: So, thank you so much for your time and patience.

Participant: Thank you also, yeah.

Interview – 09

Play Pattern

1. PCVR

2. PC

Interviewer: Okay, thank you so much for testing the prototype and attending the interview session. So I'm going to give you some background about my thesis, which is the comparative analysis of sensory engagement, user control, and comfort between virtual reality and non-virtual reality games. So by sensory engagement, I'm mostly focusing on the presence and the immersion that you feel between the two versions, and by the user control, I'm kind of focusing on the control schemes, and by comfort, I'm mostly focusing on the comfort between the two versions in general.

Interviewer: Let's get some backgrounds about you first. So can you tell me like what type of games do you generally play and how often?

Participant: I usually play all types of games in various genres. It could be first-person shooters to like static games, city building, etc.

Interviewer: How often do you generally play?

Participant: A few days a week.

Interviewer: Okay, like is it like the frequency, you can say, do you have like any minimum hours in general every week or is it like very variable in general?

Participant: I think I would usually put it around 10 hours a week.

Interviewer: 10 hours. Okay, that works. So, have you used VR before, and if you have, what kind of medium have you kind of like experienced in VR? It can be 360 videos, it can be immersive experiences, it can be games, like any kind of medium in general.

Participant: Yes, I've tried VR before. I have a meta quest that I use to play games, and I've had the opportunity to experience both like full-on immersive games to like immersive experiences or like demos and 360 videos and everything.

Interviewer: Okay, so let's move to the next section and let's talk about the sensory engagement part. Okay, so which version, VR or PC, which made you feel more present in the game itself, and why do you think it made you feel that way?

Participant: I think I would be inclined towards the VR version, mostly because how you like perceive the environment and mostly how it feels to be up close and personal with the game. So, for example, you can see your hands in the game. That's like one step into immersion. So, you have to physically touch the bots to disable them, whereas on the PC version you don't have that. So, that's kind of like a huge difference between the desktop and the VR version.

On the VR version you also have like a sense of scale. So, overall pacing, you can like go through the PC version easily, but on VR your brain kind of tricks you to take it slow and be careful. So, yeah, the VR.

Interviewer: Okay. So, one of the distinct features of the prototype was the varying heights of the buildings, and when I was designing the level I was more inclining towards dystopiac environments and dystopiac ideas of environments, and one of the main features of a dystopiac society or environment is buildings, very high buildings in general. So, and you can also kind of like, you go through the five blocks and it has an inner meaning. It has kind of like a social discrimination between the design itself.

Like you go from a building, which is like a 30 meter height, has a 30 meter height, and then you go to the next section, which is like 50 meter heights of buildings, and in the end, it's kind of like the elite series, which is like 100 meters high buildings and high rises and stops like that. So, it's kind of like, and there's like robots, a bit of sci-fi elements inside it. So, it had, I tried to capture as much as I could with just blocks in general for a dystopic environment.

So, how did you like perceived the height, which is kind of like important feature of the prototype in both versions?

Participant: For the height, I think, I didn't feel like the difference between like different levels, but I did get the feeling of like going up as you progress. So, that kind of like gives me a sense of progress.

Interviewer: Like, does it give you the sense of increasing difficulty too?

Participant: Yeah, definitely. I like how like the height gets more and more and you have to like climb a huge ladder.

Interviewer: Okay, sounds good. So, now let's talk about the interactions a bit. How would you differ your experience of climbing a ladder physically on contrast to climbing a ladder with buttons?

Participant: It really generally takes more effort, that I can say.

Interviewer: Do you think that the physical effort that you're putting in the VR version, is it like affecting you in a positive way or in a negative way or in a neutral way?

Participant: I think positive way that like gives lasting impression.

Interviewer: Okay, like it gives you a sense of achievement, right?

Participant: Yeah, definitely.

Interviewer: What about the rope mechanics between the two versions like the VR and the non-VR, how do you differ that experience?

Participant: In VR, they are definitely scarier.

Interviewer: Okay. So, was it like very hard to catch the core of the mechanics and pass that section in VR or was it fine from your end?

Participant: It seemed generally straight-forward to me.

Interviewer: Okay, and do you think the block in the middle which you can rest on is a good idea or do you think that stretch that you have to cross with the rope, it could have been like a single stretch without any kind of breaks in the middle?

Participant: I think that was necessary. You kind of get tired moving your hands in a specific motion.

Interviewer: Okay. So, how would you differ your experience with the physical levers that you pull and the buttons that you press in the PC version to work on the lever, and the lifts, and the console buttons in general? Like you literally push them. How do you kind of differ the experience in your case?

Participant: Well, it's like a totally different experience, especially the lever. I like that, and pressing down on things like that gives you like a very good immersion.

Interviewer: Okay. Did you like feel that it was very natural to see the button and press it up?

Participant: Yeah, definitely.

Interviewer: Okay, and overall, which interactions felt more satisfying between the VR controls or the PC?

Participant: Definitely the VR.

Interviewer: Why do you think that way?

Participant: As I said earlier, because of the hands, how you interact with the environment, that's the main focus.

Interviewer: So, you think that the physicality adds a lot to the overall feel, right?

Participant: Yeah, definitely. It's like a whole different game.

Interviewer: So, in which version, the VR or the PC, you kind of like, did you like felt the difference when you kind of like controlling your character? Because in VR, it kind of feels like, as you already mentioned, that the scale of sense is quite real. So, it kind of like, was it achievable in that sense that it gave you the feeling that you are the character itself rather than you are controlling a character?

Participant: Uh, so in the VR version, I cared for the player. So, when he got shot or like got into sticky situations, then yeah, that felt like I was in the player's shoes. So, that felt personal. But on the PC version, I didn't care if he died or what or like if I lost. So, I didn't care anything.

Interviewer: So, just for clarification, you would say that the physical effort you put in VR was positive, right?

Participant: Yeah. Right.

Interviewer: Okay.

Interviewer: So, now let's move to the user control section and what do you think, which version, VR or PC, which gave you like a better sense of controls over the movements and the actions?

Participant: There's a few different factors here. On the VR version, to be able to physically test the interactable items in the game, that was great. But due to like a long familiarity with controls in the PC version, that was like too easy to control.

Interviewer: So, you say that the sense of control or ease of access was much, much higher in the PC version, but it was more enjoyable in the VR version itself?

Participant: Yes. Right.

Interviewer: Okay. Were there any interactions in general in either versions that you felt awkward, was not up to the mark?

Participant: I would say like not being able to move left to right on the VR version, that's the only thing.

Interviewer: Okay, and regarding the PC version, everything was good?

Participant: Climbing the ladder, because it was like a linear action.

Interviewer: So, were there anything that felt particularly smooth, that you felt was kind of like out of the box, you really loved it?

Interviewer: Yeah, I overall loved the whole, like all of the in-game mechanics of the VR version.

Interviewer: Okay. So, as you already mentioned that when you were kind of like sneaking and you were getting caught while kind of interacting with the robots, and it felt more kind of like you cared about the player in the VR version. So, do you think that when you were approaching the situation in that case, did you felt like more restricted in the VR version or did you felt like you were approaching the situation with more freedom in general?

Participant: Um, I would say restricted, like in a mental sense, because like, it kind of feels like you're there. So, yeah.

Interviewer: Okay. Okay. So, this is kind of like a hypothetical question, but I also want to know your opinion about it. So, this game, when I first designed it, you played both of the versions in a button-based-crouch way. So, you crouch with a button in both the versions, but in the beginning there was physical crouching in the VR version, where you had to like, and it was a standing experience instead, not a sitting experience, right? Like how you played it now.

So, you have to stand and when you have to crouch, you have to crouch yourself physically to be crouched in the game itself. So, do you think it was a good idea or do you think it is good as it is right now?

Participant: I would say yes and no, because it's like a sitting experience. I was like, I didn't feel the need to use the crouch button because I was like, in my mind I was already sitting. But on the previous version, when I'm standing, that kind of gives you like an inner thought, like if I sit down.

Interviewer: So, but do you think that this physical crouching would just add an extra layer of physicality to the game because it's kind of like, as you already mentioned, the interactions was really fun in VR.

Participant: Yes, I think so.

Interviewer: So, in the end, which version was easier to learn, VR or PC?

Participant: PC was easier to learn.

Interviewer: Why do you think so? Like, which thing will you give the credit that it's easier to learn in PC, like your experience with controllers in general?

Participant: Just because like, it's the familiar layout for PC. So, you kind of expect which button to do what, but in VR, that's more like real life. But in this game, yes, there is like a, you expected something to do, some kind of interaction then it did.

Interviewer: Okay. So, now let's move to the comfort part. Did you experience any kind of motion sickness, nausea, vertigo, or any eye strain after you kind of like put down the VR?

Participant: No, it was pretty much like a moderate experience, nothing extreme.

Interviewer: So, was the speed okay for you, or do you think it would have been better if you could move a bit faster in the VR version?

Participant: It was perfect for me.

Interviewer: Okay. So, will you give the credit to the PC version to be physically comfortable overall? Or, was it fine for you in the VR version too?

Participant: I like both versions. Both versions were comfortable, but VR was enjoyable.

Interviewer: Okay. So, how long do you think that you can continue a game like this in VR? Like in one single session?

Participant: I think an hour at most.

Interviewer: So, now we come to the interesting question that when robots were nearby, in the VR version or the PC version, did you feel any kind of extra anxiety or stress while dealing with them?

Participant: Yes, definitely I did.

Interviewer: Which version do you think that made you feel more anxious?

Participant: The VR version.

Interviewer: Why do you think that?

Participant: Because I'm seeing them with my own eyes and the whole way the VR works is like to give you the experience that you're inside the game. So, yeah, that kind of like gives you like a defensive response from your brain. So, that kind of like gives you stress.

Interviewer: Was the human scale a factor in the overall stressing situation? Like, did it make you more stressed that you're kind of like perceiving them as in a human scale sense? Like they're kind of like your same height and everything?

Participant: Yes.

Interviewer: So, after removing the VR headset, did you feel any kind of disorientation?

Participant: No.

Interviewer: Okay, great. Sounds good.

Interviewer: So, now let's move to the main gist of the whole discussion, the comparative analysis between the two versions. So, as you have played both versions already, now if I give you the option to choose only one, which one would you choose to play?

Participant: The VR version.

Interviewer: Why do you think that?

Participant: It's generally more enjoyable.

Interviewer: Okay, and can you name something that the VR version did miles good than the PC version?

Participant: I would say like getting caught by the robots, getting detected by the robots because you're like standing there helplessly while they come and shoot you. So, that kind of gives you like a new sense of fear.

Interviewer: What about vice versa? Like, was there anything that the PC version did better than the VR version in general?

Participant: I think in the PC version, I liked the overall, the camera shakes and everything.

Interviewer: Do you think that the movement is also better in the PC version rather than the VR? Like the overall control?

Participant: Yeah, like you have two joysticks there. So, it was easy to move around.

Interviewer: So, finally for climbing the ladder, which version would you prefer now?

Participant: VR version.

Interviewer: Why do you think that you prefer the VR version? Was it because of the physicality you mentioned that you have to like literally interact with it in a real life sense?

Participant: Yeah. Turns out it's very much fun to climb ladders in VR.

Interviewer: For the zipline? Which version do you prefer?

Participant: Sorry?

Interviewer: For the zipline.

Participant: I would prefer the PC version for that.

Interviewer: Why do you prefer the PC version?

Participant: The overall like visual feeling.

Interviewer: Like the camera shakes, feedbacks and everything?

Participant: Yeah. Camera shakes and feedbacks.

Interviewer: Okay, and for disabling the robots, would you just say that the VR version was more engaging in general?

Participant: Yeah. Because of how the movement worked in the VR version, you have to like make statistical choices. So, yeah, that was more like you have to do everything carefully.

Interviewer: Do you agree with the difficulty that the VR version had for the robots or do you think it could have been a bit more difficult or a bit more easier?

Participant: I think it's now in a sweet spot.

Interviewer: Okay, cool. So, what was your most memorable moment in the VR version?

Participant: Oh, when I got shot.

Interviewer: What kind of feeling that it gave you?

Participant: I wish I could snatch the gun.

Interviewer: What about the vice-versa, what about PC version? Was there anything particular that you really loved?

Participant: I loved moving round and round around the robots.

Interviewer: Yeah, they're kind of like slow.

Participant: Yeah.

Interviewer: So, will you be willing to sacrifice comfort of playing in a PC to enjoy the immersion in VR?

Participant: Yes.

Interviewer: You would do that?

Participant: Yeah.

Interviewer: Okay, and what about the vice-versa? Would you sacrifice the immersion of VR to enjoy the comfort of PC?

Participant: Maybe sometimes, if I have like a physical issue.

Interviewer: Okay, and do you think that genre matters in this sense? That if, for example, this was kind of like a traversal stealth game, you can say, right? But, for example, it's like a tower defense game. Would you like care about playing it in VR at all or would you just play it in PC rather than playing it in VR?

Participant: Well, it depends on how the game is made. Like, if I'm looking at it from top down, then I would say no. But, if I'm like looking down from the tower itself and operating the machinery, then yes.

Interviewer: Okay. So, after playing the game, what do you think that could make the VR experience much better? Is there anything that you want to mention about it?

Participant: More freedom of movement, I would say.

Interviewer: Like, moving left, right? Did you like the rotation, snap rotation?

Participant: Yeah, that helps with motion sickness for me.

Interviewer: Okay. So, you don't think that it would have been much better if you could move smoothly on all the axes?

Participant: Yeah, I would not prefer that. I'm more inclined towards using snap and like, for smaller adjustment, I can just move myself.

Interviewer: So, you kind of like sometimes switch to the teleport mode, but did you just do it for the accessibility or was the speed of the movement uncomfortable for you?

Participant: Yeah, that would be for accessibility because of like, in certain situations where I felt that I could use left-right movement, so that's when I opted to use the teleport.

Interviewer: Now, what about vice versa? What is, if you have to name a suggestion that could make the PC experience better?

Participant: I think ramping up the difficulty a bit.

Interviewer: On the AI?

Participant: On the AI and like, reducing the movement speed of the player. I think overall like, in VR, you have to like, carefully position yourself. But on PC, that's kind of careless. So, more aggressive detection would be better. Like, if you're like, in front of the robot, they could like, detect you instantly.

Interviewer: So, after trying both versions, would you be interested in playing more VR games?

Participant: Yeah, definitely.

Interviewer: Why do you think that you would be more interested in playing or trying VR games?

Participant: Because like, I haven't played any VR games in this genre and this felt like, really, really interesting compared to what I've played on PC so far for the same genre, and this gives you like, more, better feelings.

Interviewer: So, this combination of stealth and traversal is a good mix?

Participant: Yes.

Interviewer: So, finally, is there anything else that you want to add regarding the development, regarding the game design or environment design or anything at all?

Participant: Well, the world building felt good, even if it's blocks, but I see the vision. So, yeah, I definitely like the game.

Interviewer: As you have, I think, already guessed that, in the game design, the environment itself kind of like, speaks to you in a way, with colors. So, anything that's yellow, you know that you can instantly interact with it. So, did this theology confuse you on the ladder, or was it like your instinct that you have to hold the rungs rather than the poles? **Because the poles were gray and the rungs were yellow, but on the other cases, everything that's yellow is interactable, but on the ladder it's not.**

Participant: **Yeah, I think you're right. I usually reach for the yellow part of the ladder first.**

Interviewer: Do you think this was the reason? Do you think that maybe if we kind of like switch the colors, it would make more sense that you would rather grab the poles rather than the rungs?

Participant: Yes.

Interviewer: Okay. So, anything else you want to add?

Participant: No. All good.

Interviewer: Okay. Thank you so much for participating, and I appreciate your time and effort.

Interview – 10

Play Pattern

1. PCVR

2. PC

Interviewer: Okay, so first of all, thank you so much for attending the playtest sessions and now attending the interview. I really appreciate your time and effort. So I'm going to give you some background about my thesis first.

My thesis topic, word by word, is comparative analysis between sensory engagement, comfort and control between virtual reality and non-virtual reality games. So by sensory engagement, I'm more inclining towards the immersion and presence that you felt during the gameplay of the both versions. By the control, I'm kind of inclining to discuss the control schemes that you tried in both the versions, and in your case, one of them is keyboard and mouse and one of them is motion controllers, and by comfort, I'm inclining to discuss the comfort level between the two versions that you tried.

So let's get some backgrounds about you first. Can you tell me like what type of games do you usually play and how often do you play them?

Participant: I generally play like different games. Some of my favorite games are Assassin's Creed and The Witcher. I also love games with beautiful landscapes like Horizon Zero Dawn and The Forbidden West. I also love Death Standing a lot.

Interviewer: How often do you usually play?

Participant: I generally play games whenever I have time after like completing my daily task. So the time is quite like variable. Sometimes I play 10 to 20 hours in a week, sometimes I don't play for a while.

Interviewer: Okay. So have you used VR before today? If like yes, how much VR experience would you say you have?

Participant: I have used VR before, but my experience is quite limited. I have played some simple FPS games in VR. I also tried a bit of like Assassin's Creed Nexus, and Beat Saber.

Interviewer: Okay, sounds good. So now let's move to the next section of our conversation, which is I want to talk about the immersion and presence that you felt during the gameplay. So which version, VR or PC, made you feel more present in the game world and why?

Participant: Definitely the VR one, because it gave me a feeling as if I was present inside the game. It definitely felt more real and I enjoyed it more.

Interviewer: As you have seen already, that the game has varying heights of buildings and the game is mostly played on the rooftops of the buildings itself. So the building, I wanted to design a dystopian world when I was kind of trying to design the game itself in the beginning, and one of the very distinct features of a dystopian world is to have very high-rise buildings and also rogue robots and sci-fi elements to it. So the height is kind of like a very important design decision in the game.

So how did experiencing the heights and rooftops differed between VR and PC for you?

Participant: The VR version felt more real because of the depth. In VR, I felt the heights in a more realistic way.

Interviewer: Okay, so how would you describe, like, what was it like to physically climb ladders in VR compared to pressing a button to climb in PC?

Participant: Climbing the ladder, like, physically was more fun because I felt like I was actually doing something rather than controlling a character in a game. So I would vote for the VR in this case.

Interviewer: Great. So how did physically grabbing the rope differed in VR compared to the version in PC?

Participant: My answer would be the same. Though I struggled a lot with the rope, I finally completed it after seven to eight tries and it was quite satisfying. It demanded a lot of physical effort, which was at times stressing, but really entertaining in the end.

Interviewer: Okay, so what was your experience of, like, physically reaching to push buttons and pull the levers in VR compared to pressing keyboard keys in PC?

Participant: In this case, I would again vote for VR, because of the realism and physicality. I enjoyed pushing the buttons and pulling the lever, because I found a lot of similarities on how you do it in this real life. So definitely, I, it was more enjoyable in VR than PC.

Interviewer: Okay, sounds great. So, okay, so can you say, like, overall, which felt most satisfying to you? Like, the physical interactions in VR or the button controls in PC, and please also say, why did you feel that way?

Participant: Um, I would say VR because of the factors I already mentioned, like, realism of the interaction with real life and the physicality it demanded to perform the action.

Interviewer: Okay, so now let's talk about the next section, the embodiment and effort that you needed in the gameplay. So, in which version VR or PC, did it feel more like you were performing the action versus controlling a character?

Participant: Definitely, it's the VR, because of the scale that you can feel in the environment, the ladder, the rope, the zipline, everything felt like, life-like, because of the scale according to the real human. The height of the robot, the depth that I would feel while looking down from buildings felt like very real, which resulted in better embodiment of the character.

Interviewer: Okay, so how did the physical effort, because this game required a lot of physical effort, especially in the VR version. So, how would you describe the feeling of the physical effort required in VR, how it affected your performance, like, was it positive, negative, or neutral?

Participant: The physical effort that I had to put in the VR version was mostly positive. I enjoyed the ladder, though, like, I got confused when where to hold on the ladder at the start of the game. The rope was also very satisfying when I was able to scale it until the end, though, in the beginning, it was stressing when I was falling constantly from it.

Interviewer: Okay, so now let's talk about a bit on the control schemes of the two games. In your case, you used keyboard and mouse for the PC gameplay and motion controllers for the VR. So, which version, VR or PC, gave you better control over your movements and actions?

Participant: I would say the controls were much easier to get a grasp on PC. It was not because the VR had bad controls, but rather because I'm more familiar with the layout on PC. I also love the head-based movement in VR, but I would have preferred if the rotation was smooth rather than snapping to certain degrees.

Interviewer: Okay, so were there, like, any interactions that felt awkward in either version? Were there any that felt particularly smooth?

Participant: I would say the rope in VR. I was having a hard time because the rope got inside my player and it was uncomfortable. At times, I wouldn't see what was in front properly and I also had a hard time grabbing the rope on the next position.

Interviewer: Okay, so can you, like, compare your experience of sneaking and using EMP to disable robots in VR versus PC?

Participant: The experience was much interactive in VR because I felt like I was, like, pressing my hands against the robot from behind to switch them off rather than getting on a range and just pressing a button. I also pressed the button in VR to disable them, but the feeling of touching them from behind was fun and more interactive.

Interviewer: Okay, so this is kind of like a hypothetical question. When I was developing the game in the beginning, I had physical crouching based controls in the VR version, which kind of, like, worked in this way that you had to crouch in real life to crouch in the game, and as you have already played both of the versions, you know that there is a lot of crouching involved in the game to sneak past the robots.

So then I kind of transitioned towards the button based crouching for both of the versions, the VR and the PC, because I think at times it was quite stressing on the body itself and was quite physically demanding. So, as the game involves a lot of crouching to stay hidden, do you think physical crouching would have made sense or is this button based crouching is more on-line?

Participant: I think physical crouching would have been more enjoyable and interactive, but as there was indeed a lot of crouching while playing the game, I personally think I wouldn't have been able to play the game for a long time in VR while crouching and standing all the time. So the experience of playing the game would have been more stressing rather than being entertaining and fun.

Interviewer: Okay, so which version would you credit VR or PC was easier to learn and why?

Participant: I would again say PC as I'm quite familiar with the layout of the PC version. I am probably a bit biased towards it.

Interviewer: Okay, so in which version VR or PC, did you feel more freedom to approach situations in your own way?

Participant: Hmm, PC version provided me more freedom to explore the surroundings, because again, I am more familiar with the PC controls. So it naturally came to me and I wasn't stressed about it, the controls at all. It was like mostly muscle memories kicking.

Interviewer: So, let's talk about the comfort section of the conversation now, and did you like experience any emotional sickness, dizziness, nausea, eye strain or physical discomfort during the VR gameplay, and if you have, can you describe that feeling?

Participant: Mostly no, though I felt a bit dizzy after I took off the VR headset from my head, probably because my eyes were still adjusting.

Interviewer: Okay, so which, which version VR or PC, was more physically comfortable overall? How long could you comfortably play each version? What do you think?

Participant: I can play on the PC version for at least a couple of hours while on the VR, it would mostly be around 40 to 45 minutes. Though, I enjoyed VR more, and my session was a bit longer than 45 minutes, I was feeling a bit tired.

Interviewer: Okay, so when the robots were nearby, did either version make you feel more anxious or stressed, and which version actually did made you feel more anxious or stressed if there was one and why?

Participant: Um, the VR version was more stressing due to the scale of the surroundings. For some reason, in the PC version, dying or getting caught wasn't that stressing. But in VR, I actually cared about not getting caught or shot by the robots, probably because I felt more present in the world in VR.

Interviewer: Okay, so after removing the VR headset, did you feel disoriented or experience any unusual sensations?

Participant: Like I said before, I felt a bit of dizziness when I removed my headset, because I believe my eyes were still adjusting to my surroundings.

Interviewer: Okay, so now let's move to the next part, which is kind of like the gist of the whole conversations that we're having until now, and which is the comparative analysis between the two versions. So now if you could choose only one, as you have played already both of the versions, and now if I give you the option to choose only one version that you can continue playing, would you choose VR or PC, and can you justify the reason why you would choose one?

Participant: It's a complicated question. I would say VR, if there wasn't any comfort related issue while playing the game, because I enjoyed VR more. But if we are talking about playing longer sessions, I would go with PC version for the comfort.

Interviewer: Okay, so can you tell or mention some things that the VR version did better than the PC version?

Participant: I would say interactions. In the PC version, the interactions were something that I have done many, many times in other games, and it just didn't feel that different. The VR version, however, is another story. I loved on how physical and life-like the experience was. I honestly, like, enjoyed it more.

Interviewer: So can you say the vice versa, like what did the PC version did better than the VR version, if there is anything to mention?

Participant: I would say the controls again, probably because I am more familiar with the layout on PC. I had a hard time trying to control my character in VR.

Interviewer: Okay, so now let's talk about the specific mechanics one more time, because they are kind of like the base of the whole difference between the two versions. So for climbing the ladders, which version did you prefer VR or PC, and why?

Participant: Of course, it's the VR version again, because of the physicality and life-like experience it offers. Though, I was a bit confused on where to grab when I was trying to grab it for the first time. When I did it for a number of times, it was more fun to do in VR.

Interviewer: So for the zipline, which version was more exciting for you, VR or PC and why?

Participant: I prefer the VR version, because I could move my head physically to see my surroundings.

Interviewer: Okay, so for disabling the robots, as you have already mentioned that disabling the robots in VR, induced much more anxiety and was more stressing for you. So would you say like disabling the robots felt more tense or engaging in VR, and can you say why?

Participant: As I said before, the VR version was more tense and engaging, because of the feeling of being more present in the world, due to the proper scale of the environment.

Interviewer: Okay, so can you describe your most memorable moment in the VR version?

Participant: I would say the rope climbing. Though, it was stressing in the beginning, when I completed it, I was very satisfied. Like, I was very satisfied with my accomplishment.

Interviewer: Okay, and can you say the vice versa? What was your most memorable moment in the PC version?

Participant: I really liked the fifth block of the game while I was playing in PC. I tried to experiment with different parts to disable the robots and finish the game, which was quite fun.

Interviewer: Okay, so will you be willing to sacrifice the comfort of the PC version? As you already mentioned, the PC is a bit more comfortable to play than the VR. Will you just sacrifice the comfort to get VR's immersion?

Participant: I think it depends on the genre of the game. If the game has a lot of physical reactions like this one, then I would sacrifice the comfort to enjoy VR's immersion.

Interviewer: Okay, so will you do the vice-versa? Will you sacrifice VR's immersion to get PC's comfort and familiarity?

Participant: I would say this also depends on the genre of the game. If the game is not too much physically interactive or fast-paced, then I would probably play it on PC rather than VR.

Interviewer: Okay, sounds great. So, which is the one thing that you think would make the VR experience much better?

Participant: Maybe the ability to rotate smoothly rather than having to rotate in a certain angle would be great.

Interviewer: Okay, and can you say the vice versa? Like which is one thing that you think could make the PC experience much better?

Participant: Everything was fine. From my end, the only thing I would say was missing for me was the ability to see my surroundings while I was on the zipline.

Interviewer: Okay, so as you tried both versions, and would you be interested in playing more VR games, and can you say if you would be interested, why would that be?

Participant: I think I would be interested in playing more VR games, if it has this kind of physical interactions, which are demanding, but not way too stressing on my body.

Interviewer: Okay, so is there anything else about your whole experience with either versions that you would like to share?

Participant: One particular scenario that I remember was, when I was like disabling the robots they still showed red on my sonar scan, which confused me a bit. I would say a different color would be great to indicate the player, which robot is deactivated or which is not.

Interviewer: Okay, so thank you so so much for your time, and effort and I really appreciate it, and yeah, I just want to say thank you for attending the playtest session and the interview. So I hope you have a great day.

Participant: Thank you.